

DETAILED PROGRAM

LEGEND

Plenary sessions

Oral Sessions

Poster sessions

Social Events

Professional Development events

Panel sessions

Lunches

K Keynote Presentation

SO Short Oral

YT Young Talent

 Posters

 Chairs

 Speaker

The search engine will allow you to find speakers, authors, session titles, abstract titles. You can use the "Topic" filter and the search engine to narrow your program research.

Sunday 14 July

14:00 - 20:00 | Registration Opening

 Hall Bellecour

15:30 - 16:10 | OPEN-01 | Opening Ceremony

 Amphitheatre

16:10 - 16:30 | OPEN-02 | Young IACS Award ceremony

 Amphitheatre

**16:30 - 17:20 | AW01 | 2024 Heinz Heinemann Award of IACS Lecture - Kazunari DOMEN **

 Amphitheatre

17:20 - 18:10 | AW02 | 2024 International Catalysis Award of IACS Lecture - Yuriy ROMAN-LESHKOV

 Amphitheatre

18:10 - 18:30 | AW03 | Rhodium Sponsor Lecture - Marissa REIGEL, Saint-Gobain Norpro

 Amphitheatre

18:30 - 20:00 | Welcome Reception

 Exhibition Hall

Monday 15 July

08:00 - 19:30 | Registration

Hall Bellecour

08:30 - 09:15 | PL01 | Plenary Lecture - Keiichi Tomishige: "Heterogeneous catalysis for hydrodeoxygenation of biomass-based platform chemicals"

Amphitheatre

Catherine PINEL

09:25 - 10:25 | MON-T8-01 | Characterization of catalysts and of catalytic reactions - General

Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

Gylène COSTENTIN, Miguel BANARES

09:25 - 09:45 | Quantitative Hydrogen Spillover: How Surface Entropy and Surface Hydroxyl Chemistry Drive H Spillover on Au/TiO₂ Catalysts

Bert CHANDLER - *Pennsylvania State University, United States*

09:45 - 10:05 | Direct observation of Ni nanoparticle growth in carbon supported nickel under carbon dioxide hydrogenation atmosphere

Nienke VISSER - *Materials Chemistry and Catalysis, Utrecht University, Netherlands*

10:05 - 10:25 | Exploring Reaction Mechanisms of Rh-based Nanoparticle Catalysts Using an Operando TEM System

Longshu TANG - *Graduate School of Engineering, Nagoya University, Japan*

09:25 - 10:25 | MON-T10-01 | Transient methods in heterogeneous catalysis

Tête d'or 1+2

Evgeny KONDRATENKO, Evgeniy REDEKOP

K 09:25 - 10:05 | Challenges, successes and failures in advancing the time scale of operando experiments for transient kinetic studies

Rebecca FUSHIMI - *Idaho National Laboratory*

10:05 - 10:25 | Elucidating the kind and the role of oxygen species for oxidative coupling of methane over (MnO_x)-M₂WO₄/SiO₂ (M = Na, K, Rb or Cs)

Vita KONDRATENKO - *Leibniz Institute for Catalysis, Germany*

09:25 - 10:25 | MON-T13-01 | Photocatalysis

Amphitheatre

Kazunari DOMEN, Nicolas KELLER

09:25 - 09:45 | Alternative Oxidation Reactions over Perovskite Oxynitrides for Efficient Sunlight-driven Seawater Splitting

Jeongsuk SEO - *Chonnam National University, Korea (Republic of)*

YT 09:45 - 10:05 | Development of Organic-Inorganic Hybrid Perovskite as Visible Light Photocatalyst for Solar Fuel production

Hong WANG - *University of Liverpool, United Kingdom - Chinese Academy of Sciences, China*

10:05 - 10:25 | Photoelectrochemical conversion of methane using proton exchange membrane cell with gas-diffusion photoanodes

Fumiaki AMANO - *Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan*

09:25 - 10:25 | MON-T17-01 | Catalysis in refining and petrochemistry : current and future trends

Auditorium Pasteur

Michele SARAZEN, Christophe BOUCHY

09:25 - 09:45 | Production of alkyl aromatic compounds utilizing CO₂ in Fluid Catalytic Cracking flue gas and existing refinery equipment

Koichi MATSUSHITA - *ENEOS Corporation, Japan*

SO 09:45 - 09:53 | GaO_x-based catalysts for the dehydrogenation of methanol to formaldehyde and hydrogen

Martin MUHLER - *Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry, Ruhr University Bochum, Germany*

SO 09:53 - 10:01 | Catalytic Oxidative desulphurization of Marine fuel oil: Catalyst's Deactivation phenomena

Teddy ROY - *SEGULA Technologies, France*

SO 10:01 - 10:09 | Successful Development of a Taylor-made Catalyst System for Linde's EDHOXTM Technology

Gerhard MESTL - *Clariant AG, Germany*

SO 10:09 - 10:17 | Effect of alumina support modifiers on the activity and selectivity of Ru-based Fischer-Tropsch synthesis catalysts

 Sanele MOLOI - *University of Cape Town, South Africa*

SO **10:17 - 10:25 | Investigating the Role of Metal Ratios: A Kinetic Study on SiO₂-Supported NiWMo Catalysts for High-Pressure Ring Opening Reactions**

 Christoph GROSS - *Technical University Munich, Germany*

09:25 - 10:25 | MON-T20-01 | Single-atom catalysis

 Auditorium Lumière

 Tao ZHANG, Graham HUTCHINGS

YT **09:25 - 09:45 | Chemical Kinetic Method for Active-Site Quantification in Atomically Dispersed Fe-N-C Catalysts**

 Jason S. BATES - *Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Virginia, United States*

09:45 - 10:05 | APPLICATIONS OF IN SITU/OPERANDO MÖSSBAUER SPECTROSCOPY IN SINGLE ATOM CATALYSIS

 Xuning LI - *Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, China*

10:05 - 10:25 | Advances in the X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy Characterization of Single Atom Catalysts

 Simon BARE - *SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory, United States*

09:25 - 10:25 | MON-T24-01 | Conversion of Nitrogen based small molecules (N₂, NH₃, NO_x, ...)

 Prestige Gratte Ciel

 Ilenia ROSSETTI, Xavier COURTOIS

09:25 - 09:45 | Enhanced N₂O decomposition over a technical Fe-FER catalyst: an operando IR mechanistic investigation

 Mathias LALUC - *ENERCAT ALSYS GROUP - LCS - CASALE, France*

SO **09:45 - 09:53 | Towards improved Fe-zeolites for N₂O decomposition through synthesis and catalytic descriptors from operando spectroscopy**

 Daniel CANO-BLANCO - *Paul Scherrer Institut, Switzerland - École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Switzerland*

SO **09:53 - 10:01 | In-situ XAFS Analysis of Isolated Electron-Rich Pt in Pt-Co/Al₂O₃ under NO-CO-C₃H₆-O₂ Reaction**

 Katsutoshi SATO - *Nagoya University, Japan*

SO YT **10:01 - 10:09 | Transient kinetic analysis of RHC and OHC in low temperature Standard SCR over Cu-CHA catalysts: effect of Cu loading**

SO **10:09 - 10:17 | Enhancing sulfur tolerance for LNT catalyst in coupled NSR-SCR DeNOx Technology in diesel engines**

 Sergio MOLINA-RAMÍREZ - *University of Malaga, Spain*

SO **10:17 - 10:25 | Evaluating the potential of sorption-enhanced ammonia synthesis by thermodynamic and kinetic analysis**

 Theresa KUNZ - *Institute of Chemical Engineering, Ulm University, Germany*

09:25 - 10:25 | MON-T30-01 | Catalysis for polymer synthesis, plastic recycling and upcycling

 Bellecour 1+2+3

 Ina VOLLMER, Vincent MONTEIL

09:25 - 09:45 | Chemical recycling of commercial-grade polyolefins over titania-supported ruthenium nanoparticles via hydrogenolysis

 Antonio J. MARTÍN - *Department of Chemistry and Applied Biosciences, ETH Zurich, Switzerland*

K **09:45 - 10:25 | Tandem catalytic upcycling of polyolefins: From monomers to value-added molecules**

 Susannah SCOTT - *University of California Santa Barbara, United States*

10:25 - 11:00 | Coffee Break

 Exhibition Hall

11:00 - 12:20 | MON-T8-02 | Characterization of catalysts and of catalytic reactions - General

 Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

 Stephane LORIDANT, Atsushi URAKAWA

11:00 - 11:20 | Resolving reaction behavior on a single catalytic particle

 Johannes ZEININGER - *Institute of Materials Chemistry, TU Wien, Getreidemarkt 9, 1060, Vienna, Austria, Austria*

11:20 - 11:40 | Suprabeads for catalysis – making supraparticles applicable in continuous gas-flow reactors

	Thomas ZIMMERMANN - <i>Department of Chemistry and Pharmacy, Inorganic Chemistry, Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany</i>	
SO YT	11:40 - 11:48 Effect of the Applied Chemical Potential on Strong Metal-Support Interaction in Ni-TiO₂ Catalysts	
	Min TANG - <i>University of Antwerp, Belgium</i>	
SO	11:48 - 11:56 Selective Dimethyl Ether Production by Methane Partial Oxidation Over Pt Catalysts and Structural Analysis of Active Sites	
	Kyoko BANDO - <i>Nanomaterials Research Institute, National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology, Japan</i>	
SO	11:56 - 12:04 In-situ MAS NMR Unveiled Desilication Details in the Formation of Hierarchical Zeolites	
	Nina TSERESHKO - <i>King Abdullah University of Science and Technology, Saudi Arabia</i>	
SO	12:04 - 12:12 Enhancing Catalyst Performance in SiO₂-Supported Co_xPt_{1-x} Nanoalloys for the Dry Reforming of Methane via Co:Pt Ratio Control	
	David NIEDEBALK - <i>Department of Mechanical and Process Engineering, ETH Zurich, Switzerland</i>	
SO	12:12 - 12:20 Illuminating the reaction mechanism of ammonia synthesis through H₂/D₂ isotope effect studies	
	Simon Ingeman HANSEN - <i>Technical University of Denmark, Denmark</i>	
11:00 - 12:20 MON-T10-02 Transient methods in heterogeneous catalysis		
Tête d'or 1+2		
Evgeniy REDEKOP		
11:00 - 11:20 Homolytic H₂ dissociation for enhanced hydrogenation catalysis on oxides		
Yifeng ZHU - <i>Department of Chemistry, Fudan University, China</i>		
11:20 - 11:40 Understanding of CO₂ interaction with Pt-Sn catalysts in CO₂-assisted propane dehydrogenation by TAP and MEXAS		
Lennert D'OOGHE - <i>Laboratory for Chemical Technology, Ghent University, Belgium</i>		
SO	11:40 - 11:48 Enhancement of mechanistic understanding through spatially resolved SSITKA-DRIFTS and Transient Kinetic Modeling	
	Damian VICO VAN BERKEL - <i>TU Delft, Netherlands</i>	
SO	11:48 - 11:56 Programmable Catalysis for Steam Reforming of Methane on Ruthenium	

SO **11:56 - 12:04 | Time-resolved analysis of isotopic exchange reveals fast elementary steps in catalytic reaction**

 Amira DJAAFRI - *Université de Lille, France*

SO **12:04 - 12:12 | REACTANT-CATALYST INTERACTIONS IN THE EPOXIDATION OF PROPENE WITH HYDROGEN PEROXIDE ON TITANIUM SILICATES**

 Matias ALVEAR - *University of Wisconsin-Madison, United States*

SO **12:12 - 12:20 | Real time kinetic measurement method to study catalytic reactions on various Pt surfaces**

 Stefan HÖRANDL - *University of Goettingen, Germany - Max Planck Institute, Germany*

11:00 - 12:20 | MON-T13-02 | Photocatalysis

 Amphitheatre

 Nicolas KELLER, Kazunari DOMEN

11:00 - 11:20 | Scalable Solar Energy Conversion via Photocatalytic Water Splitting

 Rengui LI - *Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences., China*

11:20 - 11:40 | "Freezing" Artificial Quantasomes within Porous Organic Polymer

 Jérôme CANIVET - *IRCELYON, France*

K **11:40 - 12:20 | Electrolyte engineering for water splitting: Reactant switching, reaction mechanism, and (photo)catalytic activity**

 Kazuhiro TAKANABE - *The University of Tokyo, Japan*

11:00 - 12:20 | MON-T17-02 | Catalysis in refining and petrochemistry : current and future trends

 Auditorium Pasteur

 Joris THYBAUT, Elodie DEVERS

11:00 - 11:20 | Quantifying the Role of Structure Directing Agents and AI-distribution during Toluene Methylation Reactions

 David HIBBITTS - *Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Florida, United States*

YT	11:20 - 11:40 Hydrodeoxygenation of lignin pyrolysis bio-oils and co-processing with petroleum fractions towards hydrocarbon fuels	
	Antigoni MARGELLOU - <i>Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece</i>	
	11:40 - 12:00 Direct transesterification: from seeds to biodiesel in one-step using heterogeneous catalyst.	
	Issis ROMERO-IBARRA - <i>Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Mexico</i>	
YT	12:00 - 12:20 Consequences of confinement on Lewis-acid-catalyzed alcohol dehydration	
	Gina NOH - <i>Pennsylvania State University, United States</i>	
	11:00 - 12:20 MON-T20-02 Single-atom catalysis	
	Auditorium Lumière	
	Abhaya DATYE, Aiqin WANG	
K	11:00 - 11:40 Progress and Perspectives of Single-Atom Catalysis	
	Jun LI - <i>Tsinghua University, China</i>	
	11:40 - 12:00 Geminal-atom copper catalysts for sustainable organic transformations	
	Sharon MITCHELL - <i>Institute for Chemical and Bioengineering, ETH Zurich, Switzerland</i>	
	12:00 - 12:20 Remotely Bonded Bridging Dioxygen Ligands Enhance Hydrogen Transfer in a Silica-Supported Tetrairidium Cluster Catalyst	
	Alexander KATZ - <i>University of California, Berkeley, United States</i>	
	11:00 - 12:20 MON-T24-02 Conversion of Nitrogen based small molecules (N₂, NH₃, NO_x, ...)	
	Prestige Gratte Ciel	
	Leon LEFFERTS, Nicolas BION	
	11:00 - 11:20 Catalytic Ammonia Synthesis by Co-loaded BaAl₂O₄-xHx Electride	
	Masaaki KITANO - <i>Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan</i>	
	11:20 - 11:40 Complex Ruthenium Hydrides Catalyze Ammonia Synthesis	
	Qianru WANG - <i>Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China</i>	
	11:40 - 12:00 Mechanocatalytic Synthesis of Ammonia from Its Elements	
	Steffen REICHLE - <i>Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Germany</i>	

12:00 - 12:20 | Lanthanum-based materials for ammonia decomposition in an electric field

Catherine BATIOT-DUPEYRAT - *IC2MP, Poitiers, France*

11:00 - 12:20 | MON-T30-02 | Catalysis for polymer synthesis, plastic recycling and upcycling

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Jean RAYNAUD, Susannah SCOTT

11:00 - 11:20 | Data-Driven Design of Molecular Catalysts for Copolymerization of Ethylene and Polar Monomer

Yi LUO - *Petrochina Petrochemical Research Institute, China*

11:20 - 11:40 | Catalytic Upcycling of Single-Use Plastics for Monomer Production

Yuxin WANG - *West Virginia University, United States*

SO **11:40 - 11:48 | Towards a Greener Bioeconomy: Synthesis and Characterization of Lignin-Polylactide Copolymers**

Tim LANGLETZ - *Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, RWTH Aachen, Germany*

SO **11:48 - 11:56 | Plastiloop2.0 - Digitally Enabled Acceleration of the Full Circularity of Aromatic Polymers**

Changru MA - *Eco-Efficient Products and Processes Laboratory (E2P2L), China*

SO **11:56 - 12:04 | Advancing Circularity: Catalytic Plastic Conversion with Hierarchical Catalysts**

Sabino ARMENISE - *CEPSA, Spain*

SO **12:04 - 12:12 | Pt enhanced C-H bonds activation for efficient polyethylene hydrogenolysis over alloyed RuPt/ZrO₂**

Chengyang SUN - *East China University of Science and Technology, China*

SO **12:12 - 12:20 | Mechanocatalytic Upcycling of Plastics**

Carsten SIEVERS - *Georgia Institute of Technology, United States*

12:20 - 13:30 | Seated lunch / Lunch bags

12:20 - 14:00 | Lunch Break

12:30 - 13:30 | "Tending to our Wings" lunch event

Salon Pasteur

14:00 - 15:40 | MON-T3-01 | Enzymatic, hybrid and bioinspired catalysis

 Arnaud TRAVERT - *University of Caen*

14:00 - 15:40 | MON-T13-03 | Photocatalysis

 Amphitheatre

 Kazuhiro TAKANABE, Eric PUZENAT

14:00 - 14:20 | Bi-based heterojunctions for CO₂ photoconversion in gas phase

 Angélique BOUSQUET - *ICCF, France*

YT 14:20 - 14:40 | Solar-driven CO₂ and H⁺ reduction coupled with alcohol oxidation

 Vasileios NIKOLAOU - *Nantes Université, CNRS, CEISAM, UMR 6230, France*

14:40 - 15:00 | Photocatalytic Reforming of Diols over Pt/TiO₂ for the Production of H₂ and Value-Added Chemicals

 Luke ROEBUCK - *University of Manchester, United Kingdom*

SO 15:00 - 15:08 | Boosting photocatalytic performances of porphyrinic Zr-MOFs for CO₂ reduction

 Caroline MELLOTT-DRAZNIKS - *CNRS, Collège de France, LCPB, France*

SO 15:08 - 15:16 | Molecular polyoxo- and thiometalate clusters as a bridge between homogeneous and heterogeneous photocatalysis

 Stephen MYAKALA - *TU Wien, Austria*

SO 15:16 - 15:24 | MXenes dots as photocatalysts for CO₂ hydrogenation

 Ana PRIMO - *Instituto de Tecnología Química (UPV-CSIC), Spain*

SO 15:24 - 15:32 | Solid Solution of GaN and ZnO Synthesized Using Solid Nitriding Reagents and Their Photocatalytic Water Splitting Activity

 Natsutogi IWASA - *Graduate School of Medicine, Science and Technology, Shinshu University, Japan*

SO YT 15:32 - 15:40 | An oxyhalide SrBi₃O₄Cl₃ with two different halogen layers as a photocatalyst for visible-light-driven water splitting

 Hajime SUZUKI - *Kyoto University, Japan*

14:00 - 15:40 | MON-T20-03 | Single-atom catalysis

 Auditorium Lumière

 Jun LI, Abhaya DATYE

14:00 - 14:20 | Single-atom catalysis: Challenges and Opportunities

 Pedro SERNA - *Instituto de Tecnología Química, Spain*

14:20 - 14:40 | Coordinated Migration of Metal and Oxide Single Atoms to Generate Active Metal/Oxide Reverse Interfaces

 Haifeng XIONG - *Xiamen University, China*

14:40 - 15:00 | Dynamics of Thermally Stable Single Atom Catalysts

 Yong WANG - *Washington State University/Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, United States*

15:00 - 15:20 | Au salt stabilization for improved acetylene hydrochlorination catalysts

 Joseph CARTWRIGHT - *Cardiff Catalysis Institute, United Kingdom*

YT 15:20 - 15:40 | High-Entropy Intermetallics: Providing Isolated Pt Sites for Ultrastable Propane Dehydrogenation Catalysis

 Yuki NAKAYA - *Graduate School of Engineering, Osaka University, Japan*

14:00 - 15:40 | MON-T21-01 | Acid-base catalysis

 Prestige Gratte Ciel

 Nadine ESSAYEM, Antonella GERVASINI

YT 14:00 - 14:20 | Design of metal-zeolite architectures for catalytic cracking of polyolefins

 Michele SARAZEN - *Princeton University, United States*

14:20 - 14:40 | Fluorinated-Sulfated Alumina: towards a possible synergy between Fluorine and Sulfate species for stronger acid catalysts design

 Roua BEN SALEM - *Institut de recherches sur la catalyse et l'environnement (IRCELYON), France*

14:40 - 15:00 | Water-resistant superbases niobium oxide clusters

 Seiji YAMAZOE - *Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan*

15:00 - 15:20 | Adsorption of alcohols allows defining hydrophilic and hydrophobic interactions in tectosilicates

 Ruixue ZHAO - *Technical University of Munich, Germany*

15:20 - 15:40 | Design of Strong Oxide Base Catalysts: Oxygen Vacancy with Nitride ion Substitution in BaTiO_{3-xNy}

 Masayoshi MIYAZAKI - *Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan*

14:00 - 15:40 | MON-T24-03 | **Conversion of Nitrogen based small molecules (N₂, NH₃, NO_x ...)**

 Tête d'or 1+2

 Lidia CASTOLDI, Marco DATURI

14:00 - 14:20 | **The competition between the electrochemical nitrogen and water oxidation on rutile(110) electrodes**

 André WARK - *Science Institute of the University of Iceland, Iceland*

YT 14:20 - 14:40 | **Making Iron Active: Highly-loaded Bimetallic Iron-Cobalt Catalysts for Hydrogen Release from Ammonia**

 Shilong CHEN - *Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Kiel University, Germany*

14:40 - 15:00 | **Lattice-stabilized single chromium atoms on ceria for nitrous oxide synthesis via ammonia oxidation**

 Ivan SURIN - *ETH Zürich, Switzerland*

15:00 - 15:20 | **Low-temperature NO_x removal (NH₃-SCR) over Sodium Vanadium Bronzes**

 Toru MURAYAMA - *Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan*

15:20 - 15:40 | **Exploring the Structural Dynamics of Pd in the H₂-SCR of NO_x by Operando XANES and DRIFTS**

 Thomas ELDRIDGE - *Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany*

14:00 - 15:40 | MON-T30-03 | **Catalysis for polymer synthesis, plastic recycling and upcycling**

 Bellecour 1+2+3

 Sylvie MAURY

14:00 - 14:20 | **Hydroformylation of Plastic Pyrolysis Oils**

 George HUBER - *University of Wisconsin-Madison, United States*

14:20 - 14:40 | **Surface-Activated Grinding Spheres Enable the Mechano-Catalytic Depolymerization of Polypropylene Waste**

 Adrian H. HERGESELL - *Utrecht University, Netherlands*

14:40 - 15:00 | **Room-temperature co-conversion of polyvinylchloride and polypropylene to liquid hydrocarbons**

 Yue LIU - *East China Normal University, China*

15:00 - 15:20 | Polyolefin catalytic upcycling: insight into catalysts properties – catalytic performance relationship

Kinga GÓRA-MAREK - *Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland*

15:20 - 15:40 | Depolymerization by ball milling – from hydrogenating different carbons into methane to practical polyethylene upcycling

Linfeng LI - *Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Germany*

15:40 - 16:10 | Coffee break - Exhibition - Posters

Exhibition Hall

16:10 - 17:30 | MON-T3-02 | Enzymatic, hybrid and bioinspired catalysis

Auditorium Pasteur

Damien DEBECKER

16:10 - 16:30 | Optimized spatial configuration of heterogeneous biocatalysts to manufacture fine chemicals

Fernando LÓPEZ-GALLEGO - *Biomaterials Research Center- CIC biomaGUNE, Spain*

16:30 - 16:50 | A light-driven hybrid nanoreactor harnessing organic frameworks and carboxysome synergy for efficient hydrogen production

Jing YANG - *University of Liverpool, United Kingdom*

SO **16:50 - 16:58 | Hetero-Bio Catalytic Systems for Redox Reactions**

Simon FREAKLEY - *University of Bath, United Kingdom*

SO **16:58 - 17:06 | HMF oxidation by photochemical and enzymatic cascade reaction**

Ivaldo ITABAIANA JUNIOR - *FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF RIO DE JANEIRO, Brazil*

SO **17:06 - 17:14 | Crystallization-assisted enantiopure amine synthesis using membrane-immobilized transaminase**

Hippolyte MEERSSEMAN ARANGO - *Institute of Condensed Matter and Nanosciences, UCLouvain, Belgium*

SO **17:14 - 17:22 | Heterogeneous Catalysis mediated Cofactor Regeneration for Biosynthesis**

Xiaodong WANG - *Lancaster University, United Kingdom*

SO **17:22 - 17:30 | Bioinspired single site catalysts for photocatalytic NADH regeneration**

16:10 - 17:30 | MON-T4-01 | Preparation of heterogeneous catalysts

 Tête d'or 1+2

 Jessi VAN DER HOEVEN, Changhui LIANG

K **16:10 - 16:50 | Super catalytic performances of in-situ electrochemically induced negatively charged metal nanoparticles for CO₂ reduction**

 Joongjai PANPRANOT - *Chulalongkorn University*

YT **16:50 - 17:10 | Metal phosphides and other d-metal/p-block element phases as catalysts for C–C bond formation reactions**

 Schirin HANF - *Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany*

17:10 - 17:30 | Flow Synthesis of High-Entropy Alloy and Oxide Nanoparticles and their Catalytic Properties

 Kohei KUSADA - *Kyoto University, Japan*

16:10 - 17:30 | MON-T9-02 | Characterization of catalysts and of catalytic reactions - Analytical developments

 Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

 Petra DE JONGH, Olivier DELPOUX

16:10 - 16:30 | Time-Resolved Ambient Pressure Photoelectron Spectroscopy for Studying Mechanisms of Catalytic Reactions under Operando Conditions

 Andrey SHAVORSKIY - *MAX IV Laboratory, Lund University, Sweden*

16:30 - 16:50 | In-situ Potassium K-edge X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy of Promoters in Oxidation, Electrochemical and Fischer-Tropsch Reactions

 Simon KONDRAT - *Loughborough University, United Kingdom*

SO **16:50 - 16:58 | Ligand-field/redox potential correlation in Co-Fe oxides investigated by 2p3d resonant inelastic X-ray emission spectroscopy**

 Olaf RÜDIGER - *Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Germany*

SO **16:58 - 17:06 | Predicting the pore-structure transport relationship in disordered alumina using hyperpolarized xenon MRI and NMR cryodiffusometry**

 Stefano COLLINS - *IFP Energies nouvelles, France*

SO YT **17:06 - 17:14 | How correlative microscopy can boost the understanding of metal/support interactions in catalytic reactions**

 Philipp WINKLER - TU Wien, Institute of Materials Chemistry, Austria

SO 17:14 - 17:22 | Mechanistic Insights into Machine Learning-Enabled Pt/Rb-Ba-Mo-Nb/TiO₂ Catalysts for Reverse Water-Gas Shift Reaction

 Nat PHONGPRUEKSATHAT - Catalysis Engineering, Department of Chemical Engineering, Delft University of Technology, Netherlands

SO 17:22 - 17:30 | Smart Characterization of Heterogeneous Catalysts: EXAFS for Single Atom Catalysts

 Javier HERAS-DOMINGO - Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia (ICIQ), Spain

16:10 - 17:30 | MON-T13-04 | Photocatalysis

 Amphitheatre

 Caroline MELLOTT-DRAZNIEKS, Bastian MEI

16:10 - 16:30 | Z-Scheme Water Splitting Utilizing CuLi_{1/3}Ti_{2/3}O₂ as Hydrogen Evolving Photocatalyst

 Hideki KATO - Tohoku University, Japan

16:30 - 16:50 | Scalable and efficient water-splitting photocatalyst sheets based on carbon-based conductors

 Chen GU - Research Initiative for Supra-Materials (RISM), Shinshu University, Japan

16:50 - 17:10 | Hydrogen generation with ionic liquid-confined Au@PdIn@TiO₂ nanocomposites: the role of the physical enrichment in photocatalysis

 Gustavo CHACON - INSTITUTO DE TECNOLOGÍA QUÍMICA (ITQ-CSIC), Spain

17:10 - 17:30 | Computational Assessment of MXenes Bandgap Engineering for the Photocatalytic Water Splitting

 Francesc VIÑES - Universitat de Barcelona, Spain

16:10 - 17:30 | MON-T20-04 | Single-atom catalysis

 Auditorium Lumière

 Richard CATLOW, Sharon MITCHELL

16:10 - 16:30 | Open-shell Single Atom Catalysts on Porous and Layered Materials

 Mario CHIESA - University of Turin, Italy

16:30 - 16:50 | Describe C-H activation over alloy surface, from single atom alloy to single site catalyst

 Zhi-Jian ZHAO - Tianjin University, China

SO	16:50 - 16:58 Ultradispersed (Mo,Re) sulfide catalysts: how many metal atoms for an active site?	
	Daria RYABOSHAPKA - <i>IRCELYON, France</i>	
SO	16:58 - 17:06 Probing the limits of "well-defined" atomically dispersed supported metal catalysts with experiment and theory	
	Rachita RANA - <i>University of California, Davis, United States</i>	
SO	17:06 - 17:14 Theoretical Study of Nonoxidative Conversion of Methane: From Single-atom to Single-Cluster Catalysis	
	Chun-Ran CHANG - <i>Xi'an Jiaotong University, China</i>	
SO YT	17:14 - 17:22 An Fe single-atom catalyst for efficient oxidative C-C cleavage of amines in the presence of H₂O and O₂	
	Haifeng QI - <i>Leibniz Institute for Catalysis e. v., Germany</i>	
16:10 - 17:30 MON-T21-02 Acid-base catalysis		
	Prestige Gratte Ciel	
	Nadine ESSAYEM, Antonella GERVASINI	
SO	16:10 - 16:18 Metal-Free Basic Carbocatalyst for Polyethylene terephthalate Monomerization via Solvolysis	
	Majd AL-NAJI - <i>Max Planck Institute of Colloids and Interfaces, Germany - TU Berlin/BasCat - UniCat BASF JointLab, Germany</i>	
SO	16:18 - 16:26 Deuterium isotope effect in the methanol-to-olefins process: evidence of multi-origin and topology-dependent products selectivity	
	Luca MAGGIULLI - <i>Paul Scherrer Institut (PSI), Switzerland - ETH Zuerich, Switzerland</i>	
SO YT	16:26 - 16:34 M-MFI (M = B, Al, Fe, Ga) zeolite as perspective catalysts for the conversion of isobutanol to linear butenes	
	Olga LARINA - <i>L. V. Pisarzhevskii Institute of Physical Chemistry of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Ukraine</i>	
SO	16:34 - 16:42 Direct upgrading of hemicellulose over WO₃/ZrO₂-SiO₂ acid catalysts	
	Marco A. FRAGA - <i>Instituto Nacional de Tecnologia, Brazil</i>	
SO	16:42 - 16:50 To be confirmed	
	Raphaël PIN	

K 16:50 - 17:30 | From biomass to fuels: a new carbon-efficient route controlled by acid and basic catalysts

Marcelo Maciel PEREIRA - *Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro*

16:10 - 17:30 | MON-T26-01 | CO2 conversion

Bellecour 1+2+3

Jerome CANIVET, Madelyn BALL

16:10 - 16:30 | Carbonatation of ethylene - glycidyl methacrylate based polymers using carbon dioxide as reagent and harnessing reactive extrusion

Véronique DUFAUD - *Univ. Lyon, CNRS, UMR 5128, Catalysis, Polymerization, Processes and Materials, France*

16:30 - 16:50 | Porous organic polymers for CO2 valorisation through One-pot epoxidation and carbonatation of vegetable oils to cyclic carbonates

Elisabeth RANGEL - *FUNDITEC, Spain*

16:50 - 17:10 | Elucidation of the Active Sites for the Selective CO2-CH3OH Conversion in a Confined Cu-Zn Structure

Xinwei YE - *Utrecht University, Netherlands*

17:10 - 17:30 | Dynamics of Zn chemical state and defect structure in ZnO-ZrO2 catalyst for methanol synthesis from CO2 reduction

Masahiro KUNISU - *Toray Research Center, Inc., Japan*

17:30 - 19:30 | Poster Session 1

Exhibition Hall

Tuesday 16 July

08:00 - 15:00 | Registration

Hall Bellecour

08:30 - 09:15 | PL02 | Plenary Lecture - Umit OZKAN: "High-temperature Electrocatalysis: Challenges and Opportunities"

Amphitheatre

Jan-Dierk GRUNWALDT

09:25 - 10:25 | TUE-T4-02 | Preparation of heterogeneous catalysts

Amphitheatre

Xavier CARRIER, Eric GAIGNEAUX

09:25 - 10:05 | Bimetallic Ni-Cu and Cu-Pd (de)Hydrogenation Catalysts – Composition and Particle Size Effects

Petra DE JONGH - *Utrecht University*

10:05 - 10:25 | Preparation of alloyed Pd-Ni and Pd-Cu alkyne hydrogenation catalysts

Kristiaan HELFFERICH - *Materials Chemistry & Catalysis, Utrecht University, Netherlands*

09:25 - 10:25 | TUE-T7-01 | Quantum simulation combined with machine learning for catalysis - Computational approaches at the atomic scale of catalysis

Auditorium Pasteur

Pascal RAYBAUD, Umberto RAUCCI

09:25 - 09:45 | Designing Catalytic Nanoparticles for Methyl Cyclohexane Dehydrogenation via Machine Learning and Microkinetic Modelling

Chuhong LIN - *Nanyang Technological University, Singapore*

09:45 - 10:05 | High-Throughput Screening of Electrocatalysts Accelerated by Interpretable Intrinsic Descriptor

Xiaoyun LIN - *Tianjin University, China*

10:05 - 10:25 | Overcoming Barriers in Computational Catalysis using Curriculum-based Training of Machine Learning Potentials (CBT/MLP)

Ambarish KULKARNI - *University of California, Davis, United States*

09:25 - 10:25 | TUE-T8-03 | Characterization of catalysts and of catalytic reactions - General

Auditorium Lumière

Arnaud TRAVERT, Silvia BORDIGA

09:25 - 09:45 | Identifying active centers of industrial vanadyl pyrophosphate catalyst

Gerhard MESTL - *Clariant AG, Germany*

09:45 - 10:05 | Sequential carbon capture and hydrogenation via Ru-doped rare-earth metal oxide based dual function materials

Jan KOPYSCINSKI - *McGill University, Canada*

10:05 - 10:25 | Adsorbate-induced frustrated Lewis pairs as catalytic active sites in zeolite

Shik Chi Edman TSANG - *The University of Oxford, United Kingdom*

09:25 - 10:25 | TUE-T12-01 | Surface science approaches

Tête d'or 1+2

Spyridon ZAFEIRATOS, Yaroslava LYKHACH

09:25 - 09:45 | Pt-High Entropy Alloy Single Crystal Model Catalyst Surface for Oxygen Reduction Reaction Study

Toshimasa WADAYAMA - *Graduate School of Environmental Studies, Tohoku University, Japan*

SO 09:45 - 09:53 | Bottom-up Synthesis of Amphiphilic Janus Catalysts: An Insight into the Aerobic Oxidation of Aromatic Alcohols in Pickering Foams

Kang WANG - *Cardiff University, United Kingdom*

SO 09:53 - 10:01 | Transition metal sulfide model catalysts in heteroatom-rich atmospheres: Combined insights from (operando) STM and XPS

Lars MOHRHUSEN - *Aarhus University, interdisciplinary Nanoscience Center iNANO, Denmark*

SO 10:01 - 10:09 | Time-resolved in situ XPS studies of heterogeneous catalysts using modulated excitation and phase sensitive detection

Luca ARTIGLIA - *Paul Scherrer Institut, Switzerland*

SO 10:09 - 10:17 | **Dynamic Behavior of Intermediate Adsorbates Controls Activity and Product Selectivity: Methanol Decomposition on Pt/TiO₂(110)**

Satoru TAKAKUSAGI - *Institute for Catalysis, Hokkaido University, Japan*

09:25 - 10:25 | TUE-T13-05 | Photocatalysis

Prestige Gratte Ciel

Hermenegildo GARCÍA GÓMEZ, Anne DOLBECQ

09:25 - 09:45 | Hydrophobic and Visible-light Responsive TiO₂ Photocatalyst for Efficient Hydrogen Peroxide Production in a Two-Phase System

Yifan ZHAO - *Osaka University, Japan*

SO 09:45 - 09:53 | **Development of a new Mechanochemical Synthesis for Covalent Triazine Frameworks active in the photocatalytic Production of H₂O₂**

Leonie HÄSER - *Institute of Technical and Macromolecular Chemistry - RWTH Aachen University, Germany*

SO YT 09:53 - 10:01 | **Photosynthesis of Hydrogen Peroxide Utilizing Hf-Based Metal-Organic Frameworks with Missing-Linker Defects and Ni Single Atoms**

Yoshifumi KONDO - *SANKEN, Osaka University, Japan - Graduate School of Engineering, Osaka University, Japan*

SO 10:01 - 10:09 | **Catalytically Active Coatings for the Removal of Indoor Pollutants**

Nathalia COSTA - *University of Twente, Netherlands*

SO YT 10:09 - 10:17 | **Piezo-photocatalysis: a winning solution for organic pollutants mineralization under solar light irradiation**

Melissa Greta GALLONI - *Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy - Consorzio Interuniversitario Nazionale per la Scienza e Tecnologia dei Materiali (INSTM), Italy*

SO YT 10:17 - 10:25 | **Kinetic Study of Homogenous, Light-Driven C-H Functionalization of Hydrocarbons using Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy**

Robert GEITNER - *Technical University Ilmenau, Germany*

09:25 - 10:25 | TUE-T26-02 | CO₂ conversion

Bellecour 1+2+3

Caroline MELLOTT-DRAZNIIEKS, Shohei TADA

09:25 - 09:45 | Room-Temperature CO₂ Hydrogenation to Methanol over Air-Stable hcp-PdMo Intermetallic Catalyst

SO	09:45 - 09:53 Manipulating PdGa intermetallic compounds confined inside MFI zeolite for highly efficient CO2 hydrogenation to Methanol and DME
	Minjie ZHAO - Universitat Politècnica de València-Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (UPV-CSIC), Spain
SO	09:53 - 10:01 Self-Regenerative Ni/CaTiO3/CaO for Integrated CO2 Capture and Dry Reforming of Methane
	Kandis Leslie GILLIARD-ABDULAZIZ - University of Southern California, United States
SO	10:01 - 10:09 Capture and conversion of CO2 under mild conditions over bifunctional mesoporous catalysts
	Huidong XU - TU Munich, Germany
SO	10:09 - 10:17 Chromium-Zirconium catalyst in tandem with zeolite as a highly selective catalyst for CO2 hydrogenation to aromatics
	Shuhei YASUDA - Applied Chemistry, School of Engineering, University of Toyama, Japan
SO	10:17 - 10:25 Regulation of Doped-Metal Sites in Bismuth Oxyhalides and Their Mechanistic Roles in Photocatalytic CO2 Reduction
	Yanjie WANG - Wolfson Catalysis Centre, Department of Chemistry, University of Oxford, Oxford, UK, United Kingdom
	09:25 - 10:25 TUE-T27-01 Conversion of biomass and waste resources - General
	Gratte Ciel 1+2+3
	François JEROME, Yuriy ROMAN-LESHKOV
YT	09:25 - 09:45 Ni on Nitrogen-Doped Carbon Catalyst in Pellet Shape for Flow-through Reductive Catalytic Fractionation of Beech Wood Sawdust
	Francesco BRANDI - Ku Leuven, Belgium - max planck institute for colloids and interface, Germany
SO	09:45 - 09:53 Catalytic Fractionation of Corn Cob-derived Lignin
	Nakisha MARK - Center for Environmentally Beneficial Catalysis, University of Kansas, United States

SO YT	09:53 - 10:01 Enhanced Reductive Catalytic Fractionation of raw lignocellulosic biomasses with a magnetic recyclable catalyst	
	Tommaso TABANELLI - <i>Industrial Chemistry Department "Toso Montanari", University of Bologna, Italy - Center for Chemical Catalysis-C3, Italy</i>	
SO	10:01 - 10:09 Process intensification approach for Black liquor valorization	
	Laura REYES VILLAMIZAR - <i>CP2M, UMR 5128, UCBL1, CNRS, CPE Lyon, France</i>	
SO	10:09 - 10:17 Enzymatic hydrolysis lignin dissolution and low-temperature solvolysis in ethylene glycol	
	Yushuai SANG - <i>Aalto University, Finland</i>	
SO	10:17 - 10:25 A Glance At Avantium's Furanic Humins	
	Sandra CONSTANT - <i>Avantium Renewable Polymers B.V., Netherlands</i>	
10:25 - 11:00 Coffee break - Exhibition - Posters		
	Exhibition Hall	
Computational approaches at the atomic scale of catalysis -		
11:00 - 12:20 TUE-T7-02 Quantum simulation combined with machine learning for catalysis		
	Auditorium Pasteur	
	William SCHNEIDER, Felix STUDDT	
11:00 - 11:20 Screening diffusion pathways in the MTO process with machine learning techniques		
	Pieter CNUUDE - <i>Ghent University, Belgium</i>	
11:20 - 11:40 Reference-Quality Free Energy Barriers in Catalysis from Machine Learning Thermodynamic Perturbation Theory		
	Michael BADAWI - <i>Université de Lorraine, France</i>	
SO YT	11:40 - 11:48 Data-driven modeling and design of catalytic materials for carbon dioxide hydrogenation	
	Raffaele CHEULA - <i>Aarhus University, Denmark - Carnegie Mellon University, United States</i>	
SO	11:48 - 11:56 A deep learning potential for [Cu(NH₃)₂]⁺ dynamics in Cu-CHA and Cu-AEI catalysts	
	Reisel MILLAN - <i>Institute of Chemical Technology, Spain</i>	
SO	11:56 - 12:04 Accurate Large-Scale Simulations of Palladium-Hydride Systems	

SO YT **12:04 - 12:12 | Combining machine learning and enhanced sampling to reveal the effects of dynamics on catalysis: N2 decomposition on Fe(111)**

 Luigi BONATI - *Italian Institute of Technology, Italy*

SO **12:12 - 12:20 | Automated Chemical Reaction Network Generation for Heterogeneous Catalysis**

 Oliver LOVEDAY - *Institut Català d'Investigació Química, Spain - Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Spain*

11:00 - 12:20 | TUE-T8-04 | Characterization of catalysts and of catalytic reactions - General

 Auditorium Lumière

 Miguel BANARES, Guylène COSTENTIN

11:00 - 11:20 | Vibrational Insights into Cation-Mediated Surface Species in Copper-Catalyzed eCO₂RR

 Jim DE RUITER - *Utrecht University, Netherlands*

YT **11:20 - 11:40 | Deciphering the Mechanism of Crystallization of MIL-53 and UiO-66 Metal-Organic Frameworks**

 Vitaly SUSHKEVICH - *Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland*

K **11:40 - 12:20 | Highlighting the adsorbate-induced ductility in supported metal nanoparticles through a multi-technique approach**

 Elena GROPPPO - *University of Torino*

11:00 - 12:20 | TUE-T12-02 | Surface science approaches

 Tête d'or 1+2

 Luca ARTIGLIA, Mathias BARREAU

11:00 - 11:20 | Visualizing catalyst complexity and dynamics at the meso- and nanoscale by in situ correlative surface microscopy

 Günther RUPPRECHTER - *TU Wien, Austria*

11:20 - 11:40 | Electronic metal support interaction coupled with cation exchange

 Yaroslava LYKHACH - *Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany*

11:40 - 12:00 | Towards low-temperature heterogeneous hydrogenation of carbonyl compounds: molecular systems for reversible hydrogen storage

 Swetlana SCHAUERMANN - *Kiel University, Germany*

12:00 - 12:20 | Discriminating reaction intermediates and spectators during CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol

 Frederic MEUNIER - *CNRS - Univ Lyon, France*

11:00 - 12:20 | TUE-T13-06 | Photocatalysis

 Prestige Gratte Ciel

 Clément MAHEU, Audrey BONDUELLE

11:00 - 11:20 | Direct Evidence for Sulfur Induced Deep Electron and Hole Traps in Titania

 Brian FREDERICK - *University of Maine, United States*

11:20 - 11:40 | Probe-Assisted NAP-XPS for Mapping Charge Distribution on Facet-Engineered Photocatalysts

 Wentian NIU - *University of Oxford, United Kingdom*

11:40 - 12:00 | Photocatalytic set-up for in situ and operando ambient pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy at the MAX IV laboratory

 Alexander KLYUSHIN - *MAX IV Laboratory, Sweden*

12:00 - 12:20 | Photo-thermo-catalytic H₂ production for solar energy conversion

 Simone LIVOLSI - *University of Milan, Italy*

11:00 - 12:20 | TUE-T23-01 | H₂ production and utilization as energy vector

 Bellecour 1+2+3

 Teko NAPPORN, Gonzalo PRIETO

11:00 - 11:20 | Green hydrogen production from methane cracking via mechanical catalysis approach

 Yu TIE - *Shandong University, China*

11:20 - 11:40 | Surface Evolution of Ni-Mo-MgO Catalyst in Methane Conversion for Hydrogen and Carbon Nanotube Production

 Laura Alejandra GOMEZ GOMEZ - *University of Oklahoma, United States*

YT **11:40 - 12:00 | Dynamic lattice strain oscillations in nanoalloy fuel cell catalysts**

 Zhi-Peng WU - *King Abdullah University of Science and Technology, Saudi Arabia*

12:00 - 12:20 | Assessing the use of Treated Wastewater for Green Hydrogen via SOEC

Marina MADDALONI - *Department of Civil, Environmental, Architectural Engineering and Mathematics, University of Brescia, Italy*

11:00 - 12:20 | TUE-T26-03 | CO2 conversion

Amphitheatre

Thibault CANTAT, Liliana GONÇALVES

11:00 - 11:20 | Intermediate transfer rate, ion migration, and acid strength determine the hydrocarbon yields for tandem CO2 hydrogenation

Manish SHETTY - *Texas A&M University, United States*

11:20 - 11:40 | Coupling ZnZrOx and SSZ-13 for CO2 hydrogenation to olefins

Julien DEVOS - *KU Leuven, Belgium*

11:40 - 12:00 | Low-nuclearity CuZnx ensembles on ZnZrOx catalyze methanol synthesis from CO2

Tangsheng ZOU - *ETH Zurich, Switzerland*

12:00 - 12:20 | Promoting Copper for Methanol Synthesis from CO2 in Gas and Liquid Phase Reactions

Malte BEHRENS - *Kiel University, Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Germany*

11:00 - 12:20 | TUE-T27-02 | Conversion of biomass and waste resources - General

Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

Dorothee LAURENTI, Pieter BRUIJNINCX

11:00 - 11:20 | The role of niobium-based catalysts in the catalytic conversion of biomass and plastics

Yanqin WANG - *East China University of Science and Technology, China*

11:20 - 11:40 | Co-pyrolysis as an efficient way to transform wastes in heterogeneous catalysts

Lilia LONGO - *Università Ca' Foscari Venezia, Italy*

11:40 - 12:00 | Anisole disproportionation on zeolites: inhibition effect of high aluminium content

Jean Wilfried HOUNFODJI - *Université de Lorraine, France*

12:00 - 12:20 | Synthesis of Solketal through Acetylation of Glycerol Using Heterogeneous Acid Catalysts

 Vijayalakshmi THANGARAJ - *University of Manchester, United Kingdom*

12:20 - 13:30 | Seated lunch / Lunch bags

12:20 - 14:00 | Lunch Break

12:30 - 13:30 | "Tending to our Roots" lunch event

 Salon Pasteur

14:00 - 15:40 | TUE-T4-03 | Preparation of heterogeneous catalysts

 Auditorium Lumière

 Malika BOUALLEG, Gerhard MESTL

K 14:00 - 14:40 | Zeolite fixed metal nanoparticles as efficient heterogeneous catalysts

 Feng-Shou XIAO - *ZheJiang University*

14:40 - 15:00 | Creating highly active Lewis Acid zeolites through connecting spectroscopy and precursor design

 Nicholas BRUNELLI - *The Ohio State University, United States*

15:00 - 15:20 | Organic alkalis as an alternative to traditionally inorganic ones for ecofriendly mechano-chemical synthesis of LDH-type catalysts

 Octavian-Dumitru PAVEL - *University of Bucharest, Romania*

15:20 - 15:40 | Optimizing the accessibility of acid sites in faujasite zeolites

 Gerhard PIRNGRUBER - *IFP Energies nouvelles, France*

Computational approaches at the atomic scale of catalysis -

14:00 - 15:40 | TUE-T7-03 | Quantum simulation combined with machine learning for catalysis

 Auditorium Pasteur

 Veronique VAN SPEYBROECK, Evgeny PIDKO

14:00 - 14:20 | Accurate Adsorption Free Energies of Oxygen-Containing Species on Pt(111) Surface: Beyond Harmonic Oscillator Approximation

 Thanh-Nam HUYNH - *Institute of Catalysis Research and Technology, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany*

14:20 - 14:40 | Dynamics and Reactivity with Ethylene of O-promoted Ag Surface Reconstructions

 Christopher PAOLUCCI - *University of Virginia, United States*

14:40 - 15:00 | Computing catalytic reaction times and paths with machine learning and rare events sampling methods

 Thomas PIGEON - *IFP Energies nouvelles, Rond-point de l'échangeur de Solaize, 69360, France*

K **15:00 - 15:40 | Artificial Intelligence Leap for Quantum Simulations in Materials Science and Catalysis**

 Alexander TKATCHENKO - *University Of Luxembourg*

14:00 - 15:40 | TUE-T8-05 | Characterization of catalysts and of catalytic reactions - General

 Tête d'or 1+2

 Francoise MAUGE, Jose Antonio DE LOS REYES

14:00 - 14:20 | Solvent Reorganization in Confined Spaces: Catalytic Consequences and Thermodynamic Ramifications

 David FLAHERTY - *Georgia Institute of Technology, United States*

14:20 - 14:40 | Stimulus-responsive control of electric fields near water-metal interfaces dictates activity of thermo-catalysts

 Jimmy FARIA - *Faculty of Science and Technology, MESA+ Institute for Nanotechnology, University of Twente, Netherlands*

14:40 - 15:00 | Oscillatory behaviors of the Fischer-Tropsch reaction over Co/Ce-oxide and CoCu/Ce-oxide catalysts

 Norbert KRUSE - *Washington State University, United States - Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, United States - Université Libre de Bruxelles, Belgium*

SO **15:00 - 15:08 | Pd/SSZ-13 passive NOx adsorber: strong FT-IR evidences of the H2O role on Pd reduction by CO**

 Sara MORANDI - *Università di Torino, Italy*

SO **15:08 - 15:16 | Application of Spectrokinetic Techniques for the Understanding of Active Sites and Intermediate Species in Heterogeneous Catalysis**

 Alejandra TORRES VELASCO - *The University of Kansas, Center for Environmentally Beneficial catalysis (CEBC), United States*

SO **15:16 - 15:24 | New insights on the role of perimeter sites in O2 and methanol activation in furfural oxidative esterification over Au catalysts**

 Maela MANZOLI - *Department of Drug Science and Technology and NIS Centre, University of Turin, Italy*

SO 15:24 - 15:32 | Pd based Lateral Condensed Catalyst (LCC) for Acetylene Hydrogenation Reaction

 Katarzyna SKORUPSKA - Fritz Haber Institute of the Max Planck Society, Germany

SO 15:32 - 15:40 | Triggering Catalytic Activity of Rh Nanoclusters on Cr and Rh-incorporated Ceria Catalysts with N-Heterocyclic Carbenes

 Satoshi MURATSUGU - Nagoya University, Japan

14:00 - 15:40 | TUE-T13-07 | Photocatalysis

 Prestige Gratte Ciel

 Eric PUZENAT, Audrey BONDUELLE

14:00 - 14:20 | Combining light and heat: Selective Thermophotocatalytic Gas-Phase Conversion of Methanol

 Bastian MEI - Ruhr-University Bochum, Germany

14:20 - 14:40 | Ru nanoparticles encapsulated in carbon microspheres as photo-thermal catalyst for NH₃ decomposition

 Diego MATEO - King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST), Saudi Arabia

14:40 - 15:00 | The ways hydrophobicity promotes PFOA photodegradation over hBN

 Kimberly HECK - Rice University, United States - Nanotechnology Enabled Water Treatment Center, United States

15:00 - 15:20 | Photocatalytic Dihydroxylation of Light Olefins to Glycols by Water

 Vitaly ORDOMSKY - UCCS-Unité de Catalyse et Chimie du Solide, France

15:20 - 15:40 | Biomimetic Photocatalysis: Opportunities for Elaboration of New Photocatalysts and Commercial Operations in Wastewater Treatment

 Jiaqiang WANG - School of Materials and Energy, School of Chemical Sciences & Technology, Yunnan University, China

14:00 - 15:40 | TUE-T23-02 | H₂ production and utilization as energy vector

 Bellecour 1+2+3

 Narcis HOMS, Pilar RAMÍREZ DE LA PISCINA

14:00 - 14:20 | H₂ production by gas-phase formic acid dehydrogenation on highly dispersed Ru based photothermal catalysts

 Nicolas KELLER - ICPEES - CNRS - University of Strasbourg, France

14:20 - 14:40 | Enhancing photocatalytic hydrogen production by water splitting using 2D-3D composite materials

Alexandra Corina IACOBAN - *University of Bucharest, Romania - University of Bucharest, Romania*

14:40 - 15:00 | New reactors for green hydrogen production via photocatalysis

Mireya CARVELA SOLER - *Centro Tecnológico Industrial de Castilla-La Mancha (ITECAM), Spain*

SO

15:00 - 15:08 | Regeneration of spinel derived Ni Catalysts in Ethanol Steam Reforming

Sergio IGLESIAS-VÁZQUEZ - *University of the Basque Country, Spain*

SO

15:08 - 15:16 | Aqueous phase reforming of wastewater streams for H₂ production: experimental and theoretical insights on competitive adsorption

Giuseppe PIPITONE - *Politecnico di Torino, Italy*

SO

15:16 - 15:24 | Asymmetric dense ceramic membranes activated with Pt for high temperature H₂ purification and water splitting

Francesco BASILE - *University of Bologna, Italy*

SO

15:24 - 15:32 | H₂ Evolution over Fluidizable Electrocatalyst Particles with Electron Shuttles

Qing-Nan WANG - *Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, China*

SO

15:32 - 15:40 | Hydrogen production from residual aluminum and wastewater: An attractive energy solution for northern and remote communities

Stanislav STOYANOV - *Natural Resources Canada, Canada*

14:00 - 15:40 | TUE-T26-04 | CO₂ conversion

Amphitheatre

Carmen CLAVER, Emanuele MOIOLI

14:00 - 14:20 | Carbon dioxide reduction via the reverse Water Gas Shift reaction over iron-nickel alloy-based catalysts

Nico FISCHER - *Catalysis Institute, University of Cape Town, South Africa*

YT

14:20 - 14:40 | Low-temperature and high-pressure reverse water-gas shift over Cu-catalysts: alkali metal promotion boost

Sergei CHERNIAK - *Utrecht University, Netherlands*

14:40 - 15:00 | Efficient CO₂ conversion by reverse water gas shift using Cu-In-oxide chemical looping material

 Takuma HIGO - *Waseda University, Japan*

YT 15:00 - 15:20 | Investigation of Ni-catalyzed CO₂ methanation

 Madelyn BALL - *West Virginia University, United States*

15:20 - 15:40 | Effect of preparation methods on CO₂ methanation over Ru/m-ZrO₂

 Shohei TADA - *Hokkaido University, Japan*

14:00 - 15:40 | TUE-T28-01 | Conversion of biomass and waste resources - Fuels from biomass

 Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

 Christophe GEANTET, Agnieszka RUPPERT

14:00 - 14:20 | Production of higher olefins in hydrodeoxygenation of methyl palmitate over reduced transition metal oxide catalysts

 Eika QIAN - *Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology, Japan*

14:20 - 14:40 | Spatial segregation of catalytic sites within zeolites for catalytic cascade fatty acid hydrodeoxygenation to alkanes

 Christopher PARLETT - *University of Manchester, United Kingdom*

14:40 - 15:00 | Highly dispersed Ni nanoparticles onto isolated Zr-SiO₂, as selective catalyst for lignin deoxygenation toward aromatic products

 Carmen CIOTONEA - *Unité de Chimie Environnemental et Interactions sur le Vivant, Université Littoral Côte d'Opale, France*

15:00 - 15:20 | Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF) Production from Catalytic Fast Pyrolysis and Hydrotreating of Woody Biomass

 Matthew YUNG - *National Renewable Energy Laboratory, United States*

15:20 - 15:40 | Kinetic study of bio-oxygenates C-C coupling on TiO₂ for fuel-grade hydrocarbons production

 Veronica PIAZZA - *Politecnico di Milano, Italy*

15:40 - 16:10 | Coffee break - Exhibition - Posters

 Exhibition Hall

16:10 - 17:30 | TUE-T4-04 | Preparation of heterogeneous catalysts

 Auditorium Lumière

16:10 - 16:30 | Tuning the activity of potassium glasses active in soot combustion via their structural doping with aliovalent redox metals

 Andrzej ADAMSKI - Jagiellonian University, Poland

16:30 - 16:50 | Hollow silica nanospheres as efficient catalysts for the acid-catalyzed upgrading of glycerol

 Carmela APRILE - University of Namur, Belgium

16:50 - 17:10 | Ni exsolution from (NiO)_xZrO₂ for catalytic CO₂ methanation

 Josefine SCHNEE - Laboratoire de Réactivité de Surface (LRS) - CNRS, France

17:10 - 17:30 | Preparation of multi-functional metalorganic hybrid materials through the design of active low-dimensional builder units

 Urbano DÍAZ - Instituto de Tecnología Química (UPV-CSIC), Spain

16:10 - 17:30 | TUE-T5-01 | Computational approaches at the atomic scale of catalysis - General

 Auditorium Pasteur

 Céline CHIZALLET, Matthew NEUROCK

K 16:10 - 16:50 | Insights from first principles calculations on the electro-oxidation of biomass on metal catalysts

 Karoliina HONKALA - University of Jyväskylä

16:50 - 17:10 | On the Importance of the Walden Inversion for the Modeling of Catalytic Processes at Electrified Solid/ Liquid Interfaces

 Kai EXNER - University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany

17:10 - 17:30 | Effects of Distortion on the Catalytic Activity of Silica-Supported $\equiv\text{Ti-OH}$ Species

 Alexis BELL - University of California at Berkeley, United States - Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, United States

16:10 - 17:30 | TUE-T8-06 | Characterization of catalysts and of catalytic reactions - General

 Tête d'or 1+2

 Elise BERRIER, Spyridon ZAFEIRATOS

16:10 - 16:30 | Different Particle Density Effects in Polyolefin and Small-Alkane Hydrogenolysis over Ru/TiO₂ Catalysts

Janos SZANYI - *Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, United States*

16:30 - 16:50 | Operando XAS study on the phase evolution of CuO/Al₂O₃ during high temperature redox reactions.

Virgile ROUCHON - *IFP Energies Nouvelles, France*

16:50 - 17:10 | Comparative analysis of the structural and functional aspects of binuclear iron sites in FER and *BEA zeolites for O₂ activation

Kinga MLEKODAJ - *J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Czechia*

17:10 - 17:30 | Evolution of active oxygen species on silver in ethylene epoxidation revealed by ambient pressure X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

Man GUO - *Paul Scherrer Institut, Switzerland - ETH Zurich, Switzerland*

16:10 - 17:30 | TUE-T23-03 | H₂ production and utilization as energy vector

Bellecour 1+2+3

Narcis HOMES, Pilar RAMÍREZ DE LA PISCINA

16:10 - 16:30 | Influence of support surface reconstruction on Cu/CeO₂ CO-PROX catalysts

Arturo MARTINEZ-ARIAS - *ICP-CSIC, Spain*

16:30 - 16:50 | Unraveling the role of Co in bimetallic oxygen carriers for H₂ production via sorption enhanced chemical looping reforming

Andy ANTZARAS - *Department of Chemical Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece*

16:50 - 17:10 | Continuous Hydrothermal Flow Synthesis of Bimetallic Co-Ni Spinel Catalysts for Ammonia Decomposition to Hydrogen

Anh Binh NGO - *Fritz Haber Institute of the Max Planck Society, Berlin, Germany - Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Mulheim an der Ruhr, Germany*

17:10 - 17:30 | A New Application of High Temperature Water Gas Shift for Reduction of CO₂ Emissions in the Iron and Steel Industry

Liliana LUKASHUK - *Johnson Matthey, United Kingdom*

16:10 - 17:30 | TUE-T25-01 | Valorization of C₁ molecules (CH₄, CO, MeOH) except CO₂

Prestige Gratte Ciel

YT **16:10 - 16:30 | Disentanglement—breaking the activity-selectivity “tradeoff” effect in catalytic conversion of syngas to light olefins**

16:30 - 16:50 | Carbon Guarded Co-Nanoparticles in Bifunctional System Stabilize the Product Selectivity in Efficient CO Hydrogenation

 Md. Shahajahan KUTUBI - *Nagoya University, Japan*

16:50 - 17:10 | Synthesis of higher alcohols from syngas over Cu-Fe-CoK/Attapulgite catalysts

 Atte AHO - *Åbo Akademi University, Finland*

17:10 - 17:30 | Amines and Nitriles Synthesis through Catalytic CO Hydrogenation in the Presence of Ammonia

 Hafsa KARROUM - *Washington State University, United States*

16:10 - 17:30 | TUE-T26-05 | CO2 conversion

 Amphitheatre

 Jerome CANIVET, Clément CAMP

16:10 - 16:30 | Solid solution catalyst and its application for e-methanol synthesis

 Wang JIJIE - *State Key Laboratory of Catalysis, Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China*

YT **16:30 - 16:50 | Bridging the Gap between Fundamental Mechanistic Insights and Industrial Catalyst Design for CO2 Hydrogenation to Methanol**

 Maxim ZABILSKIY - *Clariant Produkte (Deutschland) GmbH, Germany*

K **16:50 - 17:30 | Catalysis for a circular carbon economy: CO2 chemistry and chemical recycling of waste plastics**

 Thibault CANTAT - *CEA*

16:10 - 17:30 | TUE-T28-02 | Conversion of biomass and waste resources - Fuels from biomass

 Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

 Antoine DAUDIN, Yanqin WANG

YT **16:10 - 16:30 | Catalytic upgrading of wet waste-derived volatile fatty acids to sustainable aviation fuel and chemical intermediates**

 Jacob MILLER - *National Renewable Energy Laboratory, United States*

16:30 - 16:50 | Nb2O5 promotion effect on activated carbon catalyst for pyrolysis oil hydrodeoxygenation

 Mariana Myriam CAMPOS FRAGA - *Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany*

SO **16:50 - 16:58 | Tuning performance of Ni–Mo catalysts for the HDO of lignin oils to fuels**

 Tove KRISTENSEN - *Department of Chemical Engineering, Lund University, Sweden - Hulteberg Chemistry & Engineering AB, Sweden*

SO **16:58 - 17:06 | Sustainable Aviation Fuels Production under Atmospheric Pressure Via Metathesis-Deoxygenation of Biodiesel and Ethylene**

 Kittisak CHOOJUN - *Department of Chemistry, School of Science, King Mongkut's Institute of Technology Ladkrabang, Thailand*

SO **17:06 - 17:14 | Exploring new routes for biofuels production: H2-free HDO enabled by multifunctional catalysts**

 Sergio CARRASCO-RUIZ - *University of Seville, Spain*

SO **17:14 - 17:22 | In situ XAFS/XES Studies on FeZSM-5 during Catalytic Fast Pyrolysis**

 Luke HIGGINS - *Diamond Light Source, United Kingdom*

SO **17:22 - 17:30 | Catalytic set-up operated under supercritical water conditions for methane production**

 Alessandro CAJUMI - *Università di Messina, Italy*

17:30 - 19:30 | Poster Session 2

 Exhibition Hall

19:30 - 21:00 | Young Scientists Career Fair

 Salon Pasteur

Wednesday 17 July

08:00 - 19:30 | Registration

Hall Bellecour

08:30 - 09:15 | PL03 | Plenary Lecture - Jeroen van BOKHOVEN: "Advanced Spectroscopic tools applied to heterogeneous catalysis"

Amphitheatre

Cathy Ya-Huei CHIN

09:25 - 10:25 | WED-T6-01 | Unifying Concepts to Tackle Dynamics in Computational Catalysis
Computational approaches at the atomic scale of catalysis -

Tête d'or 1+2

Maren PODEWITZ, Ainara NOVA

09:25 - 09:45 | Solvent and salts control the nature of organozincs reagents: insights from Ab-initio molecular dynamics

Jordan RIO - ICBMS, Université Lyon 1, France

SO 09:45 - 09:53 | Insights Into Dynamics of Supported Metal Clusters via Machine Learning Potentials

Tereza BENEŠOVÁ - Department of Physical and Macromolecular Chemistry, Charles University in Prague, Czechia

SO 09:53 - 10:01 | Diffusion of Alcohols on Carboxylate-Decorated Cobalt: Effects of Chain Length

Xiaojing WU - ENS Lyon, France

SO 10:01 - 10:09 | Rational Design of Mo₂C for Hydrodeoxygenation: Mechanism and Descriptor Identification

Guanna LI - Wageningen University, Netherlands

SO 10:09 - 10:17 | Constrained TI in internal coordinates as a promising tool to address the adsorption problem in free energy calculations

Tomas BUCKO - Comenius University in Bratislava, Slovakia - Slovak Academy of Sciences, Slovakia

SO 10:17 - 10:25 | Decoding the active site in supported organometallic catalysts via autonomous configurational space exploration

 Alexander KOLGANOV - *Delft University of Technology, Netherlands*

09:25 - 10:25 | WED-T15-01 | Non-conventional activation methods and media

 Bellecour 1+2+3

 Tony CHAVE, Nathalie TANCHOUX

09:25 - 09:45 | Designing heterogeneous catalysts for microwave assisted selective oxygenation

 Jonathan BARTLEY - *Cardiff Catalysis Institute, School of Chemistry, Cardiff University, United Kingdom*

SO **09:45 - 09:53 | Investigating the role of different supports for low temperature Plasma assisted CO2 methanation**

 Sana ULLAH - *Commonwealth scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), Australia*

SO **09:53 - 10:01 | Catalytic Reaction Triggered by Magnetic Induction Heating Can be Mechanistically Different from a Standard Thermal Reaction**

 Ming YANG - *Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering, Clemson University, United States*

SO **10:01 - 10:09 | Carbon-coated Core-shell Nanoparticles for Induction Heated Catalysis**

 Luis M. MARTÍNEZ-PRIETO - *Instituto de Investigaciones Químicas (CSIC-US), Spain - Universitat Politècnica de Valencia (UPV), Spain*

SO **10:09 - 10:17 | Water-assisted Sonochemically-induced Demethylenation of Benzyl Alcohol to Phenol over Structurally Stable Cupric Oxide Catalyst**

 Prince AMANIAMPONG - *CNRS-University of Poitiers, France*

SO **10:17 - 10:25 | Plasma-catalytic Nitrogen Fixation with In Situ Adsorption**

 Leon LEFFERTS - *University of Twente, Netherlands*

09:25 - 10:25 | WED-T18-01 | Transitioning from refining to circular and sustainable chemistry : transition metal sulfide catalysts at the crossroads

 Amphitheatre

 Hirsa TORRES GALVIS, Pavel AFANASIEV

K **09:25 - 10:05 | Transition metal sulfides and related catalysts for electrochemical and photoelectrochemical (PEC) H2 production and use**

 Thomas JARAMILLO - *Stanford University, United States*

10:05 - 10:25 | Designing defective molybdenum sulfide nanomaterials from molecular clusters for fine chemical synthesis and electrocatalysis

Iván SORRIBES - *Institute of Advanced Materials (INAM), Universitat Jaume I, Spain*

09:25 - 10:25 | WED-T22-01 | Catalytic reactions for hydrogen storage and release

Prestige Gratte Ciel

Valérie MEILLE, Phillimon MODISHA

09:25 - 09:45 | On-demand hydrogen production at low-temperature driven by surface protonics

Yasushi SEKINE - *Waseda University, Japan*

SO YT **09:45 - 09:53 | Catalyst with Atomic Interfacial Structure for Efficient Cyclohexane Dehydrogenation**

Mi PENG - *Peking University, China*

SO **09:53 - 10:01 | Enhanced activity of Fe, Mo and Zr promoted Pt/Al₂O₃ catalyst for the dehydrogenation of perhydro-benzyltoluene**

Alvaro MARTÍNEZ - *University of the Basque Country, Spain*

SO **10:01 - 10:09 | Stable and active LOHC dehydrogenation catalyst synthesis by ball milling**

Krista KUUTTI - *VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, Finland*

SO YT **10:09 - 10:17 | Coal Fly Ash as a Cost-Free, Environment-Friendly, and Fe-based Catalyst for Ammonia Decomposition to Produce CO_x-free Hydrogen**

Samira F. KURTOGLU-ÖZTULUM - *Turkish-German University, Turkey - Dpt of Chemical and Biological Engineering - Koç University TÜPRAŞ Energy Center (KUTEM), Turkey*

SO **10:17 - 10:25 | Barium hydride mediates dinitrogen fixation and catalytic ammonia synthesis**

Yeqin GUAN - *Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China*

09:25 - 10:25 | WED-T25-02 | Valorization of C1 molecules (CH₄, CO, MeOH) except CO₂

Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

Rebecca FUSHIMI, Yves SCHUURMAN

09:25 - 09:45 | Lithium Carbonate-Promoted Mixed Oxide Catalysts for Chemical-Looping Oxidative Coupling of Methane with High Yields

SO YT	09:45 - 09:53 Understanding OCM kinetics through operando thermal inspection and spatial reactor analyses	
	Jose PALOMO - <i>Delft University of Technology, Netherlands</i>	
SO	09:53 - 10:01 Unusual Facet and Co-catalyst Effects in TiO₂-based Photocatalytic Coupling of Methane	
	Shunji XIE - <i>Xiamen University, China</i>	
SO	10:01 - 10:09 Ultra-stable dry reforming of methane (DRM) with anchored Ni nanocluster through in-situ generated Ni-O-Si rigging	
	Lizhuo WANG - <i>The University of Sydney, Australia</i>	
SO	10:09 - 10:17 Role of Ni/CeO_{2-x} interfaces for thermal and combined photo-thermal DRM reaction	
	Kristijan LORBER - <i>National institute of chemistry, Slovenia</i>	
SO	10:17 - 10:25 Promoting coke gasification with nitric oxide: a support study	
	Beatrice SENONER - <i>Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Padua, Italy</i>	
09:25 - 10:25 WED-T26-06 CO₂ conversion		
	Auditorium Lumière	
	Véronique DUFAUD, Gerhard PIRNGRUBER	
	09:25 - 09:45 Enhancing the reaction of CO₂ and H₂O using non-thermal plasma-catalysis	
	Piu CHAUDHURY - <i>Post doctoral research associate, United Kingdom</i>	
SO	09:45 - 09:53 Low-temperature CO₂ hydrogenation in CO₂-dissolved expanded liquid	
	Hiroshi YOSHIDA - <i>Institute of Science and Engineering, Kanazawa University, Japan</i>	
SO	09:53 - 10:01 Disclosing the reaction mechanism of the CO₂ conversion into methanol over CuCeO_x/TiO₂: spectrokinetics and isotopic labelling	
	Tomás VERGARA - <i>Karlsruher Institut für Technologie, Germany</i>	
SO	10:01 - 10:09 Understanding Nickel-Support Interactions in Catalytic CO₂ Hydrogenation with Modulation Excitation Infrared Spectroscopy	
	Angela MELCHERTS - <i>Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
SO	10:09 - 10:17 Direct and Efficient N-Methylation of Ethylenediamine with CO₂ and H₂ over Carbon-Supported Re-Ir Catalyst	

 Min WANG - *Tohoku University, Japan*

09:25 - 10:25 | WED-T32-01 | Chemicals and fine chemistry

 Auditorium Pasteur

 Rafael GRAMAGE-DORIA, Antoine SIMONNEAU

09:25 - 09:45 | Photoredox Carbon-Carbon Coupling without Iridium using Nickel Single-Atom Catalysts

 De Vries Ibanez MIGUEL - *Politecnico di Milano, Italy*

09:45 - 10:05 | Non-noble metal nanoparticles and structurally simple complexes as promising catalysts for olefin hydrosilylation reactions.

 Chloé THIEULEUX - *CP2M - UMR 5128 CNRS-UCBL-CPE Lyon, France*

10:05 - 10:25 | Boron Catalysis for Oxidative Dehydrogenation of Alkanes to Olefins

 Tao WU - *Dalian University of Technology, China*

10:25 - 11:00 | Coffee break - Exhibition - Posters

 Exhibition Hall

11:00 - 12:20 | WED-T6-02 | Unifying Concepts to Tackle Dynamics in Computational Catalysis

 Auditorium Lumière

 Aleix COMAS VIVES, Nuria LOPEZ

11:00 - 11:20 | The Influence of Surface Dynamics on Ammonia Synthesis and Decomposition in Transition-Metal-Free Catalysts

 Umberto RAUCCI - *Italian Institute of Technology, Italy*

11:20 - 11:40 | Theoretical Modelling of Cluster Catalysis under Operando Conditions

 Jin-Xun LIU - *University of Science and Technology of China, China*

K 11:40 - 12:20 | A dynamics view on zeolite catalysis at operating conditions bridging length and time scales

 Veronique VAN SPEYBROECK - *Ghent University*

11:00 - 12:20 | WED-T15-02 | Non-conventional activation methods and media

 Bellecour 1+2+3

 Franck LAUNAY

K 11:00 - 11:40 | **Conversion of biomass to fine chemicals : deep eutectic solvents or mechanocatalysis strategies**

Karine DE OLIVEIRA VIGIER - *IC2MP - Université de Poitiers*

11:40 - 12:00 | **Methanol Dehydration to Dimethyl Ether on Ball Milling-Derived High-Surface-Area Alpha-Alumina Catalysts**

Özgül AGBABA - *Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Germany*

12:00 - 12:20 | **Increasing textural properties of planetary milled alpha alumina**

Dina LOFFICIAL - *IFP Energies Nouvelles, France*

11:00 - 12:20 | **WED-T18-02 | Transitioning from refining to circular and sustainable chemistry : transition metal sulfide catalysts at the crossroads**

Tête d'or 1+2

Laetitia OLIVIERO, Hong NIE

11:00 - 11:20 | **Pt nanoclusters on 2D MoS₂ for highly efficient hydrogen evolution**

Tamás OLLÁR - *Surface Chemistry and Catalysis Department, Centre for Energy Research, Hungary*

11:20 - 11:40 | **CoMoS/Al₂O₃ catalysts: link between Mo precursors speciation and MoS₂ multi-scale arrangement via a multi-technique approach**

Anne-Sophie GAY - *IFP Energies Nouvelles, France*

SO 11:40 - 11:48 | **Acceleration of low-alkane (C₄, C₅) dehydrogenation by lattice S₂-species of iron sulfide catalyst**

Ryo WATANABE - *Shizuoka University, Japan*

SO 11:48 - 11:56 | **Transient formation of NiS_x during reactive adsorption of gasoline desulfurization**

Bo PENG - *SINOPEC Research Institute of Petroleum Processing Co., Ltd., China*

SO YT 11:56 - 12:04 | **A transition from fossil to solar fuels with RuS₂-based catalysts, some good practices to work on the photocatalytic H₂ production**

Clément MAHEU - *Institut des Matériaux de Nantes Jean Rouxel (IMN), France - Université de Lyon, France*

SO 12:04 - 12:12 | **Photocatalytic CO₂ Conversion over Nickel Phosphides and Borides**

Mark E. BUSSELL - *Western Washington University, United States*

SO 12:12 - 12:20 | **Few layer MoS₂ as a catalyst for the hydrodeoxygenation of fatty acids to alkanes**

 Fuli DENG - *Lehrstuhl für Technische Chemie II, TUM School of Natural Sciences, Technische Universität München, Germany*

11:00 - 12:20 | WED-T22-02 | Catalytic reactions for hydrogen storage and release

 Prestige Gratte Ciel

 Victoria Laura BARRIO, Alban CHAPPAZ

**11:00 - 11:20 | Catalytic Hydrogen Loading and Release in the LOHC system
Benzyltoluene/Perhydro Benzyltoluene**

 Barbara BONG - *Institute for Technical and Macromolecular Chemistry, RWTH Aachen University, Germany*

11:20 - 11:40 | Catalytic Dehydrogenation in LOHC Technology

 Olvido IRRAZÁBAL MOREDA - *European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF), France*

11:40 - 12:00 | Single Rh1Co catalyst enabling reversible hydrogenation and dehydrogenation of N-ethylcarbazole for hydrogen storage?

 Xinqing CHEN - *Shanghai Advanced Research Institute, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China*

12:00 - 12:20 | Design of Uniformly Dispersed Platinum Catalyst for Efficient Hydrogen Evolution from Methylcyclohexane Dehydrogenation

 Junhyeok JUNG - *Seoul National University, Korea (Republic of) - Institute for Basic Science (IBS), Korea (Republic of)*

11:00 - 12:20 | WED-T25-03 | Valorization of C1 molecules (CH₄, CO, MeOH) except CO₂

 Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

 Stephane LORIDANT, Dmitry MURZIN

11:00 - 11:20 | The Relationships between the Formaldehyde Productivity and Catalyst Performance in the Methanol-to-Hydrocarbons Conversion

 Vladimir PAUNOVIC - *ETH Zurich, Switzerland - Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland*

11:20 - 11:40 | Selective methanol-to-ethylene conversion using anisole as an intermediate

 Yue WANG - *Key Lab of Applied Chemistry of Zhejiang Province, Department of Chemistry, Zhejiang University, China*

11:40 - 12:00 | Low-temperature Continuous Production of Hydrogen Cyanide from Methane with Nitric Oxide over Pt/Al₂O₃ Catalyst

 Atsushi TAKAGAKI - *Yokohama National University, Japan*

12:00 - 12:20 | Pd active sites and catalytic reaction mechanism for indirect oxidative carbonylation of methanol to dimethyl carbonate

Chunzheng WANG - *China University of Petroleum (East China), China*

11:00 - 12:20 | WED-T26-07 | CO2 conversion

Amphitheatre

Jerome CANIVET, Malte BEHRENS

11:00 - 11:20 | Water-promoted CO2 electrolysis to multi-carbon compounds over a matched catalyst

Xiaoyang HE - *Xiamen University, China*

11:20 - 11:40 | Nanoparticle for Enhanced Electrocatalytic CO2 Conversion: Unveiling Novel Pathways to Sustainable Chemical and Fuel Production

Ali SEIFITOKALDANI - *McGill University, Canada*

11:40 - 12:00 | Deciphering the interplay between mass, charge transport and kinetics in gas diffusion electrode assisted CO2 electroreduction

Kaustav NIYOGI - *Politecnico di Milano, Italy*

12:00 - 12:20 | Development of CO2 conversion catalysts by electronic structure regulation

Wenhang WANG - *Liaocheng University, China*

11:00 - 12:20 | WED-T32-02 | Chemicals and fine chemistry

Auditorium Pasteur

Rafael GRAMAGE-DORIA, Chloe THIEULEUX

11:00 - 11:20 | Enantioselective catalyzed allylboration of acetylene. Unlocking pathways for natural products synthesis.

Andrés Manuel ÁLVAREZ CONSTANTINO - *University of Santiago de Compostela - CiQUS, Spain*

YT

11:20 - 11:40 | Regioselective α -C-H Functionalization of Tertiary Amines to Enaminones via Tandem Aerobic Oxidation by Au Nanoparticle Catalysts

Takafumi YATABE - *School of Engineering, The University of Tokyo, Japan - Japan Science and Technology Agency (JST), Japan*

SO **11:40 - 11:48 | Towards Sustainable Aldol Chemistry via Solid Acid Catalysis**

Isaac OGABIELA - *University Massachusetts Amherst, United States*

SO	11:48 - 11:56 Sustainable Alkylamine Synthesis through Reductive Amination of Carboxylic Acids under H₂ over a Pt-Mo Catalyst	
	Katsumasa SAKODA - <i>Osaka University, Japan</i>	
SO	11:56 - 12:04 Investigating the role of surface reconstruction for Ni,Cu/Al₂O₃ in ethanol dehydrogenation	
	Elena SPENNATI - <i>DICCA, University of Genova, Italy - INSTM, Italy</i>	
SO	12:04 - 12:12 Silver catalyst with iodonium salt: O-Arylation of α-fluorocarboxylic acid	
	Kotaro KIKUSHIMA - <i>Ritsumeikan University, Japan</i>	
SO	12:12 - 12:20 One-pot N-alkylation of formamides with syngas: synthesis of fatty N-alkylamide commodities from renewable N1 and C1 sources	
	Ilaria CETERONI - <i>Instituto de Tecnologia Quimica (UPV-CSIC), Spain</i>	
12:20 - 13:30 Seated lunch / Lunch bags		
12:20 - 14:00 Lunch Break		
12:30 - 13:30 "Tending to our Wings" lunch event		
	Salon Pasteur	
14:00 - 18:00 Excursions		

Thursday 18 July

08:00 - 19:30 | Registration

Hall Bellecour

08:30 - 09:15 | PL04 | Plenary Lecture - Thomas MASCHMEYER: "Driving sustainable technology through catalysis"

Amphitheatre

Hilde VENVIK

09:25 - 10:25 | THU-T5-02 | Computational approaches at the atomic scale of catalysis - General

Prestige Gratte Ciel

Mercedes BORONAT, Pieter CNUUDE

09:25 - 09:45 | On the interpretation of H₂-TPR from Cu-CHA using first-principles calculations

Joachim BJERREGAARD - *Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden*

09:45 - 10:05 | FIRST-PRINCIPLES ASSESSMENT OF THE ROLE OF WATER INTO THE REDOX MECHANISM OF LOW-TEMPERATURE NH₃-SCR OVER CU-CHA

Gabriele CONTALDO - *Politecnico di Milano, Laboratory of Catalysis and Catalytic Processes, Dipartimento di Energia, Italy*

10:05 - 10:25 | Decoding Multimetallic Ensembles in Zeolite Pores: Towards Bias-Free Operando Modeling

Evgeny PIDKO - *Delft University of Technology, Netherlands*

09:25 - 10:25 | THU-T15-03 | Non-conventional activation methods and media

Auditorium Pasteur

Catherine BATIOU-DUPEYRAT

09:25 - 09:45 | Evaluation of Microwave Assisted Plug Flow Reactor Based on Rigorous Kinetics and Thermodynamics of Ammonia Synthesis

Fuminao KISHIMOTO - *The University of Tokyo, Japan*

09:45 - 10:05 | Plasma-catalytic One-step Anaerobic Oxidation of Methane to Methanol

Shangkun LI - *Research group PLASMANT, Department of Chemistry, University of Antwerp,, Belgium*

Jason HICKS - *University of Notre Dame, United States*

Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

Eric MARCEAU, Emilie GAUDRY

09:25 - 09:45 | Intermetallic Compounds as Reliable Platform Materials for Catalyst Development

Marc ARMBRÜSTER - *Chemnitz University of Technology, Germany*

Shinya FURUKAWA - *Osaka University, Japan*

Isaac DANIEL - *Max Planck–Cardiff Centre on the Fundamentals of Heterogeneous Catalysis, Cardiff University., United Kingdom*

Amphitheatre

Nicolas BION, Masaaki KITANO

K 09:25 - 10:05 | Hydrides for Catalytic Ammonia Synthesis

Ping CHEN - *Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences*

Peter NGENE - *Utrecht University, Netherlands*

Tête d'or 1+2

Petra DE JONGH, Martin MUHLER

09:25 - 09:45 | Ambient-pressure Alkoxy carbonylation for Linear-selective Synthesis of Esters

SO **09:45 - 09:53 | Application of structured internals for the intensification of Fischer-Tropsch tubular reactors**

 Martino PANZERI - *Politecnico di Milano, Italy*

SO **09:53 - 10:01 | Development of alumina-supported VC catalysts for efficient reverse water gas shift reaction**

 Pilar RAMÍREZ DE LA PISCINA - *University of Barcelona-IREC, Spain*

SO **10:01 - 10:09 | Developing and Understanding N/P Stabilized Cobalt Nanoparticles Resisting Leaching during Liquid Phase Hydroformylation**

 Silvia GUTIÉRREZ TARRIÑO - *Instituto de Tecnología Química, Spain*

SO **10:09 - 10:17 | Sequential Activation of CO₂ and CH₄ for CH₃COOH Production**

 Seungdon KWON - *Department of Chemistry, Chonnam National University, Korea (Republic of)*

09:25 - 10:25 | THU-T26-08 | CO₂ conversion

 Bellecour 1+2+3

 Kwan Young LEE, Céline PAGIS

09:25 - 09:45 | Molecular Understanding of Heterogeneous Organometallic Photocatalyst

 Riddhi KUMARI - *Erlangen Center for Interface Research and Catalysis (ECRC), Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany*

09:45 - 10:05 | Engineering dual-active sites in catalyst for selective photocatalytic CO₂ reduction to C₂+ products

 Biyun LIN - *Department of Applied Biology and Chemical Technology, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, China*

10:05 - 10:25 | Improved activity in CO₂-hydrogenation over iron-based catalysts upon in-situ dosing of water

 Nicholas FEATHERSTONE - *University of Cape Town, South Africa*

09:25 - 10:25 | THU-T28-03 | Conversion of biomass and waste resources - Fuels from biomass

 Auditorium Lumière

 Harry BITTER, Delphine MINOUX

YT 09:25 - 09:45 | Continuous Conversion of Tall Oil over Ni-Cu/SAPO-11 to Aromatics-rich Sustainable Aviation Fuel Blendstock

09:45 - 10:05 | Methanol to Sustainable Aviation Fuel: Mixed Olefin Oligomerization

 Karthikeyan RAMASAMY - *Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, United States*

10:05 - 10:25 | Production of bio-jet fuel precursors via aldol condensation of furfural and cyclopentanone over dendritic ZSM-5 zeolite catalysts

 Rafael Ángel GARCÍA-MUÑOZ - *Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Rey Juan Carlos University, 28933 Móstoles, Madrid, Spain*

10:25 - 11:00 | Coffee break - Exhibition - Posters

 Exhibition Hall

11:00 - 11:40 | THU-T28-04 | Conversion of biomass and waste resources - Fuels from biomass

 Auditorium Lumière

 George HUBER, Angeliki LEMONIDOU

11:00 - 11:20 | Furfural – a intermediate for renewable fuels and chemicals awakening.

 Jean-Paul LANGE - *Shell Global Solutions Int. , Netherlands - University of Twente, Netherlands*

11:20 - 11:40 | Fine-tuned bimetallic Ru-based catalysts for hydroxymethylfurfural hydrodeoxygenation

 Agnieszka RUPPERT - *Lodz University of Technology, Poland*

11:00 - 12:20 | THU-T8-07 | Characterization of catalysts and of catalytic reactions - General

 Prestige Gratte Ciel

 Sylvain CRISTOL, Elena GROppo

11:00 - 11:20 | New Atomic-Scale Insights into Structure and Dealumination Process of USY Zeolites by High-Resolution 1H Solid-State NMR and DFT

 Mickael RIVALLAN - *IFPEN, France*

YT 11:20 - 11:40 | Newly identified [Cu-O-Cu]²⁺ and [CuOH]⁺ Sites in Zeolites for Selective Oxidation of Methane to Methanol

 Dieter PLESSERS - *KU Leuven, Belgium*

YT **11:40 - 12:00 | Disentangling Reaction and Deactivation of Single Oriented Sinusoidal and Straight Channels within Zeolite ZSM-5 Thin-films**

 Donglong FU - *Tianjin University, China, China*

12:00 - 12:20 | The use of experiment total neutron scattering and simulation techniques, with combined NMR.

 Terri-Louise HUGHES - *STFC, United Kingdom*

11:00 - 12:20 | THU-T14-01 | Catalysis at electrodes

 Amphitheatre

 Elena BARANOVA, Philippe VERNOUX

K **11:00 - 11:40 | Beyond Static Models: Chemical Dynamics in Energy Conversion Catalysts**

 Beatriz ROLDAN CUENYA - *Fritz Haber Institute of the Max Planck Society*

SO **11:40 - 11:48 | Development of a Highly Robust Oxide Anode for Water Electrolysis at Neutral pH Consisting of Cobalt and Iron**

 Hiroyuki OKADA - *Center for Research on GSC, Tottori University, Japan*

SO YT **11:48 - 11:56 | Hydride-Free Hydrogenation: Unraveling the Mechanism of Electrocatalytic Alkyne Semihydrogenation by Nickel-Bipyridine Complexes**

 Gabriel DURIN - *Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Germany*

SO YT **11:56 - 12:04 | Identification of Reactive Oxygen Surface Species During Electrochemical Alkene Epoxidation with H₂O on Au and Au-Alloys**

 Richa GHOSH - *Georgia Institute of Technology, United States*

SO **12:04 - 12:12 | Catalytic Condensers for Programmable Catalysis of Hydrocarbons**

 Paul DAUENHAUER - *University of Minnesota, United States*

SO **12:12 - 12:20 | Electrically-Driven Proton Transfer Promotes Brønsted Acid Catalysis by Orders of Magnitude**

 Karl WESTENDORFF - *Massachusetts Institute of Technology, United States*

11:00 - 12:20 | THU-T19-02 | Catalysis by metals and metal oxides

 Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

 Eric MARCEAU, Gina PECCHI

11:00 - 11:20 | Improving the catalytic recyclability of unsupported CuCo bimetallic nanocatalysts by carbon coating

Lorette SICARD - *ITODYS, Université Paris Cité, France*

11:20 - 11:40 | Low temperature exsolution of metal nanoparticles as a strategy towards the synthesis of active catalysts in C1 chemistry

Daniel DELGADO - *Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Fritz-Haber-Institut der Max-Planck-Gesellschaft, Germany*

K 11:40 - 12:20 | Low-Temperature Catalytic Water Activation and Hydrogen Production

Ding MA - *Peking University*

11:00 - 12:20 | THU-T22-04 | Catalytic reactions for hydrogen storage and release

Auditorium Pasteur

Ping CHEN, Justin HARGREAVES

11:00 - 11:20 | Ru/RScSi intermetallics for ammonia synthesis in mild conditions

Fabien CAN - *IC2MP (Institut de Chimie des Milieux et Matériaux de Poitiers), France*

11:20 - 11:40 | Phosphorus-modification improves activity and CO-stability of palladium-based catalysts for hydrogenation with impure hydrogen

Adrian SEITZ - *Institute of Chemical Reaction Engineering, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany*

11:40 - 12:00 | Conceptual design of a process for the use of liquid ammonia as hydrogen vector

Ilenia ROSSETTI - *Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy*

12:00 - 12:20 | Engineering 2D Mo-based MXenes and Application in Ammonia Synthesis

Amanda SFEIR - *Université de Lille, CNRS, ENSCL, Centrale Lille, Univ. Artois, UMR 8181-UCCS-Unité de Catalyse et de Chimie du Solide, France*

11:00 - 12:20 | THU-T25-05 | Valorization of C1 molecules (CH₄, CO, MeOH) except CO₂

Tête d'or 1+2

Narcis HOMS, Holger FRIEDRICH

11:00 - 11:20 | Coking and decoking chemistry for resource utilization of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and low-carbon process

Nan WANG - *Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China*

11:20 - 11:40 | Direct conversion of syngas to BTX/para-xylene aromatics over bifunctional catalysts based on large-crystal mesoporous ZSM-5

Agustin MARTINEZ - *Instituto de Tecnologia Quimica UPV-CSIC, Spain*

YT 11:40 - 12:00 | Revealing Key Morphology Factor and Constructing Directional Component Distribution of Syngas-to-Aromatics Catalyst

Chang LIU - *SINOPEC Shanghai Research Institute of Petrochemical Technology Co., Ltd., China*

12:00 - 12:20 | Oxide-zeotype bifunctional catalysts efficient for the conversion of CO to light olefins

Stephane LORIDANT - *Univ. Lyon, Université Claude Bernard-Lyon 1, CNRS, IRCELYON-UMR 5256, France*

11:00 - 12:20 | THU-T26-09 | CO2 conversion

Bellecour 1+2+3

Bruce GATES, Tommaso TABANELLI

11:00 - 11:20 | Direct CO2 hydrogenation to para-Xylene over Fe/ZnZr-ZSM5@SiO2 catalyst: Effect of calcination temperature to product distribution

Mansoor ALI - *School of Chemical Engineering, Sungkyunkwan University, South Korea, Korea (Republic of)*

11:20 - 11:40 | Cu-based methanol catalysts for CO2 hydrogenation: is the pre-treatment a really necessary step?

Mariarita SANTORO - *CNR-ITAE "Nicola Giordano", Via S. Lucia sopra Contesse, Italy*

SO 11:40 - 11:48 | Improving the performance of SSZ-39 and SAPO-18 by steaming towards CO2 hydrogenation to propylene

Ahmed SAJID - *KU Leuven, Belgium*

SO 11:48 - 11:56 | Development of Cascade Nanoreactors for the Direct Conversion of CO2 to Sustainable Marine Transportation Fuels

Maciej WALEROWSKI - *University of Southampton, United Kingdom*

SO 11:56 - 12:04 | Small Cobalt Nanoparticles Favor Reverse Water-Gas Shift Reaction Over Methanation Under CO2 Hydrogenation Conditions

Xiaoyu ZHOU - *ETH Zurich, Switzerland*

SO 12:04 - 12:12 | The effect of support on the mechanism of CO2 hydrogenation over supported Ru catalysts

Fabio BELLOT NORONHA - *National Institute of Technology, Brazil - Centrale Lille, France*

SO

12:12 - 12:20 | Rates, reversibility, and site densities for CO₂ hydrogenation on Cu-based catalysts

Ting LIN - *University of Minnesota-Twin Cities, United States*

11:40 - 12:20 | THU-T29-01 | Conversion of biomass and waste resources - Chemicals from biomass

Auditorium Lumière

George HUBER, Angeliki LEMONIDOU

11:40 - 12:00 | Core-shell structured magnesia-silica as next generation catalysts for one-step ethanol-to-butadiene Lebedev process

Sangho CHUNG - *KAUST Catalysis Center, Saudi Arabia*

YT

12:00 - 12:20 | Highly efficient iridium-iron-molybdenum catalyst for biomass-derived diols hydrogenolysis to secondary mono-alcohols

Ben LIU - *Tohoku University, Japan*

12:20 - 13:30 | Seated lunch / Lunch bags

12:20 - 14:00 | Lunch Break

12:30 - 13:30 | "Tending to our Roots" lunch event

Salon Pasteur

14:00 - 15:40 | THU-T2-01 | Molecular catalysis: main group and organocatalysis

Auditorium Pasteur

Anna M MASDEU-BULTO, Clément CAMP

K

14:00 - 14:40 | Bridging the gap between homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysis using Supramolecular cages

Joost REEK - *University of Amsterdam*

14:40 - 15:00 | Metallomimetic C-F activation catalysis by simple phosphines

Antoine SIMONNEAU - *Laboratoire de Chimie de Coordination du CNRS, France*

SO

15:00 - 15:08 | Barium Alginate Gel Beads: A Homochiral Porous Material from Brown Algae for Heterogeneous Asymmetric Catalysis

Luca BERNARDI - *University of Bologna, Italy*

SO	15:08 - 15:16 Synthesis of ZIF67 with recycling of 2-methylimidazole solution and impact on particle size	
	Cícero ÁVILA-NETO - <i>Federal University of Paraná, Brazil</i>	
SO	15:16 - 15:24 Geometrically constrained main-group elements for "low reorganization energy" catalysis	
	Kajetan BIJOUARD - <i>Université de Namur, Belgium</i>	
SO YT	15:24 - 15:32 Complexes of Tin and Aluminium hydrogenate CO2 and imines with H2	
	Martin HULLA - <i>Charles University, Czechia</i>	
SO	15:32 - 15:40 A NEW ALUMINUM COMPLEX BASED ON A NOVEL IMINE-AMIDINE LIGAND TO CONVERSION OF CO2 TO CYCLIC CARBONATES.	
	Fernando GÓMEZ - <i>Université Paul Sabatier, France - Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Chile</i>	
14:00 - 15:40 THU-T14-02 Catalysis at electrodes		
	Amphitheatre	
	Yuriy ROMAN-LESHKOV, Karine DE OLIVEIRA VIGIER	
	14:00 - 14:20 Influence of hydride formation in Pd/Au-based catalyst on the HMF electroreduction	
	Andrea CANCIANI - <i>University of Bologna, Italy - Center for Chemical Catalysis-C3, Italy</i>	
YT	14:20 - 14:40 Electrocatalytic hydrogenation of biomass-derived furfural on structured copper electrodes	
	Mathieu PRÉVOT - <i>CNRS-IRCELYON, France</i>	
	14:40 - 15:00 Carbon – carbon coupling during electrocatalytic hydrogenation of benzaldehyde on Cu/C	
	Hongwen CHEN - <i>Technical University of Munich, Germany</i>	
	15:00 - 15:20 Novel and Efficient Electrocatalytic Mediated Reduction Paths for Selective Oxidation	
	Matthew NEUROCK - <i>University of Minnesota, United States</i>	
	15:20 - 15:40 Controlling C(sp³)-H and C(sp³)-C(sp³) transformation at electrocatalytic interfaces for energy storage and sustainable synthesis	
	Marcel SCHREIER - <i>University of Wisconsin-Madison, United States</i>	

14:00 - 15:40 | THU-T16-01 | Data as the key resource in digital catalysis

📍 Tête d'or 1+2

👤 Annette TRUNSCHKE, Pedro MENDES, Stephan Andreas SCHUNK

14:00 - 14:20 | Machine learning approaches for improving catalyst design

👤 Parastoo SEMNANI - TU Berlin, Germany

14:20 - 14:40 | The fundamental role of published research data in the development of software tools for catalysis

👤 Abraham NIEVA DE LA HIDALGA - School of Chemistry Cardiff University, United Kingdom - UK Catalysis Hub Research Complex, Harwell, United Kingdom

14:40 - 15:00 | Language models and protocol standardization guidelines for accelerating synthesis planning in heterogeneous catalysis

👤 Manu SUVARNA - ETH Zurich, Switzerland

SO 15:00 - 15:08 | Establishing a collaboratively developed terminology for the catalysis disciplines as basis for FAIR data

👤 David LINKE - Leibniz Institute for Catalysis, Germany

SO 15:08 - 15:16 | Towards digitalization of the microkinetic modeling workflow

👤 Sofia ANGELI - Institute for Chemical Technology and Polymer Chemistry, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany

SO 15:16 - 15:24 | From Laboratory to Repository – Using an Electronic Laboratory Notebook in an Academic Laboratory

👤 Lisa BURKART - RWTH Aachen University, Institute for Inorganic Chemistry, Germany

SO 15:24 - 15:32 | Catalysts Synthesis Procedures Extraction from Synthesis Paragraphs using Large Language Models

👤 Daniel COSTA - Instituto Superior Tecnico, CQE, Portugal

SO 15:32 - 15:40 | Automated Review Generation Method Based on Large Language Models

👤 Shican WU - Tianjin University, China

14:00 - 15:40 | THU-T19-03 | Catalysis by metals and metal oxides

📍 Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

👤 Noémie PERRET, Tibor SZILVASI

14:00 - 14:20 | Ni₂P-based catalysts for the reductive amination of levulinic acid to 5-methyl-N-substitute-2-pyrrolidones

14:20 - 14:40 | Fe-based heterogeneous catalysts for N-alkylation of amines with alcohols

 Yusuke KITA - *Osaka Metropolitan University, Japan*

YT **14:40 - 15:00 | Selective Vapor-Phase Oxidative Coupling of Methanol and Dimethylamine to Dimethylformamide over Bimetallic Catalysts**

 James HARRIS - *The University of Alabama, United States*

YT **15:00 - 15:20 | Synthesis of asymmetric ketones intermediates by cross-ketonization**

 Jacopo DE MARON - *Department of Industrial Chemistry "Toso Montanari", University of Bologna, Viale Risorgimento 4, 40136, Italy*

15:20 - 15:40 | Potential of Titanium Suboxides as Novel Materials for Catalysts

 Ryoichi OTOMO - *Faculty of Environmental Earth Science, Hokkaido University, Japan*

14:00 - 15:40 | THU-T25-06 | Valorization of C1 molecules (CH₄, CO, MeOH) except CO₂

 Auditorium Lumière

 Unni OLSBYE, Yves SCHUURMAN

14:00 - 14:20 | CANCELLED - Direct conversion of CO and H₂O to hydrocarbons at atmospheric pressure using a TiO₂-x/Ni photothermal catalyst

 Xuetao QIN - *College of Chemistry and Molecular Engineering, Peking University, China*

14:20 - 14:40 | Visualization of metastable oxygen-nickel phases during self-oscillatory dry reforming of methane

 Luis SANDOVAL-DIAZ - *Fritz-Haber-Institut der Max-Planck-Gesellschaft, Germany*

14:40 - 15:00 | Exploring the Operational Envelope of Electrified Steam Methane Reforming of Biogas: A Pilot Plant Story

 Thomas FROM - *Topsoe A/S, Denmark - Aarhus University, Denmark*

K **15:00 - 15:40 | Conversion of methane to methanol over Cu-zeolites in a stepwise reaction - structure performance relationships**

 Stian SVELLE - *Department of Chemistry, University of Oslo*

14:00 - 15:40 | THU-T26-10 | CO₂ conversion

 Bellecour 1+2+3

 Manish SHETTY, Holger FRIEDRICH

YT **14:00 - 14:20 | Hierarchically ordered macro-, and mesoporous MOF-based electrocatalysts for CO2 reduction**

 Liyu CHEN - *South China University of Technology, China*

14:20 - 14:40 | Ni(acac)₂ anchored on hydroxyapatite: Preparation, characterization and catalytic activity in the CO2 methanation reaction

 Nassima BERROUG - *Faculty of Science and Technology, Universidad del País Vasco UPV/EHU, Spain*

14:40 - 15:00 | Zr-based Metal-Organic Frameworks loaded with highly dispersed small size Ni nanoparticles for CO2 methanation

 Hongmei CHEN - *Collège de France, France*

15:00 - 15:20 | Understanding Fe-Catalyzed CO2 Hydrogenation to Higher Hydrocarbons through Introducing Promoters by Physical Mixing

 Laura KRAUßER - *Leibniz Institute for Catalysis, Germany*

14:00 - 15:40 | THU-T29-02 | Conversion of biomass and waste resources - Chemicals from biomass

 Prestige Gratte Ciel

 Mickael CAPRON, Amandine CABIAC

14:00 - 14:20 | (Poly)saccharide conversion: from thermal-catalysis to electro-catalysis and from monomer to polymer

 Harry BITTER - *Wageningen University, Netherlands*

14:20 - 14:40 | Transformation of aldoses to methyl-ketosides promoted by bifunctional Brønsted-Lewis Sn-Al-USY zeolites

 Miriam EL TAWIL-LUCAS - *Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain*

14:40 - 15:00 | Mechanistic Investigation on the Reactivity of Sugars over Homogenous Tungsten- and Molybdenum-Oxoanions

 Kim LARMIER - *IFP Energies nouvelles, France*

SO **15:00 - 15:08 | Observing Electrochemical Conversion of Furfural with Nanoporous Catalyst Utilizing In-situ Surface Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy**

 Yu-Shuo LEE - *National Taiwan University, Taiwan*

SO 15:08 - 15:16 | **Selective oxidative depolymerization of lignin to vanillin and lactic acid production**

 Peng MINGMING - *Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology, Japan*

SO 15:16 - 15:24 | **Heterogeneous catalytic oxidation of furfural with hydrogen peroxide over a niobium catalyst**

 Wander PEREZ SENA - *Åbo Akademi University, Finland*

SO 15:24 - 15:32 | **Fine-tuned Ru catalysts for selective formation of ring hydrogenation or ring-opening products from 5-hydroxymethylfurfural**

 Preeti KASHYAP - *Institute of General and Ecological Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, Lodz University of Technology, Poland*

SO 15:32 - 15:40 | **Enhanced Dehydration of Methyl Lactate to Methyl Acrylate over Organic-Free Potassium-ZSM-5 Catalysts**

 Seung Hyeok CHA - *Green Carbon Research Center, Korea Research Institute of Chemical Technology (KRICT), Korea (Republic of)*

15:40 - 16:10 | Coffee break - Exhibition - Posters

 Exhibition Hall

16:10 - 17:30 | PAN01 | Panel Session : Future of refining and chemicals in the context of decarbonization and sustainable development

 Auditorium Lumière

We are moving to rapid changes, of energy landscape (e.g. integration of low carbon hydrogen, electrification ...), of feedstocks (e.g. bio-sources or waste streams ...) with a reduction of reliance on fossil fuels, evolution towards more efficient, sustainable and resilient technologies with increased focus on the CO₂ footprint... Catalysis has played a crucial role in the development of refining and petrochemical processes.

- ▶ What will be the role of catalysis in shaping the future of refining and petrochemistry ?
- ▶ What are the critical research gaps and technological innovations needed ?

The panel session will bring together industrialists and academia to exchange on the different challenges that these changes bring to catalysis in the field of refining and petrochemistry.

Moderators:

- John MURPHY
- Clyde PAYN (The Catalyst group)

Panelists:

- Quentin Debuisschert (Axens)
- Maxime Lacroix (TotalEnergies)
- Doron Levin (ExxonMobil)
- Hong Nie (Sinopec)
- Ferdi Schuth (Max Planck Institute for Coal Research)

16:10 - 17:30 | PAN02 | Panel Session : Future of industrial chemistry in the context of sustainable development

📍 Bellecour 1+2+3

Catalysis has played a crucial role in the development of chemical processes. The rapid emergence of renewable energies, the scarcity of resources (metals, minerals, water, etc.) and the need to reduce the CO₂ emissions of catalysts/chemicals/processes together with their environmental and societal impact are now radically changing the face of catalysis. This round table will mainly address the two following questions:

- ▶ What will be the main scientific hurdles faced by industry in the field of catalysis, in a context of sustainable development?
- ▶ What are the main industrial expectations in terms of research in the field of catalysis for the next ten years?

Moderator:

- Mathieu ROUAULT (Journalist)

Panelists:

- Nicolas Bats (Johnson Matthey)
- Philippe Marion (SYENSQO)
- Stephan Schunk (HTE)
- Tihana Tresler (Saint-Gobain)

16:10 - 17:30 | PAN03 | Panel Session : The Present and Future of Electricity-Based Heating in Catalysis

📍 Prestige Gratte-Ciel

The transition scenarios to the low-carbon energy in the chemical process industries are commonly based on the so-called Power-to-X concept, which basically assumes using the low-carbon or renewable electricity to produce fuels and/or chemicals.

While the electrocatalytic production of fuels from water, CO₂ or nitrogen is undoubtedly of fundamental importance for decarbonizing (or rather defossilizing) the chemical sector, it is equally important to address possible applications of electricity-based heating methods, such as microwave, radio-frequency, induction/hysteresis or Joule heating, in industrial catalysis.

Examples of questions to be discussed:

- ▶ Are some of the novel heating technologies more promising than the other?
- ▶ Will we have enough renewable electricity to supply?
- ▶ Integrated, large-scale processes Vs. distributed, small-scale manufacturing?
- ▶ Are expected decarbonisation effects large enough to justify the efforts?
- ▶ Process economy: can this ever beat current technologies?
- ▶ Industrial acceptance: how to make a convincing business case for the industry?
- ▶ How should further efforts be financed?

Moderators:

- Andrzej STANKIEWICZ
- Enrico TRONCONI

Panelists:

- Georgios Stefanidis (National Technical University of Athens)
- Bruno Chaudret (University of Toulouse)
- Dongxia Liu (University of Delaware)
- Reyes Mallada (University of Zaragoza)
- Alan Chaffee (Monash University)

16:10 - 17:30 | PAN04 | Panel Session : Data as the key resource in digital catalysis

📍 Auditorium Pasteur

How can data become a renewed source of knowledge in catalysis? How data sharing and curation be valued? How should experimental and computational datasets be composed and structured to enable evaluation by artificial intelligence? Do we need quality control and certified benchmarks and how can this be implemented institutionally? How catalysis informatics current tools can leverage data being poured online by open science policies? What is the upcoming role of machine learning and artificial intelligence in the catalysis research workflow?

The goal of this round table is to discuss as a community where we stand today in terms of data related practices, digitalization of catalysis, and what we need to ensure that digital data becomes central to catalysis and which tools can take us further in our scientific endeavor.

Round table Organisation (total duration 1h20):

- ▶ Participant introduction (short)
- ▶ Main discussion : Q&A between chairs and panelists
- ▶ Questions open to Audience
- ▶ Short wrap-up / conclusion

Moderators:

- Annette TRUNSCHKE
- Pedro MENDES

Panelists:

- Sandip De (BASF)
- Núria López (ICIQ)
- Ramazam Yildirim (Bogazici University)
- Rebecca Fushimi (Idaho National Laboratory)

16:10 - 17:30 | PAN05 | Publishing Panel session: Meet the editorial boards!

📍 Amphitheatre

The Young Scientists Committee is delighted to host a publishing panel session with esteemed representatives from the editorial boards of leading journals in catalysis which will be presented soon.

This session will include:

- ▶ A "Writing skills" tutorial lecture :
by Sandra González Gallardo (ChemCatChem - Chemistry Europe - Wiley)
- ▶ A panel discussion about the intricacies of the publishing process, shedding light on best practices, current trends, and the evolving landscape of digital publishing.

Moderators:

- Anastasiia EFREMOVA
- Liliana GONCALVES
- Samira KURTOGLU-OZTULUM
- Clément CAMP

Panelists:

- Sandra González Gallardo (ChemCatChem, Chemistry Europe - Wiley)
- Amy Welch (Chemical Science, RSC)
- Susannah Scott (ACS Catalysis, ACS)
- Kazuhiro Takanabe (Journal of Catalysis, Elsevier)
- Eric Piechota (Nature Communications, Nature publishing group)

17:30 - 19:30 | Poster Session 3

 Exhibition Hall

20:00 - 01:00 | Conference Gala Dinner

 La Sucrière

20:00 - 01:00 | Young Scientists Party

 Le Sucre

Friday 19 July

08:00 - 17:30 | Registration

Hall Bellecour

08:30 - 09:15 | PL05 | Plenary Lecture - Ulrike DIEBOLD: "Oxide Surface Science: Chemistry at the Atomic Scale"

Amphitheatre

Katia BERNARDO-GUSMÃO

09:25 - 10:25 | FRI-T1-01 | Molecular catalysis: metal-based catalysts

Auditorium Pasteur

Rafael GRAMAGE-DORIA

K 09:25 - 10:05 | Late Transition Metal Catalysts for Polymer Synthesis and Degradation

Kyoko NOZAKI - *The University of Tokyo*

10:05 - 10:25 | Electrochemically recoverable homogeneous catalyst: genesis, application and capturing

Dmitry PIRGACH - *Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands*

09:25 - 10:25 | FRI-T4-05 | Preparation of heterogeneous catalysts

Prestige Gratte Ciel

Malika BOUALLEG, Changhui LIANG

YT 09:25 - 09:45 | Spray-dried supraparticles as promising heterogeneous catalysts

Susanne WINTZHEIMER - *Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany*

SO 09:45 - 09:53 | Hierarchical zeolite single crystal reactor for maximum catalytic efficiency

Li-Hua CHEN - *State Key Laboratory of Advanced Technology for Materials Synthesis and Processing, Wuhan University of Technology, China*

SO 09:53 - 10:01 | Preparing single site isolated Fe sites in zeolites through solid state framework aluminium mobility

Max BOLS - *Universiteit Gent, Belgium*

SO **10:01 - 10:09 | Decoupling Nickel Particle Size and Support Effects in the Catalytic CO₂ Hydrogenation by Colloidal Synthesis**

 Bram KAPPÉ - *Utrecht University, Netherlands*

SO **10:09 - 10:17 | Genesis of Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalysts from an organometallic precursor under oxidative/reductive atmospheres monitored by in-situ FTIR.**

 Martin COTONI - *IFPEN, France*

SO **10:17 - 10:25 | Enhancing CO₂ Utilization via Janus Structured Catalytic Nanoparticles in Dry Reforming Processes**

 Heesu KIM - *Department of Environmental and Energy Engineering, Yonsei University, Korea (Republic of)*

09:25 - 10:25 | FRI-T11-01 | Chemical engineering and process technologies for catalysis

 Bellecour 1+2+3

 Enrico TRONCONI, Dmitry MURZIN

K **09:25 - 10:05 | Electricity is in the catalyst: a reaction engineering approach to gas treatment and valorization**

 Joris THYBAUT - *Ghent University*

10:05 - 10:25 | Face the challenges of net-zero emissions and electrification of production: new possibilities by unconventional catalysis

 Gabriele CENTI - *University of Messina and ERIC aisbl, Italy*

09:25 - 10:25 | FRI-T14-03 | Catalysis at electrodes

 Auditorium Lumière

 Umit OZKAN, Marcel SCHREIER

09:25 - 09:45 | Operando X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy study of Ni/YSZ solid oxide cell cathode electrodes during H₂O and CO₂ electroreduction

 Jinming ZHANG - *ICPEES-UMR 7515 CNRS-ECPM-Université de Strasbourg, France*

09:45 - 10:05 | Co-electrolysis of H₂O and CO₂ at intermediate temperatures with protonic ceramic cell reactors

 Vassilis KYRIAKOU - *Engineering and Technology Institute Groningen, University of Groningen, Netherlands*

10:05 - 10:25 | Probe the effect of A-site deficiency on the PrNi_{0.7}Co_{0.3}O_{3-x} perovskite materials for protonic ceramic electrochemical cells

 Haiyan ZHAO - *University of Idaho, United States*

09:25 - 10:25 | FRI-T19-04 | Catalysis by metals and metal oxides

Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

Eric MARCEAU, Cathy Ya-Huei CHIN

09:25 - 09:45 | Selective ortho a-C Alkylation of Phenol with Alcohols over Anatase TiO₂

Z. Conrad ZHANG - *Changzhou University, China - Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, China*

SO 09:45 - 09:53 | Ni nanoparticles on a Covalent Triazine Framework: an effective catalyst for Ammonia Borane Hydrolysis and Transfer Hydrogenations

Xuan Trung NGUYEN - *CNR-ICCOM, Italy*

SO 09:53 - 10:01 | Bismuth promoting role in Pt-based catalyst for aerobic alcohol oxidation

Anna Giorgia NOBILE - *ETHZ, Switzerland*

SO 10:01 - 10:09 | Design of CuCo bimetallic nanoparticles for the acceptorless dehydrogenation of alcohols

Ning HUANG - *Université Paris Cité, France*

SO 10:09 - 10:17 | Insights into the synergistic effect of CuCoMgAl mixed metal oxide on the conversion of furfuryl alcohol to 1,5-pentanediol

Asier BARREDO - *Faculty of Engineering Bilbao, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Spain*

SO 10:17 - 10:25 | Pd coated on original elastomeric structured catalytic support for selective hydrogenation of phenylacetylene in gasliquid reactor

Mohamad FAYAD - *CPE Lyon, France*

09:25 - 10:25 | FRI-T29-03 | Conversion of biomass and waste resources - Chemicals from biomass

Amphitheatre

Karine DE OLIVEIRA VIGIER, Elodie BLANCO

09:25 - 09:45 | CANCELLED - Mechanistic Insights into the C–O Bond Hydrogenolysis of O-Containing Heterocycles into α,ω -Diols over Selective Nickel Catalysts

Mohammed AL-YUSUFI - *Leibniz Institute for Catalysis (LIKAT), Germany*

YT 09:45 - 10:05 | Unlocking Sustainable Chemistry: Aldaric Acid to Biobased Adipates through Selective Deoxydehydration Process

Brigita HOCEVAR - *National Institute of Chemistry, Ljubljana, Slovenia, Slovenia*

10:05 - 10:25 | From 2-methylfuran to Renewable and Recyclable Polyesters

 Raul LOBO - *University of Delaware, United States*

09:25 - 10:25 | FRI-T31-01 | Water and air treatment

 Tête d'or 1+2

 Luca LIETTI, Pascal GRANGER

09:25 - 09:45 | Enhancing the catalytic activity of Pd-based catalysts for methane oxidation by oxygen oscillations

 Oliver KRÖCHER - *Paul Scherrer Institut, Switzerland - EPFL, Switzerland*

SO 09:45 - 09:53 | Copper(II) phosphate as promising catalyst for degradation of ciprofloxacin via photo-Fenton process.

 Mateusz ROZMYSLAK - *Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland*

SO 09:53 - 10:01 | Insights into Enhanced Catalytic Performance of Au-TiOx@TiO2 for Low Temperature CO Oxidation

 Liam BAILEY - *Max Planck-Cardiff Centre on the Fundamentals of Heterogeneous Catalysis FUNCAT, Cardiff Catalysis Institute, United Kingdom*

SO 10:01 - 10:09 | Fe and Ni-doped La_{1-x}Sr_xTiO₃ perovskites for selective catalytic reduction of NO by H₂

 Lucas DIOT - *IRCELYON, France*

SO 10:09 - 10:17 | Impact of mild hydrothermal aging on NH₃, NO, CO and SO₂ oxidation kinetics on a Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst

 Tetyana ZHELEZNYAK - *University of Chemistry and Technology, Czechia*

SO 10:17 - 10:25 | Efficient removal of paracetamol for wastewater treatment with mesostructured TiO₂ prepared through Solution Combustion Synthesis

 Nadia GRIFASI - *Politecnico di Torino, Italy*

10:25 - 11:00 | Coffee Break

 Exhibition Hall

11:00 - 12:20 | FRI-T1-02 | Molecular catalysis: metal-based catalysts

 Auditorium Pasteur

 Kyoko NOZAKI, Rafael GRAMAGE-DORIA

11:00 - 11:20 | Dual Catalysis of Gold Nanocluster toward Photocatalytic Cross-Dehydrogenative Coupling between Amines and Alkynes

	<p>	
	<p>11:20 - 11:40 Selective Thermo-responsive Hydrogenation using Ru Nanoparticles Immobilized on Aluminophosphate-Based SILP Catalysts</p> <p>	
SO	<p>11:40 - 11:48 Electrocatalytic Hydrogenation of Alkenes at an Oil-Water Interface</p> <p>	
SO	<p>11:48 - 11:56 Amine-Modified Ionic Liquid Polymer Supported Palladium Nanoparticles Catalyse CO₂ Hydrogenation to Formate</p> <p>	
SO	<p>11:56 - 12:04 Photo-dehalogenation reaction with homoleptic copper(I) complexes through reductive quenching : mechanistic study</p> <p>	
SO	<p>12:04 - 12:12 "Marriage" of C-H activation and chain-walking: Ir-catalyzed hydroarylation for the remote functionalization</p> <p>	
SO	<p>12:12 - 12:20 Identifying the promotional role of promoters in Rh-based catalysts for CO_x hydrogenation</p> <p>	
	<p>11:00 - 12:20 FRI-T5-03 Computational approaches at the atomic scale of catalysis - General</p> <p> Dorota RUTKOWSKA-ZBIK, Tomas BUCKO</p>	
YT	<p>11:00 - 11:20 Computational investigation on the photocatalytic CO₂ reduction promoted by Ni(II)-containing polyoxometalates</p> <p>	
	<p>11:20 - 11:40 Computational identification of active linear polymer/molecule photocatalysts for H₂ evolution reaction</p> <p>	
SO	<p>11:40 - 11:48 Catalysis in Confinement: Mechanism of C-X Coupling with a Cu-calix[8]arene Catalys</p>	

 Maren PODEWITZ - *TU Wien, Austria*

SO **11:48 - 11:56 | Toward improved predictions of spectroscopic properties of molecules on surfaces: the weakly bound CO on CeO₂ surfaces**

 Juana VÁZQUEZ QUESADA - *Institut für Nanotechnologie, Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT), Germany*

SO **11:56 - 12:04 | From Electrons to Reactors: ab initio multi-scale simulation of methane oxidation over palladium oxide**

 Crispin COOPER - *Johnson Matthey Technology Centre, United Kingdom*

SO YT **12:04 - 12:12 | The Influence of Strong Metal Support Interaction Phenomena on the Rates and Selectivity of Formic Acid Decomposition**

 Tej CHOKSI - *Nanyang Technological University, Singapore*

SO **12:12 - 12:20 | Unveiling closed and open site stability of Sn-, Ti-, Hf- and Zr-Beta zeolite: A DFT investigation for biomass sugar conversion**

 Nawras ABIDI - *IFP Energies nouvelles, France*

11:00 - 12:20 | FRI-T14-04 | Catalysis at electrodes

 Auditorium Lumière

 Mathieu PRÉVOT, Carine MICHEL

11:00 - 11:20 | Adsorbate-Induced Restructuring of Copper Electrodes in Electroreduction Conditions

 Zisheng ZHANG - *University of California Los Angeles, United States*

11:20 - 11:40 | Identical location AFM to study the surface evolution on different facets of polycrystalline Cu during CO₂ electroreduction

 Hui WANG - *Utrecht University, Netherlands*

11:40 - 12:00 | Impact of Site Heterogeneity of Cu on the Electrochemical CO₂ Reduction Reaction

 Bingjun XU - *Peking University, China*

YT **12:00 - 12:20 | Continuous glycerol oxidation reaction coupled with gas-phase electrocatalytic reduction of CO₂ to formate**

 Guillermo DIAZ-SAINZ - *University of Cantabria, Spain*

11:00 - 12:20 | FRI-T19-05 | Catalysis by metals and metal oxides

📍 Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

👤 Noémie PERRET, Jean-Yves PIQUEMAL

11:00 - 11:20 | Effects of Cl, Re, and Cs on rates and selectivity in ethylene oxide synthesis on Ag-based catalysts

👤 Andrey KARPOV - BASF SE, Germany

11:20 - 11:40 | Catalytic Requirements of Alkane and Alkanol Activation on Transition Metal Oxides

👤 Cathy Ya-Huei CHIN - University of Toronto, Canada

11:40 - 12:00 | Ceria nanooctahedra as an efficient metal-free catalyst for the oxidation of alcohols

👤 Anne PONCHEL - University of Artois, France

12:00 - 12:20 | Catalytic Conversion of Dialkyl Disulfides into Hydrocarbons and H₂S with Water as a Hydrogen Donor

👤 Vasile HULEA - University of Montpellier, ENSCM, Charles Gerhardt Institute, France

11:00 - 12:20 | FRI-T29-04 | Conversion of biomass and waste resources - Chemicals from biomass

📍 Amphitheatre

👤 Adam CHOJECKI, Fábio BELLOT NORONHA

K 11:00 - 11:40 | Catalytic valorization of lignocellulose to low-molecular oxygen- and nitrogen-containing compounds

👤 Tao ZHANG - Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics

11:40 - 12:00 | Tuning acid-base properties of magnesium silicate catalysts for the gamma-valerolactone ring opening reaction

👤 Albert ISSA - Sorbonne Université, Laboratoire de Réactivité de Surface, France - ENSTA UCP, IP Paris, France

YT 12:00 - 12:20 | Continuous Flow Production of gamma-Valerolactone from methyl-levulinate promoted by MOF-derived Al₂O₃-ZrO₂/C catalysts

👤 Emilia PAONE - Università degli Studi Mediterranea di Reggio Calabria, Italy

11:00 - 12:20 | FRI-T31-02 | Water and air treatment

Tête d'or 1+2

Atsushi FUKUOKA, Fabien CAN

11:00 - 11:20 | Boosting N₂O Decomposition by Fabricating Cs-O-Co Structure over Co₃O₄ with Single-layer Atoms of Cs

Lei MA - *School of Environmental Science and Engineering, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China*

11:20 - 11:40 | Stability of highly dispersed Pd/CeO₂ catalysts under hydrothermal and realistic three-way catalysis conditions

Valentin JESTL - *Eindhoven University of Technology, Netherlands*

11:40 - 12:00 | Gas-phase composition dependence of low-T NO_x Adsorption/Desorption over Pd/CHA: a combined micro-reactor and operando FT-IR study

Lidia CASTOLDI - *Politecnico di Milano, Italy*

12:00 - 12:20 | Formation and Reactivity of Cage-Confined Cu Pairs in Catalytic NO_x Reduction over Cu-SSZ-13 Zeolites

Peirong CHEN - *South China University of Technology, China*

11:00 - 12:28 | FRI-T11-02 | Chemical engineering and process technologies for catalysis

Bellecour 1+2+3

Pascal FONGARLAND

11:00 - 11:20 | Propane Dehydrogenation in Electrifiable Carbon Membrane Reactor

Dongxia LIU - *University of Delaware, United States*

11:20 - 11:40 | Multi-stage Structured-Catalyst System for Post-treatment of Greenhouse Gas Emitted from Industrial Process

Choji FUKUHARA - *Graduated School of Integrated Science and Technology, Shizuoka University, Japan*

SO 11:40 - 11:48 | Hydroformylation of olefines with CO₂ as CO precursor, an electrochemical-catalytic tandem approach.

Mario GALLONE - *Politecnico di Torino, Italy*

SO 11:48 - 11:56 | Chemical-looping application for CH₄ decomposition and CO₂ activation on Ni-Co/MgAl₂O₄

Yuchen DENG - *Natural Science Campus (16419), 2066 Seobu-ro, Jangan-gu, Suwon-si, Gyeonggi-do, South Korea, Korea (Republic of)*

SO 11:56 - 12:04 | Ferrite/zeolite hybrid materials for inductive heating of adsorbents and catalysts

 Maxim DE BELDER - *KU Leuven, COK-KAT, Belgium - VUB, CHIS, Belgium*

SO 12:04 - 12:12 | Membrane reactors for methanol synthesis: from material science to process simulation

 Vincent GAUTIER - *CEA, France - CEA, France - ICPEES, France*

SO 12:12 - 12:20 | Activation, cracking and deactivation of iron-aluminum composites in methane cracking into turquoise hydrogen and fibrous carbon

 Shihyuan CHEN - *16-1 Onogawa, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305-8569, Japan. , Japan*

12:20 - 13:30 | Seated lunch / Lunch bags

12:20 - 14:00 | Lunch Break

12:30 - 13:30 | "Tending to a Better Future" lunch event

 Salon Pasteur

14:00 - 16:00 | FRI-T1-03 | Molecular catalysis: metal-based catalysts

 Auditorium Pasteur

 Nicolas KAEFFER, Antoine SIMONNEAU

14:00 - 14:20 | Enhanced catalysis of metal complex and organocatalyst by surface environment for synthetic reactions

 Ken MOTOKURA - *Yokohama National University, Japan*

14:20 - 14:40 | Overcoming Low Reactivity of Aryl Chlorides: Bachwald-Hartwig Type Amination by Reusable Polymeric Nickel-Iridium Dual Catalysis

 Yoichi M. A. YAMADA - *RIKEN Center for Sustainable Resource Science, Japan*

14:40 - 15:00 | Towards the Electrification of Metal-Ligand Cooperative Catalysts

 Niklas VON WOLFF - *Université Paris Cité/CNRS, France*

15:00 - 15:20 | Selective supramolecular iridium-catalyzed C-H borylations enabled by remote weak coordination chemistry

 Rafael GRAMAGE-DORIA - *University Rennes, France*

15:20 - 15:40 | Mechanistic insights on Co-qpy mediated CO₂ reduction to CO

 Marcos GIL SEPULCRE - *Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Germany*

15:40 - 16:00 | Titanium, hydrogen peroxide and polyoxometalates for oxidation catalysis

 Geoffroy GUILLEMOT - Sorbonne Université, France

14:00 - 16:00 | FRI-T4-06 | Preparation of heterogeneous catalysts

 Gratte Ciel 1+2+3

 Catherine ESPECEL, Fábio BELLOT NORONHA

14:00 - 14:20 | Aerosol-assisted sol-gel to mesoporous bifunctional catalysts for the upgrading of bioethanol to butadiene

 Damien DEBECKER - University Louvain la Neuve, Belgium

14:20 - 14:40 | Efficient CO₂ hydrogenation on monolithic Fe-based catalysts benefits from mass/heat-transfer enhancement via 3D printing

 Shiyuan LIN - China University of Petroleum (East China), China

YT 14:40 - 15:00 | Towards unconstrained catalyst shaping: DLP printing of porous γ -Al₂O₃ catalysts

 Luca MASTROIANNI - Åbo Akademi University, Finland - Università degli studi di Napoli Federico II, Italy

15:00 - 15:20 | Humid air glidarc plasma: an innovative method for heterogeneous catalysts synthesis

 Fanny HANON - UCLouvain, Belgium

15:20 - 15:40 | Tuning the Reactivity of Cobalt Modified Hydroxyapatite by Rationalization of Precipitation and Co Ions Immobilization Mechanisms

 Guylene COSTENTIN - Laboratoire Réactivité de Surface, CNRS-Sorbonne Université, France

15:40 - 16:00 | Additively Manufactured In₂O₃/ZrO₂ catalysts and their performance in the direct methanol synthesis

 Emiliano DAL MOLIN - Technische Universität Berlin, Germany

14:00 - 16:00 | FRI-T5-04 | Computational approaches at the atomic scale of catalysis - General

 Prestige Gratte Ciel

 Hazar GUESMI, Mark SAEYS

14:00 - 14:20 | Cerium-Oxide-Bound CO Vibrations: Beyond DFT's Comfort Zone

14:20 - 14:40 Ab initio thermodynamic study of the oxidative dispersion of Pt nanoparticles on ceria 	
14:40 - 15:00 Quantifying Elusive Interface Effects in Catalytic Nanomaterials Combining DFT Modelling and Experiment 	
15:00 - 15:20 Principle of metal-support interaction for supported catalysts 	
15:20 - 15:40 DFT study of the effect of surface structure and Al₂O₃ modification of Pt catalyst for propane dehydrogenation 	
15:40 - 16:00 Structural and electronic properties of d-sp hybridization nano-catalysts, In-Pd as a case study 	
14:00 - 16:00 FRI-T11-03 Chemical engineering and process technologies for catalysis Joris THYBAUT, Clemence NIKITINE	
14:00 - 14:20 Kinetics of catalytic reactions on nanoclusters with limited cluster occupancy 	
14:20 - 14:40 Liquid Phase Oxidation of Propylene to Propylene Oxide with H₂O₂ on TS-1: Spatially Resolved Measurements and Reactor Simulation 	
14:40 - 15:00 Kinetic investigation of CH₄ pyrolysis on Fe-Al₂O₃ catalysts: a combined experimental and modeling study 	
15:00 - 15:20 Direct biogas cracking to green H₂ and carbon material by microwave heated catalytic fluidized bed reactor	

 Valentin L'HOSPITAL - *IRCELYON-CNRS, France*

15:20 - 15:40 | MACBETH – Progress on the implementation of more sustainable hydroformylation by supported liquid phase (SLP) catalysis

 Anders RIISAGER - *Technical University of Denmark, Denmark*

15:40 - 16:00 | Accelerating Multi-Scale Modeling of Catalytic Devices through Machine Learning Surrogates - an overview

 Felix DÖPPEL - *Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany*

14:00 - 16:00 | FRI-T14-05 | Catalysis at electrodes

 Auditorium Lumière

 Philipp RÖSE, Guillermo DIAZ-SAINZ

14:00 - 14:20 | Ir-based Single-atom-ensemble Catalyst for Durable Acidic Water Electrolysis

 Ashwani KUMAR - *Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, 45470 Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany, Germany*

YT **14:20 - 14:40 | CANCELLED - Accelerated Discovery of Stable and Active Materials for Oxygen Electrocatalysis**

 G. T. Kasun Kalhara GUNASOORIYA - *University of Oklahoma, United States*

14:40 - 15:00 | Au-decorated NiMo/Ti Electrocatalysts for Efficient Borohydride Electro-oxidation and Oxygen Reduction Reaction in Alkaline Media

 Sukomol BARUA - *Center for Physical Sciences and Technology (FTMC), Lithuania*

15:00 - 15:20 | Vacuum-connected setups for electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution in alkaline electrolyte

 Yi CUI - *Suzhou Institute of Nano-Tech and Nano-Bionics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China*

SO **15:20 - 15:28 | Engineering Stable Polyelectrolytes for Applications in AEM Electrolysers**

 Samuel POWER - *Newcastle University, United Kingdom*

SO **15:28 - 15:36 | Enhanced oxygen reduction reaction activity and durability of 14-membered ring Fe complex by heat treatment**

 Zhiqing FENG - *Graduate School of Science and Technology, Kumamoto University, Japan*

SO YT **15:36 - 15:44 | A unified theory for the origin of H₂ evolution activity in Mo-based catalysts**

SO **15:44 - 15:52 | Experimental design approach for optimizing nickel nanoparticles synthesis by polyol route**

SO **15:52 - 16:00 | Opportunities for Selectivity Control of High-flux CO Reduction and CO₂ Reduction over Cu Enabled by Microkinetic Analysis**

14:00 - 16:00 | FRI-T29-05 | Conversion of biomass and waste resources - Chemicals from biomass

 Amphitheatre

 Nathalie TANCHOUX, Dorothée LAURENTI

14:00 - 14:20 | Selective hydrogenation of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural using atomically dispersed hydrotalcite oxide supported copper catalysts

14:20 - 14:40 | Catalyst design and mechanistic studies for the HMF oxidation over bimetallic PdxPty-based catalysts

14:40 - 15:00 | The effect of Ag addition to Au catalysts for the oxidation of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural to 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid

15:00 - 15:20 | Synthesis of glycerol levulinates in the presence of Sn(IV) catalysts

15:20 - 15:40 | Effect of isolated atoms on dilute limit alloy bimetallic catalysts for aqueous phase furfural hydrogenation

15:40 - 16:00 | Reductive amination of acetal-protected 2,5-diformylfuran to 2,5-Bis(aminomethyl)furan using Co₂P Nanorods (NRs) catalyst

14:00 - 16:00 | FRI-T31-03 | Water and air treatment

 Tête d'or 1+2

14:00 - 14:20 | Designing Self-Healing Catalysts for High Temperature Applications

14:20 - 14:40 | Dynamic operation for improved low-temperature activity and water tolerance of catalysts for total oxidation of methane

14:40 - 15:00 | Microbiological air quality: catalytic inactivation of airborne pathogens

15:00 - 15:20 | Low-temperature Oxidation of Ethylene by Supported Platinum Catalysts for Preservation of Fruits and Vegetables

15:20 - 15:40 | Novel aerosol-made CuO-CeO₂ catalysts with superior CO oxidation activity

15:40 - 16:00 | Catalytic hydrogenation of chlorates by bimetallic Pt-V catalysts.

2020 Heinz Heinemann Award of IACS Lecture - Avelino CORMA: "Ab initio design of solid catalysts: From the fundamentals to the application"

 Amphitheatre

17:00 - 17:30 | CLO | Closing Ceremony

 Amphitheatre

17:30 - 18:00 | Closing drink

 Foyer Forum 6 - Level-2

Poster

15.07 17:30 - 19:30 | MON-POST01 | Poster Session 1

Exhibition Hall

T17 **Kinetic model for the catalytic aquathermolysis of Boca de Jaruco heavy oil using water-soluble catalyst**

Guillermo FÉLIX - *Kazan Federal University, Russian Federation*

T30 **Upcycling of PVC to hydrocarbon adhesive waxes**

Konstantinos GOULAS - *Oregon State University, United States*

T3 **MON-POST01-1 | Tailor-made immobilization of enzymes for flow reactions under unconventional conditions**

André DELAVault - *Institute for biological Interfaces 1 (IBG-1), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Germany*

T3 **MON-POST01-2 | Biocatalysis of phenolic compounds toward selective C-C coupling using laccase from Trametes versicolor**

Amandine FLOURAT - *URD ABI - AgroParisTech, France*

T3 **MON-POST01-3 | Rational design of functional hybrid catalysts for furfural transformation**

Enrica GIANOTTI - *Department for Sustainable Development and Ecological Transition, Università del Piemonte, Italy*

T3 **MON-POST01-4 | Calcium-based Y zeolite: A targeted and regulable activator of coagulation factor Xa**

Chaojie SHI - *Zhejiang University, China*

T3 **MON-POST01-5 | Chemo-enzymatic C-H Bond Activation via in-situ H₂O₂ Production**

Alex STENNER - *Cardiff University, United Kingdom*

T3 **MON-POST01-6 | Synthesis of Biodegradable Polymer Precursor from CO₂ and Acetaldehyde by Using Multi-enzymes**

Kazuma SUEHIRO - *Graduate School of Science, Osaka Metropolitan University, Japan*

T3 **MON-POST01-7 | Unlocking the Potential of Levoglucosan: A Renewable Resource for Sustainable Chemical Industry**

Robert WOJCIESZAK - *Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, France*

T3	MON-POST01-8 Protein-polymer conjugates as artificial enzymes for new-to-nature catalysis	
	Changzhu WU - <i>University of Southern Denmark, Denmark</i>	
T3	MON-POST01-9 Development of visible-light driven alanine production with photo/biocatalyst	
	Kyosuke YAMADA - <i>Graduate School of Science, Osaka Metropolitan University, Japan</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-12 The use of fly ashes from energy sector as promising starting components for synthesis of catalytic materials	
	Andrzej ADAMSKI - <i>Jagiellonian University, Poland</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-13 Catalytic Advancement Through Sustainable Synthesis of 2D Materials	
	Shamma ALHASHMI - <i>The University of Manchester, United Kingdom - Technology innovation institute, United Arab Emirates</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-14 Solid Catalyst with Ionic Liquid Layer (SCILL) for the direct hydrogenation of CO2 to methanol	
	Nancy ARTIOLI - <i>University of Brescia, Italy</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-15 Ionic Liquid Synthesis of Catalysts for Direct CO2 Hydrogenation to short-chain hydrocarbons	
	Nancy ARTIOLI - <i>Univervsity of Brescia, Italy</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-16 Surface modified silica as a unique support for 5-HMF valorization	
	Jaroslav AUBRECHT - <i>University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Department of Sustainable Fuels and Green Chemistry, Czechia</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-17 Tailoring γ-alumina catalysts supports via boehmite paste kneading conditions	
	Mathilde AUXOIS - <i>IFP Energies nouvelles, France - ENSL, CNRS, Laboratoire de physique, France</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-18 Precise Tin Loading on PdSn Bimetallic Catalysts Leveraging In-Situ Controlled Surface Deposition for Nitrate Reduction	
	Janek BETTING - <i>University of Twente, Netherlands</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-19 Synthesis of calcium and cobalt catalysts using eggshell employed in the catalytic oxidation of hydrocarbons.	

T4	MON-POST01-21 Optimization and Scale-Up of Catalyst Manufacturing Unit Operations	
	Bill BORGHARD - <i>Rutgers University, United States</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-22 Intermetallic CaNi₂Si₂ as a Non-Noble Metal-Based Catalyst for Selective Hydrogenation of Unsaturated Organic Anhydrides/Acids	
	Xiao CHEN - <i>Dalian University of Technology, China</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-23 Can carbon dots be used as a metal catalyst support?	
	Neil COVILLE - <i>University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-24 Synthesis of Mg-doped Aluminophosphates from Waste Materials	
	Catherine CROCKETT - <i>Durham University, United Kingdom</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-25 Bimetallic catalyst synthesis with controlled composition and structure and application for renewable chemical production	
	Weijian DIAO - <i>Villanova University, United States</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-26 Sustainable development of ZSM-5 using rice husk ash and treatments with microwave and ultrasound for catalysis applications	
	Dirléia DOS SANTOS LIMA - <i>Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-27 Fabrication of gold and silica macroporous nanotubes, from 1D to 3D ordered networks using templating methods	
	Fabien DRAULT - <i>UCLouvain, Belgium</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-28 Porous capsules with liquid core prepared by Pickering emulsion: Diffusional phenomena understanding for catalyst implementation	
	Rémi DUCLOS - <i>IFP Energies Nouvelles, France - Laboratoire de chimie, ENS de Lyon, France</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-29 A systematic study of the experimental parameters that govern the catalytic activity of sol immobilised AuPd nanoparticles	
	Jennifer EDWARDS - <i>Cardiff University, United Kingdom</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-30 New perspectives for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis: development and advanced characterization of next-generation catalysts	
	Rabia ELBUGA-ILICA - <i>IKFT/ITCP, KIT, Germany</i>	

T4	MON-POST01-31 PREPARATION OF MULTI-COMPONENT LAMELLAR MATERIALS BASED ON ZEOLITIC LAYERS AND HYDROTALCITE SUB-DOMAINS	
T4	MON-POST01-32 Improving Coke Resistance of Ni/MgAl₂O₄ Catalysts in Methane Dry Reforming by Tuning Metal-Support Interactions	
	Sofie FERWERDA - <i>Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-33 Highly Active and Efficient Cu-Cr Catalysts for Low Temperature Oxidative Dehydrogenation of Propane	
	Patrick LOTT - <i>Institute for Chemical Technology and Polymer Chemistry, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-34 Effect of metal distribution across shaped supports on the performance of supported Pd catalysts in the CO₂ methanation reaction	
	Zafeiria FRAGKOU TOPALOGLOU - <i>Unité de Catalyse et Chimie du Solide (UCCS) – UMR CNRS 8181, Université de Lille, France</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-35 Synthesis of zeolite without template from rice husk ash and ultrasound	
	Camila Ottonelli CALGARO - <i>Instituto Federal Sul-Rio-Grandense (IFSul), Pelotas, Brasil, Brazil</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-36 Boosting the total oxidation of toluene by non-thermal plasma-assisted synthesis of supported copper oxide	
	Jean-Marc GIRAUDON - <i>University of Lille, France</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-37 Novel synthesis of a core@shell CHA with a highly siliceous shell	
	Clément GOT - <i>IFPEN, France - IRCELYON, France</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-38 Catalytic ammonia decomposition over Ru on hydrothermally-derived carbon: The tuning of catalyst support	
	Miranda GUCI - <i>Fraunhofer Institute of Solar Energy Systems, Germany</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-39 Mechanochemical Synthesis of Metal Oxide Composite Catalysts for Reverse Water Gas Shift Reaction	
	Wei HAN - <i>The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-40 Isopropanol dehydration over ZSM-5 synthesized from municipal Al and Si raw material	
	Jorge Guillermo HUERTA-MUÑOZ - <i>Universidad Autónoma de San Luis Potosí, Mexico</i>	

T4	MON-POST01-41 Synthesis of gold supported catalysts by humid air glidarc plasma	
	Fanny HANON - <i>UCLouvain, Belgium</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-42 What are the species involved in the gliding arc plasma synthesis of heterogeneous catalysts?	
	Fanny HANON - <i>UCLouvain, Belgium</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-43 Catalysis using monolayer of isocyanide on gold surface	
	Kenji HARA - <i>Tokyo University of Technology, Japan</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-44 Optimizing co-precipitation processes of magnesium silicates as catalysts for the GVL ring-opening reaction	
	Albert ISSA - <i>Sorbonne Université, Laboratoire de Réactivité de Surface, 4 place Jussieu, 75005 Paris, France</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-45 The Magic of Morphology: A TiO₂ Story	
	Anusha JAIN - <i>Indian Institute of Technology Delhi (IIT Delhi), India</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-46 Encapsulation of metallic oxide aggregates in siliceous materials for catalysis	
	Raphaël DEL CERRO - <i>IFPEN, France</i>	
T4	MON-POST01-47 Spray-flame-synthesized nanoparticulate M_xMg_{1-x}O (M=Co, Ni, Fe, Ru) catalyst precursors for NH₃ conversion to hydrogen	
	Baris ALKAN - <i>Dr. , Germany</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-50 Catalytic peroxidation of cyclohexane over Cu-N,N,N,N complexes: an insight on the mechanism by Cu-intermediates characterization	
	Mouhammad ABU RASHEED - <i>Centre for Materials Science and Nanotechnology, Department of Chemistry, University of Oslo, Norway</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-51 Functionalization of cenospheres from fly ashes towards their tailored catalytic applications	
	Andrzej ADAMSKI - <i>Jagiellonian University, Poland</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-52 The Interaction of Bio-oil with Pillared Clay Supported Nickel-Molybdenum Catalysts	
	Indri ADILINA - <i>National Research and Innovation Agency, Indonesia</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-53 Unveiling Mechanistic Insights: DFT and SSITKA-DRIFTS Analysis of Ni/CeO₂/Al₂O₃ Catalysts for Enhanced CO₂ Methanation	

	Ayesha ALKHOORI - <i>Khalifa University, United Arab Emirates - Center for Catalysis and Separation (CeCaS), United Arab Emirates</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-54 AuCu/TiO₂ catalysts in the CO oxidation: An in-situ DRIFT, UV-Vis, and Raman spectroscopy analysis Daniel G. ARAIZA - <i>Instituto de Ciencias Aplicadas y Tecnología, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-55 Influence of Extraframework Aluminum Species on Catalytic Properties of Acidic USY in Hydrocracking and Cracking Reactions Sohrab ASKARLI - <i>King Abdullah University of Science and Technology, Saudi Arabia</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-56 Insight into structure-activity relationships of SiO₂-supported bimetallic Pd-Fe catalysts for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol Angelo BELLIA - <i>ETH Zürich, Switzerland</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-57 Probing Catalyst Stability during Unsaturated Fatty Acid Hydrogenation in the Liquid Phase by In-Situ Fluorescence Spectroscopy Jelle BOS - <i>Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-58 In situ study of isopropanol dehydration to propylene: pulse catalytic test coupled with calorimetry. Tristan CABANIS - <i>Univ Lyon, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, CNRS, IRCELYON, France</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-59 Unravelling the influence of chemical composition on the oxidation behavior of Au_xPd_{1-x} bimetallic nanoparticles by in situ ETEM Francisco J. CADETE SANTOS AIRES - <i>IRCELYON (UMR 5256 CNRS/UCBLyon1), France</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-60 Low temperature methane activation pathways over mechanochemically-generated Ce⁴⁺/Cu⁺ interfacial sites Marta BOARO - <i>Università degli Studi di Udine, Italy</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-61 Design of bifunctional silica-based nanomaterials for the catalytic conversion of carbon dioxide into cyclic carbonates Chloé CÉLIS - <i>Université de Namur, Belgium</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-62 Design and optimisation of model Co-Mn Fischer-Tropsch synthesis catalysts Revana CHANERIKA - <i>Catalysis Institute, Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Cape Town, South Africa</i>	

T8	MON-POST01-63 Operando Raman Spectroscopy Revealing Reactive Forms of Oxygen in Ethylene Epoxidation	
T8	MON-POST01-64 Effect of External Surface Acidity and Pore Volume of Metal-modified MFI-type Zeolites on Methanol Aromatization	
	Ning CHEN - <i>Zeolite Group, Inorganic Materials Reserach Laboratory, Tosoh Corporation, Japan</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-65 Ni-La perovskites for CO2 methanation: impact of the catalysts structure	
	Luca CONSENTINO - <i>ISMN-CNR, Italy - STEBICEF - University of Palermo, Italy</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-66 Monitoring Restructuring and Activation of Oxide-derived Copper Electrocatalysts during CO2 Reduction	
	Jim DE RUITER - <i>Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-67 Pre-imaging tools for deeper understanding morphologies, structure and composition of micro and nanostructures - V205 case study	
	Andréa DUARTE DE FARIAS - <i>Instituto Nacional de Tecnologia, Brazil</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-68 Phosphine-based NMR probe molecules for quantification and spatial distribution of metal-based catalytic sites	
	Michael DYBALLA - <i>Insitute of Technical Chemistry, University of Stuttgart, Germany</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-69 Origin of the Pt/MexOy synergy effect for driving activity and selectivity in the CO2 hydrogenation ?	
	Anastasiia EFREMOVA - <i>University of Szeged, Department of Applied and Environmental Chemistry, Hungary</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-70 Novel sol-gel synthesis of fluorinated titania for acid catalysis	
	Fouad ELGAYAR - <i>IRCELYON, France</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-71 Promotional role of acid sites on aluminosilicate-supported PdAu for vinyl acetate synthesis	
	Welman ELIAS - <i>RICE University, United States</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-72 Acidity requirement and reaction pathway for the dehydration of 1,3-butanediol to butadiene over ZSM-22	
	Loïc ELOI - <i>Ghent University, Belgium</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-73 In situ UV-vis spectroscopy of 1-butene oligomerization to fuels	

T8 **MON-POST01-74 | Use of carbon nanotubes as support for cobalt catalysts in chemical vapor deposition**

 Laura M. ESTEVES - *Instituto Superior Técnico - Centro de Química Estrutural, Portugal*

T8 **MON-POST01-75 | Mono-directional pressure-induced downsizing of zeolite crystals increases their catalytic performances**

 Mohammad FAHDA - *Laboratoire Catalyse et Spectrochimie (LCS), Normandie Université, ENSICAEN, UNICAEN, CNRS, France*

T8 **MON-POST01-76 | Dual-site Promotion of CO₂ Hydrogenation to Methanol on ZnZrOx catalyst**

 Zhendong FENG - *Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China - University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, China*

T8 **MON-POST01-77 | Operando X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy of Nickel-based Dry Methane Reforming Catalysts Under Industrially Relevant Conditions**

 Sofie FERWERDA - *Utrecht University, Netherlands*

T8 **MON-POST01-78 | Catalytic oxidation of cyclohexene over Cu-functionalized mixed-linker Ce-UiO-67 metal-organic frameworks**

 Silvia BORDIGA - *University of Turin, Italy*

T8 **MON-POST01-79 | Unravelling Channel Structure–Diffusivity Relationships in Zeolite ZSM-5 at the Single-Molecule Level**

 Donglong FU - *Tianjin University, China, China - Inorganic Chemistry and Catalysis group, Debye Institute for Nanomaterials Science, Faculty of Science, Utrecht University, Universiteitsweg 99, 3584 CG Utrecht (The Netherlands), Netherlands*

T8 **MON-POST01-80 | Twofold Operando X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy Approach to Unravel Synergistic Effects in Multi-metal CO₂ Hydrogenation Catalysts**

 Nina S. GENZ - *Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland - Inorganic Chemistry and Catalysis, Utrecht University, Netherlands*

T8 **MON-POST01-81 | Mechanistic Aspects of NH₃-SCR on Copper Hydroxyapatite by Operando DRIFT Spectroscopy**

 Antonella GERVASINI - *University Milano, Italy*

T8 **MON-POST01-82 | Single-Step Propane Transformation on Vanadium-Supported Catalyst Revealed by Operando DRS UV-Vis Study**

 Kinga GÓRA-MAREK - *Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland*

T8	MON-POST01-83 Nb2O5/PET waste Activated Carbon: efficient catalysts for oxidation of the prothioconazole fungicide from water	
T8	MON-POST01-84 Acidic sites at the Boron Nitride surfaces as catalysts for acetylene dimerization	
	Antonio GUERRERO-RUIZ - <i>UNED, Spain</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-85 Utilizing One-Pot Synthesis to Create Mesoporous Ti-SBA-15 Catalysts for the Oxidative Desulfurization of Dibenzothiophene	
	Adisak GUNTIDA - <i>Laboratoire Catalyse et Spectrochimie (LCS), UNICAEN, Normandie Université, ENSICAEN, France</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-86 Selective Coke Removal from Ferrierite used in 1-Butene Isomerization	
	Karoline L. HEBISCH - <i>Georgia Institute of Technology, United States</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-87 Advanced STEM-EDX tomography of bimetallic Pd-Ni nanoparticles	
	Kristiaan HELFFERICH - <i>Materials Chemistry & Catalysis, Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-88 Understanding passivation: a tool facilitating the characterisation of metal-containing catalysts	
	Elisabeth Hannah WOLF - <i>Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Germany</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-89 Iso-Potential Operando DRIFTS: Measuring Adsorbate Profiles Inside Catalytic Reactors	
	Oliver KORUP - <i>Hamburg University of Technology, Institute of Chemical Reaction Engineering, Germany - Reacnostics GmbH, Germany</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-90 Hierarchical zeolites ZSM-5: preparation, characterization and application	
	Michal HORNACEK - <i>Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology, Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Radlinského 9, 812 37 Bratislava, Slovakia, Slovakia</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-91 Development of cobalt oxide catalysts for effective liquid phase oxidation reactions	
	Nobuyuki ICHIKUNI - <i>Chiba University, Japan</i>	

T8	MON-POST01-92 Understanding Coke Deposition over Ni-Based Catalysts for Dry Methane Reforming	
	Disha JAIN - <i>Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-93 Spectro-Kinetics of Carbocation Transformations in Zeolite Pores	
	Dipti BHAVE - <i>University Massachusetts Amherst, United States</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-94 Evaluation of O₂ Adsorption Sites on TiO₂ Using Organic Molecules as Probes.	
	Masaya KIMURA - <i>Graduate School of Engineering, Tokyo University of Technology, Japan</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-95 Improving Water Resistance and N₂ Selectivity over NH₃-SCR Catalysts via Encapsulating Mn Oxide Nanoparticle in Silicalite-1 Shell	
	Sarah KOMATY - <i>King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST), Saudi Arabia</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-96 Genesis of Catalytically Active Cuprous Acetylide in Ethynylation: The Importance of Formaldehyde	
	Lingdi KONG - <i>Technical University of Munich, Germany</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-97 Boron Nitride Nanotube Supported Transition Metal Catalysts for CO₂ Methanation	
	Jan KOPYSCINSKI - <i>Catalytic and Plasma Process Engineering Laboratory, McGill University, Canada</i>	
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	Ive HERMANS - <i>University of Wisconsin - Madison, United States</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-99 MoO_x@SiO₂ yolk-shell catalysts for olefin metathesis induced by propane dehydrogenation	
	Piotr KUSTROWSKI - <i>Faculty of Chemistry, Jagiellonian University, Poland</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-100 Alternative raw materials for methanol oxidative dehydrogenation catalysts	
	Velma KIMBI YAAH - <i>Environmental and Chemical Engineering, University of Oulu, Finland</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-101 Insights into Activation of Iron Oxide and Metallic Iron by Tuning Atmospheric Stoichiometry of H₂/CO	
	Xingwu LIU - <i>Synfuels China Technology Co.Ltd. , China</i>	

T8	MON-POST01-102 in Situ Magnetometry Advances for Size Characterisation of Ferromagnetic Catalysts	
T9	MON-POST01-105 Operando MES-DRIFT/Raman study on the role of gold and vanadium on ceria-based catalysts for toluene total oxidation	
	Miguel A. BANARES - <i>CSIC - Insituto de Catalisis y Petroleoquimica, Spain</i>	
T9	MON-POST01-106 Zeolite pore-space exploration during methanol-to-hydrocarbon reaction using	<i>infrared crystallography</i>
	Bettina BAUMGARTNER - <i>Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
T9	MON-POST01-107 Full Field XAS Hyperspectral Imaging: a powerful tool to highlight the mechanisms involved in the preparation of a CoMoP catalyst	
	Olivier DELPOUX - <i>IFP Energies nouvelles, France</i>	
T9	MON-POST01-108 Efficient Workflows for Real Time Analysis of Products and Nanostructure in Catalysts	
	Tim ELDRED - <i>Protochips Inc, United States</i>	
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	Filippo BUTTIGNOL - <i>Paul scherrer Institute, Villigen, Switzerland</i>	
T9	MON-POST01-110 Speciation of Ni@C catalysts through high resolution hard X-ray spectroscopy	
	Giovanni GARCIA SABOIA DE ALBUQUERQUE - <i>Universität Paderborn, Germany</i>	
T9	MON-POST01-111 Tracking Surface Changes on hBN during the Oxidative Dehydrogenation of Propane using Operando X-Ray Raman Spectroscopy	
	Ive HERMANS - <i>University of Wisconsin - Madison, United States</i>	
T8	MON-POST01-112 Effect of Bronsted acidity of zeolite on catalytic cracking of LDPE	
	Soshi TSUBOTA - <i>Nishiyama lab, graduate school of engineering science, Osaka University, Japan</i>	
T9	MON-POST01-113 Tracking Coordination Environment and Reaction Intermediates in Homo- & Heterogenous Epoxidation Catalysts via Ti L2,3-edge NEXAFS	
	Lukas LÄTSCH - <i>Department of Chemistry and Applied Biosciences, ETH Zürich, Switzerland</i>	

T9	MON-POST01-114 A modulated study of the MgO-Ni interface in a MgO-Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst for CO₂ methanation	
	Servaas LIPS - <i>Ghent University, Belgium</i>	
T9	MON-POST01-115 Understanding Catalytic Sulfur Poisoning via Ultra-High Spatial Resolution Nano-FTIR Spectroscopy at the Nanometer Scale	
	Emrah OZENSOY - <i>Bilkent University, Turkey</i>	
T9	MON-POST01-116 Nanospectroscopic investigation of the external surface of ZSM-5 zeolite crystal upon steaming	
	Mickael RIVALLAN - <i>IFPEN, France</i>	
T9	MON-POST01-117 Surface Area Measurement of Metal Oxides by Selective Adsorption of Organic Molecules	
	Lei SHANG - <i>Graduate School of Engineering, Tokyo University of Technology, Japan</i>	
T9	MON-POST01-118 Temperature-programmed desorption up to 2100 °C as a new high-sensitivity analytical method for nitrogen-doped carbon	
	Takeharu YOSHII - <i>Tohoku University, Japan</i>	
T10	MON-POST01-121 Propene Ammoxidation by Forced Dynamic Operation over Bismuth Molybdate Based Catalysts	
	William EPLING - <i>University of Virginia, United States</i>	
T10	MON-POST01-122 Scanning pulse analysis FASP and SPGC - New transient tools to study complex catalytic reactions at industrial relevant conditions	
	Frederik KAPTEIJN - <i>Delft University of Technology, Netherlands</i>	
T10	MON-POST01-123 Characterization of oxygen storage capacity of ceria with CO pulse chemisorption coupled with isotopic oxygen tracing.	
	Urim Pearl KIM - <i>Micromeritics Instrumentation Corp, United States</i>	
T10	MON-POST01-124 Fundamentals for controlling product selectivity in CO₂ hydrogenation to higher hydrocarbons over Fe-based catalysts	
	Evgenii KONDRATENKO - <i>Leibniz-Institut für Katalyse e.V. (LIKAT), Germany</i>	
T10	MON-POST01-125 From Transient to Steady-State CO hydrogenation over TiO_x-promoted Co catalysts at atmospheric pressures	
	Norbert KRUSE - <i>Voiland School of Chemical Engineering and Bioengineering, Washington State University, United States</i>	
T10	MON-POST01-126 Exploring Surface Structure-Dependent Kinetics to unravel Molecule-Surface Interactions	

	<p>Florian NITZ - <i>Institute for Physical Chemistry, Georg-August University of Goettingen</i>, 37077 Goettingen, Germany, Germany - Department of Dynamics at Surfaces, Max Planck Institute for Multidisciplinary Sciences, Germany</p>	
T10	<p>MON-POST01-127 Application of steady-state isotopic transient kinetic analysis in metathesis of ethylene with 2-butene to propene</p> <p>	
T10	<p>MON-POST01-128 Transient Pseudo-Random Binary Sequence (PRBS) Gas Injections for the Determination of Elementary Rate Constants</p> <p>	
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T10	<p>MON-POST01-131 How ZrO₂-support impacts the structure sensitivity of Cu nanoparticles for CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol</p> <p>	
T11	<p>MON-POST01-134 Low-pressure oligomerization of diluted ethylene with syngas</p> <p>	
T13	<p>MON-POST01-135 Preparation of BiOBr and bismuth-rich photocatalysts for the removal of paracetamol</p> <p>	
T13	<p>MON-POST01-136 Surface modification to activate a non-oxide photocatalyst sheet in Z-scheme water splitting</p> <p>	
T13	<p>MON-POST01-137 Elaboration and characterization of photocatalytic g-C₃N₄ nanotube membranes</p> <p>	
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T13	MON-POST01-139 Conformal 'CuO' from Cu-peptides on α-Fe₂O₃ nanoarrays in photoelectrocatalytic water oxidation	
	Tímea BENKÓ - <i>HUN-REN Centre for Energy Research, Hungary</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-140 Discovering the potential of two versatile organic polymers incorporating BTBT units as metal-free heterogeneous photocatalysts	
	M.carmen BORRALLO-ANICETO - <i>ICMM-CSIC, Spain</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-141 Improved photocatalytic performances of highly fluorinated graphitic carbon nitride	
	Tara BUZDON - <i>Institut de Chimie de Clermont-Ferrand, France</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-142 Photocatalytic and biocide properties of Ag/g-C₃N₄ nanomaterials	
	Sergio FUENTES-MOYADO - <i>Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Centro de Nanociencias y Nanotecnología, Mexico</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-143 g-C₃N₄-ZnO composite as an efficient photocatalyst for Ceftriaxone degradation	
	Sergio FUENTES-MOYADO - <i>Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Centro de Nanociencias y Nanotecnología, Mexico</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-144 Effect of CeO₂ Nanorods on the Photocatalytic Performance of Pd-TiO₂ for Hydrogen Production	
	Sergio FUENTES-MOYADO - <i>Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Centro de Nanociencias y Nanotecnología, Mexico</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-145 Photocatalytic Reduction of Carbon Dioxide by BiTeX (X = Cl, Br, I) under Visible-Light Irradiation	
	Chiing-Chang CHEN - <i>Department of Science Education and Application, National Taichung University of Education, Taiwan</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-146 Visible Light Catalyst for Indoor Air Quality Applications	
	Adam CHOJECKI - <i>Dow Benelux B.V., Netherlands</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-147 Optimization of PVDF-TiO₂ phase inversion photocatalysis for VOC degradation	
	Ewoud COSAERT - <i>Ghent University, Belgium</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-148 Design Of Metal-Organic Frameworks-Based Composites For Visible-Light-Driven Heterogeneous Photocatalysis	
	Khaled DASSOUKI - <i>Institut Lavoisier de Versailles, UMR CNRS 8180, Université de Versailles St Quentin en Yvelines, Université Paris Saclay, France</i>	

T13	MON-POST01-149 Modified phyllosilicates for solar fuels production	
T13	MON-POST01-150 Blue LED-Driven Photo-oxidative Functionalization of Natural Bioactive Compounds	
	Elisa DE MARCHI - <i>Università degli Studi di Torino, Italy</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-151 Photocatalytic reforming of glycerol to hydrogen and small oxygenates	
	Jacopo DE MARON - <i>Department of Industrial Chemistry "Toso Montanari", Bologna University, Viale Risorgimento 4, 40136, Italy</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-152 Enhancing hydrogen generation in carbon nitride materials: Synergistic effects of crystallinity, cyanamide groups and alkali metal	
	Gabriel DIAB - <i>Department of nanochemistry, Max Planck Institut für Festkörperforschung, Germany</i> - <i>Department of Chemistry, Federal University of São Carlos, Brazil</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-153 Formation, Surface Structure and Photocatalytic Performance of Titania Thin Layers from Atomic Layer Deposition in Solution	
	Fei DING - <i>Center for Interface Research and Catalysis in Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen- Nürnberg Erlangen, Germany</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-154 Photo-thermal catalysis and in-situ spectroscopy reveal the role of light in the RWGS reaction mechanism over Cu/Al₂O₃	
	Petar DJINOVIC - <i>National Institute of Chemistry, Slovenia</i> - <i>University of Nova Gorica, Slovenia</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-155 Charge Transfer Mediation in Doped Layered Perovskite Nanosheets for Photocatalytic H₂ Production	
	Mengqi DUAN - <i>University of Oxford, United Kingdom</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-156 New graphene-based composites as outstanding materials for Photocatalysis	
	Laura M. ESTEVES - <i>Instituto Superior Técnico - Centro de Química Estrutural, Portugal</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-157 TiO₂-silver zeolites nanocomposites for ethylene adsorption and photocatalytic oxidation for fruit preservation	
	Filipa RIBEIRO - <i>CQE- Centro de química estrutural, IMS, Instituto Super Técnico, Portugal</i>	

T13	MON-POST01-158 Solvothermal Synthesis of Kusachiita: Unlocking a Rare Material for Water Splitting	
T13	MON-POST01-159 Sustainable Removal of Emerging Contaminants in Water by Facile-Synthesized Bismuth Oxyhalides	
	Daniel FLORES-RAMÍREZ - <i>Unidad Profesional Interdisciplinaria en Ingeniería y Tecnologías Avanzadas - Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Mexico</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-160 Reduction of CO2 by visible-active perovskites: development of solar powered photocatalysts	
	Giulia FORGHIERI - <i>Ca'Foscari University of Venice, Italy</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-161 ZnO obtained from spent alkaline batteries as photocatalyst for carbamazepine degradation	
	Maria GALLEGOS - <i>CINDECA, Argentina</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-162 Understanding Defect Engineering in Lanthanum-Doped NaTaO3 for Cocatalyst-Free Overall Photocatalytic Water Splitting	
	Michael GOEPEL - <i>Leipzig University, Institute of Chemical Technology, Germany</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-163 Effect of morphology and heterojunctions in BiVO4 thin films made by Physical Vapor Deposition on the visible light photocatalysis	
	Mathias GOUTTE - <i>Institut de Chimie de Clermont-Ferrand (ICCF), France</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-164 Cerium titanates: An unexplored class of UV active photoanodes for water splitting	
	Cyril HACHEMI - <i>CNRS - IRCELYON, France</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-166 Photocatalytic degradation of Oxytetracycline with Bi-Pr codoped SrZrO3 ceramic powders	
	Diana L. HERNÁNDEZ-ARELLANO - <i>Instituto de Investigaciones en Materiales Unidad Morelia, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-167 Effect of Ni, Cr, and Pr doping on the BiYO3 structure and its photocatalytic properties	
	Diana Laura HERNÁNDEZ-ARELLANO - <i>Instituto de Investigaciones en Materiales Unidad Morelia, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-168 Glycerol photoreforming: comparison of the photocatalytic efficiency and mechanism of binary and ternary Pt-g-C3N4-TiO2 systems	

	<p>M. Carmen HERRERA-BEURNIO - <i>Departamento de Química Orgánica, Instituto Químico para la Energía y el Medioambiente (IQUEMA), Universidad de Córdoba, E-14071 Córdoba, Spain, Spain</i></p>	
T13	<p>MON-POST01-169 Kinetic modeling for photocatalytic pollutant removal: accurate quantum yield calculation as function of process variables</p> <p>Philippe HEYNDERICKX - <i>Ghent University Global Campus, Korea (Republic of) - Faculty of Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Belgium</i></p>	
T13	<p>MON-POST01-170 Study of enhanced photocatalytic activity under UV-light irradiation of Ln₂WO₆ and mixed Bi_{2-x}Ln_xWO₆ (Ln = Lanthanide) compounds</p> <p>Svetlana HEYTE - <i>Realcat platform, Univ. Lille, CNRS, Centrale Lille, Univ. Artois, UMR 8181 – UCCS – Unité de Catalyse et Chimie du Solide, France</i></p>	
T13	<p>MON-POST01-171 Photodeposition of Fe-Based Cocatalysts Effectively Promoting the Oxygen Evolution Activity of BaTaO</p> <p>Takashi HISATOMI - <i>Shinshu University, Japan - PRESTO-JST, Japan</i></p>	^{2N}
T13	<p>MON-POST01-172 Visible light harvesting alkyne hydrosilylation mediated by pincer platinum complexes</p> <p>Laura IBÁÑEZ-IBÁÑEZ - <i>Institute of Advanced Materials (INAM), Jaume I University, Spain</i></p>	
T13	<p>MON-POST01-173 Removal of methylene blue by modified perovskite catalysts SrZnFeO₃</p> <p>Kahina IKKOUR - <i>university, Algeria</i></p>	
T13	<p>MON-POST01-174 Overall water splitting under visible light irradiation over doped KTaO₃ photocatalysts</p> <p>Akihide IWASE - <i>Meiji University, Japan</i></p>	
T13	<p>MON-POST01-175 Efficient Ag co-catalyst prepared by ultrasonic reduction method for photocatalytic conversion of CO₂ over ZnTa₂O₆ photocatalyst</p> <p>Kio KAWATA - <i>Ichikawa Research Center, Sumitomo Metal Mining Co., Ltd., Japan - Department of Molecular Engineering, Kyoto University, Japan</i></p>	
T13	<p>MON-POST01-176 Temperature dependence of photocatalytic water splitting over SrTiO₃:Ir,Sb,Al under visible light irradiation</p> <p>Erika KIKUCHI - <i>Department of Applied Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Tokyo University of Science, Japan</i></p>	

T13	MON-POST01-177 Photocatalytic Properties of TiO₂/Sr₄Al₁₄O₂₅:Eu²⁺, Dy³⁺ Composites	
	Jung-Sik KIM - <i>University of Seoul, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-178 One-pot hydrothermal synthesis of tungsten-based photocatalysts for the photocatalytic degradation of 5-Fluorouracil under solar-LED.	
	Velma Beri KIMBI YAAH - <i>University of Oulu, Finland - University of Granada, Spain</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-179 Photocatalytic CO₂ reduction to form carbon monoxide and hydrocarbons using water as an electron donor	
	Akihiko KUDO - <i>Tokyo University of Science, Japan</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-180 Solar-Light-Mediated Photocatalytic Oxidative Coupling of Phenols over Bismuth-based Porous Metal Halide Perovskites	
	Jinsun LEE - <i>Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Germany</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-181 Z-scheme Water Splitting Using BaTaO₂N:Zr as a Hydrogen Evolution Photocatalyst	
	Wenpeng LI - <i>Graduate School of Medicine, Science and Technology, Shinshu University, Nagano, Japan, Japan</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-182 Efficient Solar-Driven Splitting of Seawater at Elevated Temperatures over Facet-Controlled TiO₂	
	Yiyang LI - <i>University of Oxford, United Kingdom</i>	
T13	MON-POST01-183 ZnO system from hydrozincite, effect of synthesis at different temperatures for their photocatalytic application degradation	
	Montserrat ESPINOZA BAUTISTA - <i>CIEMAD/IPN, Mexico</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-185 Investigation of the Fe role in paraffin cracking over Al-free Fe-ZSM-5 zeolites	
	Anastasia KURBANOVA - <i>Faculty of Science, Charles University, Czechia</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-186 Highly-Efficient Fe-Si Slurry-phase Hydrocracking Catalyst via Modulating Electronic Structure of Fe	
	Xiaojun BAO - <i>Fuzhou University, China</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-187 Application of methanesulfonic acid as substitute of sulfuric/hydrofluoric acids in the production of alkylate gasoline.	
	Heriberto DIAZ VELAZQUEZ - <i>Mexican Petroleum Institute, Mexico</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-188 Advanced aviation and marine bio-fuels via hydroprocessing of microbial lipids	

T17	MON-POST01-189 Grading schemes of hydrotreating catalysts based on progressive reaction theory	
	Si-Jia DING - <i>Dalian Research Institute of Petroleum and Petrochemicals, SINOPEC, China</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-190 Alternative to Claus process through COS as intermediate. Part 1: CO2 and H2S competitive adsorption on zeolite 13X	
	Helene RETOT - <i>Saint-Gobain CREE, France</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-191 Influence of Pt species in high-efficiency propane dehydrogenation catalysts on the formation of Carbon deposition precursor	
	Jianhao JIAO - <i>College of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, China University of Petroleum (East China) Qingdao 266555, Shandong Province, China., China - Key Laboratory of Petrochemical Catalytic Science and Technology, Liaoning Petrochemical University, China</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-192 Supported Iron Nanoparticles as sustainable Catalysts for selective Acetylene Hydrogenation under industrial Front-End Conditions	
	Hannah LAMERS - <i>Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-193 Comparison of Ni-based catalysts in the combined steam/dry reforming of bio-oil	
	Sergio IGLESIAS - <i>University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Department of Chemical Engineering, Spain</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-194 Hydroconversion of heavy aromatic compounds for xylene-rich BTX Production	
	Jung Kyoo LEE - <i>Dong-A University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-195 Beneficial Effect of Fe Catalysts and Water Contents on Aquavisbreaking of Vacuum Residue.	
	Soyeon LEE - <i>Dankook university, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-196 Catalysis as Enabler for the Energy Transition	
	Doron LEVIN - <i>ExxonMobil Technology and Engineering Co., United States</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-197 Oxidative Ethane Dehydrogenation over B-Chabazite Catalysts	
	Raul LOBO - <i>University of Delaware, United States</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-198 Biodiesel preparation from non-conventional sources by two-step transesterification over La-Ni/MgAl mixed oxides	

T17	MON-POST01-199 Alkene coverage as descriptor for catalytic cracking pathway selection	
	Bo PENG - <i>SINOPEC Research Institute of Petroleum Processing Co., Ltd., China</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-200 Conversion of heavy gas oil into Ultra-Low-Sulfur Diesel over a NiWRu (Pd) /TiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst	
	Prada Silvy RICARDO - <i>Chasm Advanced Materials, United States</i>	
T17	MON-POST01-201 Pyrolysis waxes and their synergy with vacuum gas oil in hydrocracking reactions.	
	Suní RODRÍGUEZ - <i>University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, Spain</i>	
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	Jaime S. VALENTE - <i>Mexican Petroleum Institute, Mexico</i>	
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	Haoxuan TAN - <i>China University of Petroleum (East China), PR China, China</i>	
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	Le ZHANG - <i>Sinopec, Research Institute of Petroleum Processing (RIPP) Co., Ltd, China</i>	
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	Riccardo CONTI - <i>hte GmbH – the high throughput experimentation company, Germany</i>	
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	Lu CHENG - <i>Beijing chemical research institute, Sinopec, China</i>	
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	Leandro DE CASTRO - <i>Department of Chemical Engineering , University of the Philippines Los Baños, Philippines</i>	
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	Aissam ADDOU - <i>Chemical & Biochemical Sciences, Green process Engineering (CBS), Mohammed VI university, UM6P, Morocco - Université de Lille, CNRS, ENSCL, Centrale Lille, Univ. Artois, UMR 8181-UCCS-Unité de Catalyse et de Chimie du Solide, France</i>	
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	Jong Wook BAE - <i>Sungkyunkwan University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-343 Ni-doped CeO₂ with tetrahedral NiO as highly active catalyst for CO₂ methanation: insights into the catalytic active sites	
	Mathias BARREAU - <i>LCS, CNRS-Ensicaen-University of Caen Normandy, France, France</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-344 Enhanced electroreduction of CO₂ to acetic acid based on CuMgAl Layered Double Hydroxide electrocatalysts	
	Francesco BASILE - <i>University of Bologna, Italy</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-345 Zeolites synthesis using ionic liquids for CO₂ cycloaddition to epoxides	
	Katia BERNARDO-GUSMAO - <i>Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-346 Experimental and kinetics investigation for the CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol over structured foam catalysts	
	Aakash BHARDWAJ - <i>Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, New Delhi, India, India</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-347 Liquid-phase CO₂ hydrogenation via plasmon-mediated photocatalysis using Pt/Ag nanoparticles	
	Garv BHARDWAJ - <i>Monash University, Australia</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-348 CO₂ hydrogenation on carbon-supported iron catalysts under supercritical condition	
	Sergei CHERNIAK - <i>Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-349 Additive manufacturing of multichannel “zebra” hybrid catalysts for the one-pot hydrogenation of CO₂ into DME	
	Giuseppe BONURA - <i>CNR-ITAE, Italy</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-350 Influence of pre-treatment on the support effect in catalytic methanol synthesis	
	Jonas Abitz BOYSEN - <i>Technical University of Denmark, Denmark</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-351 What role does Al play in Cu/ZnO/Al catalysts when utilized for the hydrogenation of CO₂ into methanol?	
	Bruna BRONSATO - <i>Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil - National Institute of Technology, Brazil</i>	

T26	MON-POST01-352 Effect of Ni loading on the performance of Ni-Ca-Ce dual functional materials for integrated CO₂ capture and utilization	
	Lukas C. BUELENS - <i>Laboratory for Chemical Technology, Ghent University, Belgium</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-353 Structure-Activity Relationship of Cu/ZnO/Al₂O₃ Catalyst in CO₂ to CH₃OH: A Combined Experimental and Multiscale Modeling Approach	
	Balaji C DHARMALINGAM - <i>Indian Institute of Technology Madras, India</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-354 Effect of promoters on the activity of Co/Fe-ZSM-5 for the conversion of CO₂ to value added products.	
	Cele MDUDUZI - <i>North-West University, South Africa</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-355 Synthesis of liquid hydrocarbons through carbon dioxide hydrogenation combined with oligomerization	
	Jingyu CHEN - <i>Korea Research Institute of Chemical Technology, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-356 Structure-activity relationships in Ni/CeO₂ for CO₂ methanation	
	Sining CHEN - <i>University College London, United Kingdom</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-357 Selective Hydrogenation of CO₂ on Tandem Catalysts to Light Olefins	
	Siyu CHEN - <i>Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China - University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, China</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-358 Nature of Active Sites in CO₂ Hydrogenation-to-Methanol Catalysts	
	Aleix COMAS VIVES - <i>TU Wien, Austria - Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-359 Evolution upon storage of the activity-structure of MAPO-18 (Mg, Si) as catalyst for MTH and tandem CO₂ hydrogenation	
	Tomas CORDERO-LANZAC - <i>University of Oslo, Norway</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-360 Vanadium doped catalysts for CO₂ methanation	
	Giulia DA PIAN - <i>Università Ca' Foscari Venezia, Italy - INSTM, Italy</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-361 Ni-Ru/Hydrotalcite catalysts for CO₂ methanation reaction: Active species and reaction mechanism	
	Unai DE LA TORRE - <i>University of the Basque Country, Spain</i>	

T26	MON-POST01-362 Comparison of the effect of introducing Ga₂O₃ or Y₂O₃ on urchin-like hollow nanospheres as support for Ni WGS catalyts	
T26	MON-POST01-363 Synthesis of propylene carbonate using a heterogeneous catalyst based on Brönsted-Lewis acidic ionic liquid grafted on silica gel.	
	Heriberto DIAZ VELAZQUEZ - <i>Mexican Petroleum Institute, Mexico</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-364 Investigating the reaction mechanism of methanation catalyts with spatially resolved DRIFTS and gas phase analysis	
	Timo ENGL - <i>Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-365 Composition-activity relationship for Ni-Alkali/Alkaline earth metal unsupported catalyts in the CO₂-SR technology	
	Sofía ESSOUNANI-MÉRIDA - <i>University of Málaga, Spain</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-366 Ni-based aerogel and hydrotalcite like catalyts for CO₂ methanation.	
	Daniel ESTEVEZ CARO - <i>Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea/Universidad del País Vasco, UPV/EHU, Spain</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-367 Plasma assisted CO₂ conversion over a novel bio-based catalyst under severe conditions	
	Farbod FARZI - <i>Université de Sherbrooke, Canada</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-368 Enhancing Sustainable Syngas Production: Comprehensive Study on Operational Conditions in Oxidative Ethanol Dry Reforming	
	Fahim FAYAZ - <i>Circular Economy Innovation Research Group, Materials Science and Environmental Engineering, Faculty of Engineering and Natural Sciences, Tampere University, Finland, Finland</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-369 Water and Cu⁺ synergy in selective CO₂ hydrogenation to methanol over Cu/MgO catalyts	
	Estefanía FERNÁNDEZ-VILLANUEVA - <i>Instituto de Catálisis y Petroleoquímica (ICP-CSIC), Spain - Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-370 Pyrene-based porous organic polymers as potential catalyts in the photocatalytic CO₂ reduction	
	Beatriz FUERTE DIEZ - <i>ICMM-CSIC, Spain</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-371 Mechanistic insights into CO₂ hydrogenation over α-MoC surfaces	

T26	MON-POST01-372 Capsule-like zeolite catalyst fabricated by solvent-free strategy for para-Xylene formation from CO2 hydrogenation	
	Weizhe GAO - <i>University of Toyama, Japan</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-373 Sabatier's reaction catalysts: promoter and support roles in activity and selectivity	
	Gabriella GARBARINO - <i>INSTM, Italy - DICCA, University of Genova, Italy</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-374 CO2 hydrogenation by hydrogen transfer from isopropanol over Ni/CeO2 catalysts, can it be real?	
	Julieth GARCÍA-SÁNCHEZ - <i>Centro de Investigaciones en Catálisis, Universidad Industrial de Santander, Colombia</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-375 Conversion of CO2 in Chemicals: the recent progress of research considered from an industrial point of view	
	Elena GHEDINI - <i>Ca' Foscari University of Venice, Italy</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-376 Direct biogas methanation over HT-derived NiLaMgAl catalyst: Performance and mechanism above atmospheric pressure	
	Ilenia GIARNIERI - <i>University of Bologna, Italy</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-377 Effect of support on CO2 hydrogenation to methanol by Fe promoted Cu based catalyst	
	Angeliki LATSIU - <i>University of Western Macedonia, Greece - Delft University of Technology, Netherlands</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-378 Bimetallic Ni-Ru dual-function materials with low Ru loadings for the integrated capture and methanation of CO2	
	Angeliki LATSIU - <i>University of Western Macedonia, Greece</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-379 Optimizing NiO-exfoliated phyllosilicate catalysts for the CO2 methanation reaction	
	Sharad GUPTA - <i>UCEIV, France</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-380 Understanding the direct production of synthetic natural gas from CO2 and H2 based on a detailed kinetic reaction mechanism	
	Vivien GUENTHER - <i>LOGE Deutschland GmbH, Germany</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-381 CO2 methanation catalysts derived from Ni-alkaline earth metal carbonates	

T26	MON-POST01-382 In situ DRIFTS on CO2 hydrogenation to hydrocarbons over iron-based catalysts under high pressure conditions Kohei ISHIGAI - <i>Mitsui Mining & Smelting Co. Ltd., Japan</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-383 Mixed metal (Mn, Al, Ti) cobalt oxide model systems to optimize sustainable aviation fuel production via Fischer-Tropsch synthesis Cherie HSU - <i>Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-384 UiO-66 supported Cu catalysts for CO2 hydrogenation to methanol Zonggao HU - <i>Cardiff University, United Kingdom</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-385 Electrolysis of low-concentration gaseous CO2 using a gas diffusion electrode with macrocyclic cobalt complex Shoji IGUCHI - <i>Graduate School of Engineering, Kyoto University, Japan</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-386 Dual-site metal-amine catalysts for the CO2 and propylene oxide reaction Gustavo A. FUENTES - <i>Department of Process Engineering, Universidad A. Metropolitana - Iztapalapa, Mexico</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-387 Tuning the Active Phase of a CO2 Hydrogenation Co/TiO2 Catalyst with UV Light Matteo MONAI - <i>Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
T26	MON-POST01-388 Challenges in the catalyst-sorbent coupling in the sorption-enhanced methanol synthesis from CO2 Moioli EMANUELE - <i>Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-389 Catalytic effect of Ca and Na cations on biomass pyrolysis María Dolores ALCALÁ GONZÁLEZ - <i>Universidad de Sevilla, Spain</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-390 Esterification of crude tall oil with Beta Zeolite Cícero ÁVILA-NETO - <i>Federal University of Paraná, Brazil</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-391 Wheat bran biorefinery: extraction and catalytic conversion Alicia BOIX - <i>Research Institute of Catalysis and Petrochemistry. Universidad Nacional del Litoral (UNL), Argentina</i>	

T27	MON-POST01-392 Nanocomposites of TNT/ZSM-5 for galacturonic acid dehydration to furfural	
T27	MON-POST01-393 Dramatically recalcitrance reduction by cryo-milling in olive prune biomass; a pyrolysis kinetic and deconvolution modeling study	
	María Dolores ALCALÁ GONZÁLEZ - <i>Universidad de Sevilla, Facultad de Química, Dpto. Química Inorgánica, Spain</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-394 Functionalization of lignocellulosic biomass for the production of bio-binders	
	Nolwenn DARIDON - <i>CNRS, France</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-395 Fractionation and depolymerization of eucalyptus in lithium bromide solution with HZSM-5 and lignin valorization	
	Mateus FREITAS PAIVA - <i>Univ. Lille, CNRS, Centrale Lille, Univ. Artois, UMR 8181 – UCCS – Unité de Catalyse et Chimie du Solide, France</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-396 Development of Ni/SBA-15 catalysts with high low-temperature hydrogen production performance for glycerol steam reforming	
	Jingping HONG - <i>South-Central Minzu University, China</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-397 Biomass to Syngas: ML Optimization and Experimental Validation	
	Kaushik KUNDU - <i>CRE Lab, Chemical Engineering Department, IIT Delhi, India - CAPS Lab, Chemical Engineering Department, IIT Delhi, India</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-398 Comparative study on beet vinasse catalytic supercritical water gasification	
	Robin MOCHEL - <i>CEA, France</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-399 Raman study of the sulfur poisoning of multimetallic catalysts for the self-reforming of biogas	
	Sergio MOLINA-RAMÍREZ - <i>University of Malaga, Spain</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-400 Employing water in the feed as a tactic to mitigate deactivation in the synthesis of Bio-Butadiene from 1,3-butanediol	
	Cristina PADRO - <i>Instituto de Investigaciones en Catálisis y Petroquímica, Argentina</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-401 HDO of m-cresol over reduced LaNiO₃, LaCoO₃ and LaCo_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}O₃ perovskites	
	Gina PECCHI - <i>Universidad de Concepcion, Chile</i>	

T27	MON-POST01-402 Pyrolysis of solids wastes in used edible oils: An ATR study	
	Francisca ROMERO-SARRIA - <i>University of Seville, Spain</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-403 Zirconia-Catalyzed Hydrolysis of Amide Bonds in Peptides and Polyamides	
	Satoshi TOMITA - <i>Tohoku University, Japan</i>	
T27	MON-POST01-404 Functionalized lignin-plastic based catalysts for H2 production	
	Elisabetta BORSELLA - <i>Enea, Italy</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-406 How to enhance deoxygenation of phenolic compounds over non-noble metals-based catalysts? A study of Ni-Fe-based catalysts	
	Camila ABREU TELES - <i>Université de Poitiers, France</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-407 Towards the valorization of ABE mixtures with hydrotalcite derived catalysts	
	Leonardo ALMEIDA DE CAMPOS - <i>Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-408 Hydrodeoxygenation Reaction of Oleic Acid over Octahedral Metallic Nickel Supported on ZSM-5	
	Mohamad ALNARABIJI - <i>Centre for Sustainable Catalysis and Engineering (CSCE), KU Leuven, Belgium</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-409 Co-processing of castor oil with heavy fuel oil by catalytic hydrocracking	
	Felipe SANCHEZ MINERO - <i>Unidad de Caracterización y Evaluación de Hidrocarburos, ESIQIE-IPN, Mexico</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-410 Reductive etherification of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural over Ni-loaded zeolites for biofuel obtention	
	Leví ARRIECHE-HERNÁNDEZ - <i>Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Spain</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-411 Taking off with Furfural: The missing link in the production of high-performance bio jet fuel	
	Rick BALDENHOFER - <i>University of Twente, Netherlands</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-412 Synthesis of highly active and stable Cu nanoparticles encapsulated in mesoporous silica for hydrogenation of levulinic acid	
	Mihaela BECTORAS - <i>Unité de Chimie Environnementale et Intéractions sur le Vivant - UCEIV, Université du Littoral Côte d'Opale Dunkerque, 59140, France, France - "Gheorghe Asachi" Technical University of Iasi, 700050, Iasi, Romania, Romania</i>	

T28	MON-POST01-413 Tuning selectivity and stability of Ni/SBA-15 catalysts for HDO of m-cresol and anisole by controlling Ni particle size	
T28	MON-POST01-414 Hydrotreatment of anisole over Ptx/SBA-15 catalysts with different Pt loadings	
	Monica BETANCOURT ALDANA - <i>Facultad de Química, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-415 Tailoring metal-support interactions of (Pt,Fe)-supported catalysts towards selective C-O bond cleavage over acetone HDO	
	Guilherme B. STRAPASSON - <i>University of Campinas, Brazil - Brazilian Synchrotron Light Laboratory, Brazil</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-416 Hydrodeoxygenation of lignin model compounds over metal mixed oxides-supported Ru catalysts	
	Marcelo E. DOMINE - <i>Instituto de Tecnología Química (ITQ, UPV - CSIC), Spain</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-417 Do we really need Cu in Ni-Cu/aluminosilicate catalysts for hydrodeoxygenation?	
	Víctor BALDOVINO-MEDRANO - <i>Centro de Investigaciones en Catálisis, Universidad Industrial de Santander, Colombia - Laboratorio de Ciencia de Superficies, Universidad Industrial de Santander, Colombia</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-418 From cradle to grave : the HTL pathway for biofuels production from algae, role of catalytic upgrading	
	Christophe GEANTET - <i>CNRS, France</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-419 Step-out Route to Sustainable Aviation Fuels via Acetone Coupling to Branched C9 and C12 Products	
	Weronika GRUSZKA - <i>Johnson Matthey, United Kingdom</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-420 A surface science study of oxygen poisoning of MoS2 at hydrodeoxygenation-relevant conditions	
	Martin HEDEVANG - <i>Aarhus University, Denmark</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-421 Sustainable aviation fuel production through Fischer-Tropsch synthesis and hydrocracking integration using bifunctional catalysts	
	Mitra JAFARI - <i>Department of Process and Plant Technology, Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany</i>	

T28	MON-POST01-422 Multifunctional Pt/WO₃-ZrO₂ for Remarkably Efficient Hydrogenolysis of Esters to Alkanes?	
T28	MON-POST01-423 Hydrodeoxygenation of bio-oil to diesel range alkanes over zeolite-supported palladium catalysts	
	Ushna KHALID - <i>The University of Manchester, United Kingdom</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-424 Hydroprocessing characteristics of palm fatty acid distillate in palm oil into low-carbon biofuel	
	Hyerim KO - <i>Hanyang University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-425 Investigating Stabilization – A Model Compound Study of Catalytic Stabilization of Pyrolysis Bio-Oil	
	Amalie P. KREBS - <i>Technical University of Denmark, Denmark</i>	
T28	MON-POST01-426 Catalytic conversion of Lignin into Sustainable Aviation Fuels	
	Camille PELLEGRIN - <i>IRCELYON, UMR5256, France</i>	
T29	MON-POST01-429 Glycerol oxidation using Pt supported on a commercial HZSM-5	
	Mariana SOUZA - <i>Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-430 Selective Catalytic Hydrocracking of Post-Consumer Polystyrene Wastes Using Zeolite-Beta-supported Platinum Catalysts	
	Olajumoke ALABI-BABALOLA - <i>Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Manchester, United Kingdom</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-431 Catalytic Upcycling of Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE) Plastic Wastes using Nickel Tungstated Zirconia Catalysts	
	Vijayalakshmi THANGARAJ - <i>Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Manchester, Oxford Road Manchester, M13 9PL, United Kingdom</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-432 Open- and Closed-loop Recycling: Highly Active Zinc Bisguanidine Polymerization Catalyst for Depolymerization of Polyesters	
	Tabea BECKER - <i>Institute of Inorganic Chemistry RWTH Aachen University, Germany</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-433 Old tricks for new dogs: hydroprocessing of waste plastic oils	
	Ludo BOOT - <i>Ketjen Corporation, Netherlands</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-434 New cobalt catalysts for alkene hydrosilylation and crosslinking of silicones	
	Stanislas BOUYEYRON - <i>Laboratory of Catalysis, Polymerization, Processes and Materials, CP2M, CNRS, France - Elkem Silicones France, R&D Chemistry, R&I centre «</i>	

ATRiON », France

T30 **MON-POST01-435 | Open-loop Recycling of PLA to Value-added Products using Benign Guanidine Iron Catalysts**

Lisa BURKART - RWTH Aachen University, Institute for Inorganic Chemistry, Germany

T30 **MON-POST01-436 | Catalytic Pyrolysis of Waste Expanded Polystyrene using basic CaO, MgO, BaO and Hydrotalcite Mg/Al catalysts**

Israel PALA - Seccion de graduados ESIQIE- Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Mexico

T30 **MON-POST01-437 | Selective catalytic conversion of impurities in multilayered polymer films**

Steven CROSSLEY - University of Oklahoma, United States

T30 **MON-POST01-438 | Developing an in-situ DRIFTS Method to Study the Kinetics of Ethylene Polymerization by Metallocene-based Catalysts**

Albaraa FALODAH - Utrecht University, Netherlands

T30 **MON-POST01-439 | Green H₂ production by solar plastics photoreforming using unconventional photocatalysts**

Roberto FIORENZA - Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche, Università degli studi di Catania, Italy

T30 **MON-POST01-440 | Polypropylene Cracking Proceeding in Micropores of MFI Type Zeolite**

Tomohiro FUKUMASA - Center for Research on Green Sustainable Chemistry, Tottori University, Japan

T30 **MON-POST01-441 | Ni-Pd/CeO₂-Catalyzed Hydrogenolysis of C-O Bonds for Chemical Upcycling of Epoxy Resin**

Yanze HUANG - University of Tokyo, Japan

T30 **MON-POST01-442 | Combining thermo-catalytic pyrolysis and catalytic dry reforming for simultaneous abatement of plastic waste and CO₂**

Amer INAYAT - Institute of Environmental Technology, CEET, VSB-TU Ostrava, Czech Republic, Czechia

T30 **MON-POST01-443 | Catalytic cracking of low-density polyethylene using ZSM-5 zeolites prepared from Quang Ninh coal ash components**

Atsushi ISHIHARA - Mie University, Japan

T30 **MON-POST01-444 | Glycolysis of Plastic Waste Catalyzed by Zinc-based Catalyst from Spent Alkaline Batteries**

T30	MON-POST01-445 Production of naphtha from plastic waste via tandem reaction	
	Hyeongdong JUNG - <i>Seoul National University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-446 Low-temperature catalytic conversion of polyolefins over property-controlled zeolite beta in open batch reactor setup	
	Jong Hun KANG - <i>Seoul National University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-448 Catalytic Cracking of Polyethylene over USY and β-zeolites	
	Daeun KIM - <i>Dankook university, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-449 Coke deposition resistance in polyethylene cracking by Cr6+ loading on zeolite defects	
	Shinya KOKURYO - <i>Osaka University, Japan</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-450 Red mud and calcium oxide as waste catalysts for the polystyrene recycling by pyrolysis	
	Jean-Francois LAMONIER - <i>Université Lille - UCCS, France</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-451 The effect of calcination conditions on the catalytic performances of HZSM-5 zeolite in polyethylene pyrolysis	
	Jean-Francois LAMONIER - <i>Université Lille - UCCS, France</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-452 Production of High-Value Chemicals by Selective Hydrocracking of Polystyrene Pyrolysis Oils	
	Kyutae KIM - <i>Dong-A University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-453 Chemical Recycling of (Bio)Polyesters over solid Catalysts	
	Marcus S. LEHNERTZ - <i>ITMC RWTH Aachen, Germany</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-454 Gas Phase Copolymerization to In-Chain Functionalized Polyethylenes	
	Nina MAST - <i>Universität Konstanz, Germany</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-455 Antimony activity in PET chemical recycling	
	Adrien MEKKI-BERRADA - <i>IFP Energies Nouvelles, France</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-456 In-situ and ex-situ thermocatalytic pyrolysis of plastics: a comparison of two different approaches	

Catalysis-C3, Università di Bologna, viale del Risorgimento 4, 40136 Bologna, Italy, Italy

T30

MON-POST01-457 | Textile microfibers upcycling towards high tech carbonaceous materials.

Silvia PARRILLA - *School of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering University of Surrey, Guildford, GU2 7XH, United Kingdom*

T30

MON-POST01-458 | Metal-free catalysts, machine learning, and reactor optimization for polyethylene deconstruction below pyrolytic temperatures

Makenna PENNEL - *Department of Chemistry, Stanford University, United States*

T30

MON-POST01-459 | Premix Effect of Polyethylene on Catalytic Cracking over Zeolites

Jeonghwan SEO - *Dankook University, Korea, Korea (Republic of)*

T30

MON-POST01-460 | Reactivity and Catalyst Deactivation for Polyethylene Hydrogenolysis over Redox Neutral and Reducible Metal Oxide Supported Cobalt

Manish SHETTY - *Texas A&M University, United States*

T30

MON-POST01-461 | Combination of Carbon and Induction Heating Process for Low-Temperature One-Step Conversion of Plastic Waste to Light Olefins

Romain RIVIÈRE - *BOBINE, France*

T30

MON-POST01-462 | Organocatalysts for PET Depolymerisation: Process Scale Up and Kinetics

Joe SUTTON - *School of Chemical Engineering, University of Birmingham, United Kingdom*

T30

MON-POST01-463 | Transformation of olefinic plastics to valuable chemicals over heterogeneous Ru-based catalysts

Masazumi TAMURA - *Osaka Metropolitan University, Japan*

T30

MON-POST01-464 | Depolymerization of polyethylene terephthalate by dimethyl carbonate-aided methanolysis ?

Shinji TANAKA - *National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST), Japan*

T30

MON-POST01-465 | Catalytic upgrading of plastic wastes fast pyrolysis oils towards naphtha range hydrocarbons

Antigoni MARGELLOU - *Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Department of Chemistry, Greece*

T30	MON-POST01-466 Recover polyol monomer from polyurethane via solvent-free mechanocatalytic hydrolysis with heterogeneous catalysts	
	Bolun WANG - <i>Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Germany</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-467 Ce-promoted Pt-based catalysts for hydrocracking of polyolefin plastic waste into high yield of gasoline-range products	
	Haokun WANG - <i>Wolfson Catalysis Centre, Department of Chemistry, University of Oxford, United Kingdom</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-468 "Elemental Cycle" Concept Boosts Polyvinyl Chloride Waste upcycling	
	Yanqin WANG - <i>East China University of Science and Technology, China</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-469 Microwave Catalysis Technology Application in Plastic Upcycling	
	Yuxin WANG - <i>West Virginia University, United States</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-470 Development of recycling technology for multilayer plastic film	
	Aritomo YAMAGUCHI - <i>National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST), Japan</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-471 Oxidative degradation of polyethylene into oxygenates over transition metal supported catalysts	
	Chun-Jae YOO - <i>Korea Institute of Science and Technology, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-472 Non-recyclable plastics: Coupling deoxygenation and transfer hydrogenation reactions through trifunctional catalysts	
	Muxina KONAROVA - <i>University Queensland, Australia</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-473 Polyolefins upcycling: fine-tuning of a high-throughput reactor system for the polyolefin bifunctional hydrocracking conversion	
	J. FLOREZ - <i>IFP Energies Nouvelles, France</i>	
T30	MON-POST01-474 Raman investigations to understand LDPE decomposition by zeolites	
	Emma CAMPBELL - <i>Cardiff University, United Kingdom - UK Catalysis Hub, United Kingdom</i>	

16.07 17:30 - 19:30 | TUE-POST02 | Poster Session 2 Exhibition Hall

T4	TUE-POST02-1 Synthesis of Palladium-based nanoparticles with tuneable sizes for catalytic applications.	
T4	TUE-POST02-2 Shape selectivity for naphthalene ring methylation generated by chemical vapor deposition of silica on YFI type (YNU-5) zeolite	
	Ryota KATO - <i>Center for Research on GSC, Tottori University, Japan</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-3 Highly dispersed ADP derived CuO/CeO₂/Al₂O₃ mesoporous catalysts	
	Fotios KATSAROS - <i>Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, National Center for Scientific Research Demokritos, Greece</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-4 The impact of varying ball milling conditions on the perovskite structure and its performance in dry reforming of methane	
	Seulgi KIM - <i>Department of Environmental and Energy Engineering, Yonsei University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-5 Propane dehydrogenation reaction over Co-confined core-shell silicalite-1 zeolite	
	Shohei KUBOTA - <i>Osaka University, Japan</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-6 Tailoring bi- and trimetallic nanoparticles by exsolution from perovskites	
	Lorenz LINDENTHAL - <i>Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-7 Ni catalysts over Y-modified CeO₂ nanoparticles for CO₂ methanation: Y promotion effect	
	Leonarda LIOTTA - <i>CNR-Institute for the Study of Nanostructured Materials, Italy</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-8 Mesoporous titanosilicates magnetic core-shell catalysts for the oxidation of styrene	
	Ana LOZADA - <i>Escuela Politécnica Nacional, Ecuador - Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-9 Narrowing of SBA-1 pores through silylation for the encapsulation of a deoxydehydration precatalyst	
T4	TUE-POST02-10 High-Throughput Design of Heterogeneous Catalysts for The Valorisation of Polymers' Biodegradation Products	
	Richard MARTIN - <i>Univ. Lille, CNRS, Centrale Lille, Univ. Artois, UMR 8181 - UCCS - Unité de Catalyse et Chimie du Solide, France</i>	

T4	TUE-POST02-11 Development of multi-element-nanoalloy catalyst for hydrogen evolution reaction by machine learning	
	Yuto MARUTA - <i>Grad. Sch. Sci., Kyoto Univ., Japan</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-12 Synthesis strategy for maximizing the formation of aluminum pairs in ZSM-5 zeolites	
	Kinga MLEKODAJ - <i>J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Czechia</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-13 Facile Synthesis of Multi-Element Metal Sulfide Nanoparticles as Electrocatalysts	
	Megumi MUKOYOSHI - <i>Kyoto University, Japan</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-14 Elemental Effect on CO2 Hydrogenation Selectivity by High-Entropy Alloy Nanoparticles	
	Masashi NAKAMURA - <i>Grad. Sch. Sci., Kyoto Univ., Japan</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-15 Ultrasound contribution to cation substitution in LTA zeolite	
	Tony CHAVE - <i>ICSM, France</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-16 Tuning Reactive Microenvironment of Carbon-based Electrocatalysts by Selective and Rapid Heating	
	Takatoshi MURAKAMI - <i>Hokkaido University, Japan</i>	
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	Tzia Ming ONN - <i>University of Cambridge, United Kingdom</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-18 CO2 conversion over 3D printed Martian and Lunar regolith simulants for extraterrestrial applications	
	Arturo PAJARES - <i>Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO), Belgium</i>	
T4	TUE-POST02-19 Aerosol-sol gel method as a promising tool for the synthesis of nanostructured catalysts for bioethanol conversion	
	Giovanni PAMPARARO - <i>Université catholique de Louvain, Belgium</i>	
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	Yutong PI - <i>Inner Mongolia University, China</i>	

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	Muddasar SAFDAR - <i>LS- Prozess- und Anlagentechnik, BTU Cottbus- Senftenberg, Cottbus D-03044, Germany, Germany</i>	
T1	TUE-POST02-24 Olefin metathesis with ammonium-tagged Hoveyda-Grubbs type catalyst immobilized in l-carrageenan	
	Adi WOLFSON - <i>Chemical Engineering Department, Sami Shamoon Collage of Engineering, Israel</i>	
T5	TUE-POST02-26 Theoretical investigation of Keggin-type polyoxometalates in response to external stimuli	
	Hiromu AKIYAMA - <i>Waseda University, Japan</i>	
T5	TUE-POST02-27 DFT Modeling of Carbon Monoxide Oxidation on Pt/CeO₂ and Pt/Al₂O₃ catalytic systems	
	Hristiyan ALEKSANDROV - <i>University of Sofia, Bulgaria</i>	
T5	TUE-POST02-28 Insights into The Kinetic Influence of Metallic Ba and BaO on Co-Catalyzed Ammonia Decomposition Reaction	
	Zahra ALMISBAA - <i>University of California, Los Angeles, United States</i>	
T5	TUE-POST02-29 Theoretical study of the CO₂ reduction mechanism catalyzed by a NiFe complex on graphite	
	Subash ARJUNAN - <i>University of Grenoble Alpes, France - Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives (CEA), France</i>	
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	Jiachen CHEN - <i>Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany</i>	
T5	TUE-POST02-32 A new route of the first carbon-carbon bond formation in methanol to olefins: Beyond the methane-formaldehyde mechanism	
	Wei CHEN - <i>Ghent University, Belgium</i>	
T5	TUE-POST02-33 Effect of A-site composition of perovskite (Sr_{1-x}BaxZrO₃) oxides on H atom adsorption, migration, and ammonia synthesis	
	Kenshin CHISHIMA - <i>Waseda University, Japan</i>	

T5	TUE-POST02-34 Structure-dependent microkinetic analysis of carbon deposition during Methane Dry Reforming on Rh catalysts	
	Matteo MAESTRI - <i>Politecnico di Milano, Italy</i>	
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	Claude COPPEX - <i>Karlsruhe Institut für Technologie, Germany</i>	
T5	TUE-POST02-36 Modeling of transformation of fructose to carboxylic acids: comparison of mechanism using H2SO4 and Na-BEA	
	Izabela CZEKAJ - <i>Cracow University of Technology, Poland</i>	
T5	TUE-POST02-37 Mapping acid-base sites on anatase titania surface	
	Paige DENMAN - <i>St. John Fisher University, United States</i>	
T5	TUE-POST02-38 A method for rational design of Metal Organic Framework derived catalysts	
	Akshat TANKSALE - <i>Monash University, Australia</i>	
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	Annika ENSS - <i>Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Institute of Catalysis Research and Technology, Germany</i>	
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	Yi GAO - <i>Shanghai Advanced Research Institute, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China</i>	
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	Lars GRABOW - <i>William A. Brookshire Department of Chemical and Biomolecular Engineering and the Texas Center of Superconductivity (TcSUH) at the University of Houston, United States - Center for Programmable Energy Catalysis (CPEC), United States</i>	
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	Jaroslav HANDZLIK - <i>Cracow University of Technology, Poland</i>	
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	Paige DENMAN - <i>St. John Fisher University, United States</i>	

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	Jelena JELIC - Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany	
T5	TUE-POST02-45 Zirconium and Hafnium Doped Ceria Nanoparticles and the Effects of Doping on Their Reducibility: a DFT study	
	Iskra KOLEVA - Sofia University „St. Kliment Ohridski”, Faculty of Chemistry and Pharmacy, 1126 Sofia, Bulgaria, Bulgaria	
T5	TUE-POST02-46 Computational Insights into Magnetism-Enhanced Electrocatalysis: Unraveling the Mechanism of Oxygen Evolution Reaction	
	Lulu LI - Institut Català d'Investigació Química, Spain	
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	Raju LIPIN - University of Limerick, Ireland, Ireland	
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	Bin LIU - Kansas State University, United States	
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	Louai MAGHRABI - Department of Mechanical Engineering, Khalifa University of Science and Technology, United Arab Emirates - Center for Catalysis and Separations (CeCaS), Khalifa University of Science and Technology, United Arab Emirates	
T5	TUE-POST02-50 DFT based structure-activity relationships for alcohol dehydration catalyzed by gamma-alumina	
	Pierre MARMEY - IFP Energies nouvelles, France	
T5	TUE-POST02-51 DFT Calculations of Zirconia-Based Catalysts for Methanol Synthesis by CO₂ Hydrogenation	
	Tatsuya JOUTSUKA - Ibaraki University, Japan	
T6	TUE-POST02-51 An Accelerated Approach Towards Predicting Coverage-Dependent Surface Free Energies on Transition Metal Surfaces	
	Asmee M. PRABHU - Nanyang Technological University, Singapore	
T7	TUE-POST02-53 Dynamics of Cobalt-based Catalysts for Ammonia Synthesis using Machine-Learned Potentials	
	Marthe BIDEAULT - Materials Design SARL, France - Institut de Chimie Moléculaire et des Matériaux d'Orsay (Université Paris-Saclay), France	

T7	TUE-POST02-54 Effect of Aluminum distribution on the diffusion and pairing of [Cu(NH₃)₂]⁺ complexes in Cu-CHA	
T7	TUE-POST02-55 Machine learning potentials to model catalytic systems at the top of Jacob's ladder	
	Massimo BOCUS - <i>Center for Molecular Modeling, Ghent University, Belgium</i>	
T7	TUE-POST02-56 Designing Supported Metal Catalysts for CO₂ reduction using First Principles Methods and Machine Learning	
	Tej CHOKSI - <i>Nanyang Technological University, Singapore</i>	
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	Robert GEITNER - <i>Technical University Ilmenau, Germany</i>	
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	Yusof HAGHSHENAS - <i>School of Chemical Engineering, The University of New South Wales, Sydney, NSW 2052, Australia, Australia</i>	
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	Mitra JAFARI - <i>Department of Process and Plant Technology, Brandenburg University of Technology Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany</i>	
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	Adarsh KALIKADIEN - <i>Inorganic Systems Engineering, Department of Chemical Engineering, TU Delft, Van der Maasweg 9, Netherlands</i>	
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	Laura MOLINA NOGAL - <i>Instituto de Catálisis y Petroleoquímica, CSIC, Spain</i>	
T7	TUE-POST02-62 Fast Evaluation of the Adsorption Energy of Organic Molecules on Metals via Graph Neural Networks	
	Santiago MORANDI - <i>Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia (ICIQ), Spain - Universitat Rovira I Virgili (URV), Spain</i>	
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T7	TUE-POST02-64 Neural Network Potentials (NNP) for catalyst characterization
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T7	TUE-POST02-68 High-throughput screening of catalysts with elastic strains for the hydrogen economy through machine learning
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T8	TUE-POST02-73 Investigation of Pd, Pd-Zn and Pd-Cu-Supported ZSM-5 Zeolites for Methane Carboxylation
T8	TUE-POST02-74 On the real structure of technical ammonia synthesis catalysts
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T8	TUE-POST02-76 Highly Ga-exchanged zeolites as efficient and durable catalysts for ethane dehydrogenation: Speciation of active Ga species	
	Zen MAENO - <i>School of Advanced Engineering, Kogakuin University, Japan</i>	
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	Miriam MARCHI - <i>Dept. of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences and INSTM Trieste Research UNITS, University of Trieste, Italy</i>	
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	Vittorio MARSALA - <i>NISM, Department of Chemistry, Unit of Nanomaterials Chemistry, University of Namur, Belgium</i>	
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	Debora MEIRA - <i>Canadian Light Source, United States</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-80 Guidelines for good practice and reproducibility for in-situ spectroscopic characterization	
	Jordan MEYET - <i>Materials Research Institute - Penn State University, United States</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-81 Synergy effect of Cl and Pt on the Brønsted acidity of γ-Al₂O₃ supported platinum catalysts: role of edge site	
	Jordan MEYET - <i>IFP Energies nouvelles, France</i>	
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	Matteo MONAI - <i>Inorganic Chemistry and Catalysis, Institute for Sustainable and Circular Chemistry and Debye Institute for Nanomaterials Science, Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
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	Thomas MORAGUES - <i>Department of Chemistry and Applied Biosciences, ETH Zurich, Switzerland</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-85 Spectroscopic study for active sites of methane conversion reaction	
	Kengo NAKAMURA - <i>Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-86 Preparation of Supported Au Single-atom Catalysts Utilizing Layered Double Hydroxide (LDH) and Its CO-PROX Activity	
	Akihiro NAKAYAMA - <i>Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan</i>	

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	Abdallah NASSEREDDINE - <i>Institut Néel, Univ. Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, Grenoble INP, 38000 Grenoble, France, France</i>	
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	Gabriele CONTALDO - <i>Politecnico di Milano, Italy</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-90 Porous clay minerals catalysts for isopropanol dehydration to propylene: a comparative study on their characteristics and reactivity	
	Tien Hoang NGUYEN - <i>Institut de Recherches sur la Catalyse et l'Environnement de Lyon UMR 5256 CNRS/Universite Lyon 1, France</i>	
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	Tomohiro NOGUCHI - <i>Institute for Materials Chemistry and Engineering, Kyushu University, Japan</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-92 Manganese cobalt oxide catalysts for the preferential oxidation of carbon monoxide studied	<i>in situ</i>
	Thulani NYATHI - <i>University of Cape Town, South Africa</i>	
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	Ferensa OEMRY - <i>Research Center for Quantum Physics - BRIN, Indonesia</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-94 Oxygenates adsorption on alumina supported Ni/Cu catalysts	
	Katerina PACULTOVÁ - <i>VSB-TUO, CEET, IET, Czechia</i>	
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	Jessi E. S. VAN DER HOEVEN - <i>Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
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	Xingyu QI - <i>The University of Tokyo, Japan</i>	

T8	TUE-POST02-97 A multi-capillary reactor for high throughput in-situ catalysis experiments at Diamond Light Source, UK	
	Nitya RAMANAN - <i>Diamond Light Source, United Kingdom</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-98 Promoter effect of Zn on supported Cu catalysts for the butanol dehydrogenation reaction	
	Inmaculada RODRÍGUEZ-RAMOS - <i>Instituto de Catálisis y Petroleoquímica, CSIC, Spain</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-99 (Photo)thermocatalytic activity of Cu-doped SiO₂@TiO₂ and @TiO₂ core-shell structures in toluene combustion	
	Anna ROKICINSKA - <i>Jagiellonian University, Faculty of Chemistry, Poland</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-100 Low temperature propane oxidative dehydrogenation over Fe-ferrierite	
	Dorota RUTKOWSKA-ZBIK - <i>Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry PAS, Poland</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-101 Titanium and Zirconium-doped hollow silica nanospheres for the conversion of ethyl levulinate into γ-valerolactone	
	Martina SAITTA - <i>Unit of Nanomaterials Chemistry, Department of Chemistry, NISM, UNamur, 5000 Namur, Belgium, Belgium - IMCN Institute, MOST Division, UCLouvain, 1348 Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium, Belgium</i>	
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	Pranit SAMANTA - <i>Research Scholar, India</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-104 Characterization and structure-activity relationship of a SLP system for more sustainable gas phase hydroformylation of 1-butene	
	Anders RIISAGER - <i>Department of Chemistry, Technical University of Denmark, Denmark</i>	
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	Anke SCHOCH - <i>Paderborn University, Germany</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-106 Degradation of organic contaminants at mineral-water interfaces: A molecular approach using continuous-flow FTIR-ATR spectroscopy	
	Ana Carolina SCHUH FRANTZ - <i>Laboratoire de Réactivité de Surface (LRS, Sorbonne Université), France - Institut de Minéralogie, de Physique des Matériaux et de Cosmochimie (IMPMC, Sorbonne Université), France</i>	

T8	TUE-POST02-107 Visualising Sulphur Poisoning in Structured Honeycomb Catalysts with Hard X-ray Nanotomography	
	Leonardo ALMEIDA DE CAMPOS	
T8	TUE-POST02-108 LTA zeolites synthesized from different silicon sources for CO2 adsorption	
	Mariele SOARES DE MELLO - <i>LABPEMOL UFRN, Brazil</i>	
T8	TUE-POST02-109 FTIR and emission spectroscopy as a tool for the analysis of zinc speciation in zeolite matrices	
	Edyta TABOR - <i>J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry of the CAS, v. v. i., Czechia</i>	
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	Ye Ji KIM - <i>Sungkyunkwan University (SKKU), Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T12	TUE-POST02-113 Operando investigation of Pd/ZnO catalysts prepared by Cluster Beam Deposition Technology for CO2 hydrogenation to methanol	
	Imran ABBAS - <i>KU Leuven, Belgium</i>	
T12	TUE-POST02-114 On the tracks of surface dynamics of LaFeO3-based perovskites	
	Elise BERRIER - <i>Université de Lille, CNRS, Centrale Lille UMR CNRS 8181 UCCS - Unité de Catalyse et Chimie du Solide, France</i>	
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	Shuang CHEN - <i>Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany</i>	
T12	TUE-POST02-116 Unraveling the structure evolution and dynamic active sites of LaNiO3 for water oxidation	
	Haritha CHERAPARAMBIL - <i>Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Germany</i>	
T12	TUE-POST02-117 Carbon Surface Chemistry: Features of oxygen functionalities on carbon materials	
	Yuxiao DING - <i>Lanzhou Institute of Chemical Physics (LICP) of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), China</i>	
T12	TUE-POST02-118 Top Atomic Layer Analysis of Bimetallic Nanoparticles by Low-Energy Ion Scattering	
	Thomas GREHL - <i>IONTOF GmbH, Germany</i>	
T12	TUE-POST02-119 Surface hydroxylation of an ultrathin Co3O4(111) film grown on Ir(100): in situ NAP-XPS and DFT studies	

 Thomas HAUNOLD - *TU Wien, Austria*

T12 **TUE-POST02-120 | Binary oxide catalysts based on cobalt oxide thin films for reforming of alcohols**

 Viktor JOHÁNEK - *Charles University Prague, Czechia*

T12 **TUE-POST02-122 | Nature of the Reactive Oxygen Species in the Selective Methanol Partial Oxidation to Formaldehyde on Silver Catalysts**

 Emrah OZENSOY - *Bilkent University, Turkey*

T12 **TUE-POST02-123 | Pd and PdAu Laterally Condensed Catalysts – NAP-XPS/NEXAFS Study during Selective Acetylene Hydrogenation Reaction**

 Eylül ÖZTUNA - *Fritz Haber Institute of the Max Planck Society, Germany - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie, Germany*

T12 **TUE-POST02-124 | Ligand-Directed Heterogeneous Catalysis: When the Dynamically Changing Ligand Layer Controls the Hydrogenation Selectivity**

 Carsten SCHRÖDER - *CAU Kiel - Institut für physikalische Chemie, Germany*

T12 **TUE-POST02-125 | Protocol to Synthesis Highly Active and Selective Molecular Imprinting Catalyst for Nitroarene Hydrogenation**

 Feng SHI - *Lanzhou Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China*

T12 **TUE-POST02-126 | Isopropanol electro-oxidation on well-defined model Pt-Ru alloys: activity and composition**

 Alexander SIMANENKO - *Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany*

T12 **TUE-POST02-127 | Operando FT-IR/UV-vis-MS-GC investigation of ethylene conversion over Ag/H-ZSM-5 zeolites**

 Karolina TARACH - *Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland*

T12 **TUE-POST02-128 | Single- and Few-Layer MoS₂ as Efficient Hydrogen Evolution and Hydrogenation Catalysts**

 Shik Chi Edman TSANG - *University of Oxford, United Kingdom*

T12 **TUE-POST02-129 | Improving Harsh Environmental Stability of Few-Layer Black Phosphorus by Local Charge Transfer**

 Ning WANG - *Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

T12	TUE-POST02-130 Ethylene hydrogenation on HOPG supported and unsupported Ag, Au, and Cu model catalysts	
	Thomas WICHT - <i>TU Wien, Austria</i>	
T12	TUE-POST02-131 Adsorption and reactions of formic acid on ceria single-crystal and powder surfaces	
	Zairan YU - <i>karlsruhe institute of technology, Germany</i>	
T12	TUE-POST02-132 Hydroformylation of ethylene over Rh-based SILP catalysts: molecular interactions and speciation studied by in-situ IRAS and DFT	
	Kailun ZHANG - <i>Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany</i>	
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	Philipp Alexander HAUGG - <i>Kiel University, Germany</i>	
T11	TUE-POST02-134 Enhancing catalyst performance in methanation with the right reactors: examples across the scales	
	Moioli EMANUELE - <i>Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-136 Photothermal Synergistic Catalysis Oxidative Dehydrogenation of Propane over Defect-Rich Hexagonal Boron Nitride	
	Jingdong LIN - <i>Department of Chemistry, Xiamen University, China</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-137 Water-stable Nickel Metal-Organic Framework Nanobelts for Cocatalyst-free Photocatalytic Water Splitting to Produce Hydrogen	
	Lifang LIU - <i>Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-138 Insight into the reaction mechanism of photocatalytic production of solketal	
	Francisco LÓPEZ-TENLLADO - <i>University of Cordoba - Department of Organic Chemistry, Spain</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-139 Light-driven Methane Conversion to One-Carbon Oxygenates via Cocatalysts Engineering	
	Lei LUO - <i>Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-140 Tunable phase, morphology, and performance of Bismuth Oxyiodides Photocatalysts by different synthesis procedures	
	Andrea MARTINEZ-TOPETE - <i>Institute of Construction Science Eduardo Torroja, IETcc-CSIC, Madrid, Spain, Spain - Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM), Spain</i>	

T13	TUE-POST02-141 Simulating the Optical Properties of Bimetallic Plasmonic Catalysts to Enable Rational Design	
	Fergus MCLAREN - <i>Monash University, Australia</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-142 Comparative Study on the Photocatalytic Activity of SnO₂/CuO Heterojunctions under Natural and Simulated Sunlight	
	Simoni MENEGHETTI - <i>Federal University of Alagoas, Brazil</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-143 Compressive Analysis of Excited States in Photoactive Titania Nanostructures	
	Ángel MORALES - <i>University of Barcelona, Spain</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-144 Preparation of RGO-TaON composites for Z-schematic water splitting under visible light with a (CuGa)_{0.5}ZnS₂ H₂-photocatalyst	
	Misa MORIYA - <i>Meiji University, Japan</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-145 Deciphering Rapid Photocatalytic Decomposition of Ethanol: Uncovering Intermediates and Mechanisms with TiO₂-Embedded PVDF Membrane	
	Hadis MORTAZAVI MILANI - <i>LumiLab, Department of Solid State Sciences, Ghent University, 9000 Ghent, Belgium, Belgium</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-146 Improvement in Photocatalytic Activity of SrTiO₃ by Mg-doping for Selective Conversion of CO₂ to CO Using H₂O as an Electron Donor	
	Takechi NAKAMOTO - <i>Department of Molecular Engineering, Graduate School of Engineering, Kyoto University, Japan</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-147 Photocatalyst Sheets Employing Oxysulfide for Overall Water Splitting Under Atmospheric Pressure	
	Swarnava NANDY - <i>Shinshu University, Japan</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-148 Visible-Light Responsive Z-scheme Ti₃C₂ MXene/In₂S₃/CeO₂ Heterojunction for Enhanced Water Depollution	
	Jingbo NI - <i>Department of Chemistry and Bioscience, Aalborg University, Denmark</i>	
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	Patrick NIMAX - <i>Universidad del Pais Vasco, Spain</i>	
T13	TUE-POST02-150 Contribution of visible light to Reverse Water Gas Shift reaction over Cu/CeO₂	

T13	TUE-POST02-151 Operando FTIR investigation of the photocatalytic reduction of CO₂ in presence of water vapour over Pt/TiO₂ Céline PAGIS - <i>IFP Energies Nouvelles, France</i>
T13	TUE-POST02-152 Photo-chargeable inorganic membrane filter using application to As(III) oxidation in the dark Jiyeon PARK - <i>Kyungpook National University, Korea (Republic of)</i>
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T13	TUE-POST02-154 Doped LaFeO₃ materials as promising photocatalyst for sustainable NH₃ production Lorenzo RIZZATO - <i>University of Padova, Italy</i>
T13	TUE-POST02-155 ULTRASOUND SYNTHESIS OF A BI-BATIO₃ CATALYST AND ITS PHOTOCATALYTIC ACTIVITY ON THE DEGRADATION OF WATER POLLUTANTS Anel ROBLES-CORTES - <i>Unidad Profesional Interdisciplinaria en Ingenieria y Tecnologias Avanzadas- IPN, Mexico</i>
T13	TUE-POST02-156 SONOPHOTOCATALYTIC/PHOTOCATALYTIC PERFORMANCE OF BiFeO₃ NANOPARTICLES IN THE DEGRADATION OF A CARCINOGENIC DYE (RhB) . Anel I. ROBLES-CORTES - <i>Unidad Profesional Interdisciplinaria en Ingenieria y Tecnologias Avanzadas- IPN, Mexico</i>
T13	TUE-POST02-157 CO₂ activated g-C₃N₄ for enhanced photocatalytic activity Matevz ROSKARIC - <i>National Institute of Chemistry, Slovenia</i>
T13	TUE-POST02-158 Photoreduction of CO₂ to formic acid in a high pressure photoreactor Gianguido RAMIS - <i>Università degli Studi di Genova, Italy</i>
T13	TUE-POST02-159 Tuning the chemical composition and nanostructure of TiO₂ supported Mo oxysulfides for the gas-phase photoreduction of CO₂ Sébastien ROTH - <i>IFP Energies Nouvelles, France</i>
T13	TUE-POST02-160 Methane Oxidative Coupling on Au-TiO₂ Catalyst: DFT studies Dorota RUTKOWSKA-ZBIK - <i>Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry PAS, Poland</i>

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	Taichi SATO - <i>Meiji University, Japan</i>	
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	Jianying SHI - <i>Sun Yat-Sen University, China</i>	
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	Gloria I. SILLER-MONROY - <i>Instituto Politecnico Nacional, Mexico</i>	
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	Angel SOUSA - <i>KAUST, Saudi Arabia</i>	
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	Natsuki SUTO - <i>Department of Applied Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Tokyo University of Science, Japan</i>	
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	Shabnam TAGHIPOUR - <i>The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong - Department of Civil Engineering, Sharif University of Technology, Iran</i>	
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	Rosanna PAPARO - <i>Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Italy</i>	
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	Andre Luiz ALVARENGA MARINHO - <i>Institut de Chimie des Milieux et Matériaux de Poitiers (IC2MP), University of Poitiers, CNRS UMR 7285, France</i>	
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	Max BERKERS - <i>PCS group, Faculty of Science & Technology, University of Twente, Netherlands</i>	
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	Chih-Hao CHEN - <i>Department of Chemical Engineering, National Taiwan University, Taiwan</i>	
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	Mingyu CHEN - <i>ICBMS -Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France</i>	
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	Angela MARTINS - <i>DEQ, Instituto Superior de Engenharia de Lisboa, IPL, Portugal</i>	
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	Isabel VIDAL - <i>Department of Chemical Engineering - University Castilla La Mancha, Spain</i>	
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	Yiling DAI - <i>Tsinghua University, China</i>	
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	Charilaos DRAGOIDIS - <i>Polytechnic University of Madrid, Spain</i>	
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	Isabel VIDAL - <i>Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Chemical Sciences and Technologies, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain</i>	

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	Jesus GONZALEZ-COBOS - <i>CNRS, France</i>	
T14	TUE-POST02-182 Highly Dispersed Transition Metal Sulfides Supported on N- and S-Doped Mesoporous Carbon for Enhanced Electrocatalytic ORR	
	Patrick GUGGENBERGER - <i>Department of Functional Materials and Catalysis, University of Vienna, Austria - Vienna Doctoral School in Chemistry (DoSChem), University of Vienna, Austria</i>	
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	Badr ELKAMASH - <i>Technical University Berlin, Germany</i>	
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	Jeroen HOMAN - <i>TU Delft, Netherlands - Cellcentric GmbH & Co. KG, Germany</i>	
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	Eunseo JEON - <i>Dankook University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
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	Yuhei KOJIMA - <i>Tokyo institute of technology, Japan</i>	
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	Julia KOLODIAZHNAIA - <i>Aarhus University, Denmark</i>	
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	Tatsuya KOUYAYASHI - <i>Department of chemistry, Graduate of science, Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan</i>	
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	Gabriel ACOSTA - <i>INSA Rouen Normandie, Univ Rouen normandie, Normandie Université, LSPC UR4704, France</i>	
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	Zhiping LEI - <i>Anhui University of Technology, China</i>	

T14	TUE-POST02-191 Aminopolymer-modified hollow carbon spheres incorporating Ag nanoparticles for syngas electrosynthesis	
	Kaining LI - <i>Division of Materials and Manufacturing Science Graduate School of Engineering, Osaka University, Japan</i>	
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	Yongdan LI - <i>Aalto University, Finland</i>	
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	Zhan-Ku LI - <i>Anhui University of Technology, China</i>	
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	Zhan-Ku LI - <i>Anhui University of Technology, China</i>	
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	Mathilde LUNEAU - <i>Department of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden - Competence Centre for Catalysis, Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden</i>	
T14	TUE-POST02-196 Catalyst deactivation during electrocatalytic hydrogenation of phenol in acetate electrolyte	
	Yue MA - <i>Department of Chemistry and Catalysis Research Center, TUM School of Natural Sciences, Technical University of Munich, Germany</i>	
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	Clément MAHEU - <i>Institut des Matériaux de Nantes Jean Rouxel (IMN), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), Nantes Université, 44000, France - Department of Materials and Earth Sciences, Technische Universität Darmstadt, 64287, Germany</i>	
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	Rashid MEHMOOD - <i>State Key Laboratory of Catalysis, Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China</i>	

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	Matthew NEUROCK - <i>University of Minnesota, United States</i>	
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	Manon POULLY - <i>IFP Energies Nouvelles, France</i>	
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	Jun Tae SONG - <i>Department of Applied Chemistry, Kyushu University, Japan - International Institute for Carbon-Neutral Energy Research, Kyushu University, Japan</i>	
T14	TUE-POST02-204 Facile synthesis of N, P co-doped carbon as a metal-free catalyst for ORR	
	Ryuji TAKADA - <i>Osaka University, Japan</i>	
T14	TUE-POST02-205 Bi-Zr highly active electrocatalysts for CO2 reduction to formate	
	Yuta TAKAOKA - <i>Department of Applied Chemistry, Kyushu University, Japan</i>	
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	Miho YAMAUCHI - <i>Kyushu University, Japan - Tohoku University, Japan</i>	
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	Tao WU - <i>Dalian University of Technology, China</i>	
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	Sebastian AMAR GIL - <i>CNRS– Université de Poitiers, Institut de Chimie des Milieux et des Matériaux de Poitiers (IC2MP), France</i>	
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	Daniela ZANCHET - <i>Institute of Chemistry, University of Campinas, Brazil</i>	
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T19	TUE-POST02-212 Enhancing Alcohol Chain Growth: control over Pd and OH species within UiO-66 Metal-Organic Frameworks for Guerbet reaction.	
	Pedro CANTARERO - Department of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, 	
T19	TUE-POST02-213 Hydroxyl Group on Alumina to Strongly Bind Catalytically Active Species for Durability	
	Yunji CHOI - Korea Advanced Institute of Science & Technology (KAIST), Korea (Republic of) 	
T19	TUE-POST02-214 Soft-Templated Mg-Co Mixed Oxides for the Catalytic Transesterification of Propylene Carbonate to Dimethyl Carbonate	
	Maria Giorgia CUTRUFELLO - Chemical and Geological Sciences Department - Cagliari University, Italy	
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	Damien DEBECKER - University Louvain la Neuve, Belgium 	
T19	TUE-POST02-216 Role of phosphorus in highly active heterogeneous platinum catalysts for cycloalkane dehydrogenation	
	Patrick SCHÜHLE - Institute of Chemical Reaction Engineering, Friedrich-Alexander- Universität (FAU) Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany	
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	Joseph ESPOSITO - University of Minnesota Twin Cities, United States 	
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	Shoji FUKUDA - Department of Chemistry, Graduate School of Science, Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan	
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	Xin GAO - Syracuse University, United States - Xi'an Jiaotong University, China 	
T19	TUE-POST02-220 Exploring active sites and application potential of ZnOx/ZrO2-TiO2 catalysts for non-oxidative propane dehydrogenation	
	Shanlei HAN - China University of Petroleum, Beijing, China - Leibniz-Institut für Katalyse e. V, Germany	

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T19	TUE-POST02-231 A multi-defect engineering approach for developing SnO₂ catalysts for catalytic organic dehydrogenation	
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	Soyeon KIM - <i>Sookmyung Women's University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
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	Shuntaro KUNII - <i>Graduate School of Science, The University of Tokyo, Japan</i>	
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	Savitri LARASATI - <i>Tohoku University, Japan</i>	
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	Thomas LEN - <i>Departamento de Química Orgánica, Instituto de Química Fina y Nanoquímica, Universidad de Córdoba,, Spain</i>	
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	Zehua LI - <i>Fritz-Haber-Institut der Max-Planck-Gesellschaft, Germany</i>	
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T19	TUE-POST02-238 Activation of light alkanes on Cu surface at ambient conditions	
	Qi LU - <i>Tsinghua University, China</i>	
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	Bo-Qing XU - <i>Tsinghua University, China</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-241 Palladium Nanoparticles Supported on C₃N₄ for Efficient Hydrogen Storage System Based on Sodium Bicarbonate/Formate	
	Lidón ARROYAS - <i>Institute of Advanced Materials (INAM), Spain</i>	

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T22	TUE-POST02-243 Influence of medium acid sites and pressure on 1,4-butandiol dehydrogenation over copper-based catalysts in the LOHC context	
	François BIHL - <i>ICPEES, France</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-244 Application of a laboratory-based EXAFS spectrometer to <i>in situ</i> NH₃ decomposition studies on 3 transition metal-based catalysts	
	John Carl CAMAYANG - <i>Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Germany</i>	
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	Santiago CASU - <i>Heraeus Precious Metals GmbH & Co. KG, Germany</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-246 Three-phase trickle bed reactors modeling for different LOHC dehydrogenation (H12-BT and BDO)	
	Alban CHAPPAZ - <i>CEA-Liten, France</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-247 Elementary Steps and Bifunctional Scavenging Pathways in Methylcyclohexane Dehydrogenation on Dispersed Pt Nanoparticles	
	Sai CHEN - <i>Tianjin University, China</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-248 Catalyst Synthesis via Strong-Electrostatic Adsorption (SEA) for Enhanced MCH Dehydrogenation: Impact of Calcination Temperatures	
	Chi Cheng CHONG - <i>School of Chemical, Chemical Engineering and Biotechnology, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore</i>	
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	Ezgi DEMIRÖZ - <i>Delft University of Technology, Netherlands</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-250 Ammonia Decomposition Performed at Moderate Temperature from Mixed Non-Noble/Noble Metal Catalytic Interfaces	
	Justine DORIVAL - <i>CEA, France - ENSL, France</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-251 Parametric Study of Ru-CeO₂ Catalysts for Ammonia Decomposition prepared by Mechanochemical Synthesis	
	Andrea FELLI - <i>University of Udine, Italy</i>	

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	PoI FERNANDEZ REIXACH - <i>KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden</i>	
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	Yong GUO - <i>East China University of Science & Technology, China</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-254 Direct enthalpy measurement for hydrogenation of LOHCs by Differential Scanning Calorimetry under H₂ pressure	
	Parviz HAJIYEV - <i>University Grenoble Alpes, CEA, LITEN, LVME, France</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-255 Shaped Inorganic-Organic Hybrid Catalyst Materials Based on Highly Crosslinked Porous Polymers for Formic Acid Dehydrogenation	
	Peter HAUSOUL - <i>ITMC, RWTH Aachen, Germany</i>	
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	Nick HERRMANN - <i>Universität Hamburg, Germany</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-257 Ammonia decomposition over high-surface-area Ni/Rare-earth oxide catalyst	
	Haruki ISHIDA - <i>Department of Energy & Hydrocarbon Chemistry, Graduate School of Engineering, Kyoto University, Japan</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-258 Comparison of Catalyst Performances for Transfer Hydrogenation between LOHC and Acetone: Activity and Kinetic Study	
	Xiaolong JI - <i>IRCELYON - CNRS - Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France - LAGEPP - CNRS - Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-259 Hydrogen storage in dibenzyltoluene via catalytic hydrogenation: in-depth compound analysis and kinetic study	
	Xiaolong JI - <i>IRCELYON - CNRS - Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France - LAGEPP - CNRS - Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-260 Optimizing sulfur doped PtMo/Al₂O₃ catalysts for perhydrobenzyltoluene dehydrogenation.	
	Alconada KEVIN - <i>UPV/EHU, Spain</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-261 Catalytic Ammonia Cracking and Its Integrated Process for Large-Scale Carbon-Free Hydrogen Production	
	Beom-Sik KIM - <i>POSCO Holdings, Korea (Republic of)</i>	

T22	TUE-POST02-262 Hydrogenation of aromatic LOHC over Ru/CeO₂ with heterolytic H₂ adsorption and H₂ spillover	
	Dongun KIM - <i>Hanyang University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
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	Byung Sun YOON - <i>Chonnam National University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T22	TUE-POST02-264 Advanced NH₃ cracking catalysts with outstanding low temperature activity and durability	
	Arnaud LAHOUGUE - <i>Enercat - Alsys Group, France</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-267 Low-carbon Hydrogen Production Via Oxidant-Assisted Methane Pyrolysis	
	Henry MOÏSE - <i>Stanford University, United States</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-268 H₂ production from H₂O by vibro-catalytic system using low-frequency vibration	
	Yuto OBA - <i>Department of Chemistry, Graduate School of Science, Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-269 Synergistic Role of Carbon Defects and Nitrogen Dopants for Electrochemical Oxygen Reduction Reaction	
	Takatoshi MURAKAMI - <i>Hokkaido University, Japan</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-270 Photocatalytic H₂ production over MoxC/g-C₃N₄ nanocomposites governed by MoxC characteristics	
	Narcis HOMS - <i>Universitat de Barcelona, Spain - IREC, Spain</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-271 Tailoring the properties of nickel, aluminum and magnesium catalysts for biohydrogen production	
	Maria Do Carmo RANGEL - <i>Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil - Universidade Federal da Bahia, Brazil</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-272 Nanostructured thin films of CeO₂ as a catalyst in the electrolysis process.	
	Gabriela Mariela REYES CHAPARRO - <i>UPIITA - IPN, Mexico</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-273 Experimental and computational study of methane steam reforming on a Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst	
	Jana RICHTER - <i>LOGE Deutschland GmbH, Germany</i>	

T23	TUE-POST02-274 Production of hydrogen by ethanol steam reforming using Ni-Co/Ex HDT-WOx	
T23	TUE-POST02-275 Hydrogen production by glycerol steam reforming using the catalysts Ni, Co and Ni-Co/Ex HDT-WOx.	
	Pala Rosas ISRAEL - <i>Instituto Politecnico Nacional, Mexico</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-276 On the mechanism of Preferential Oxidation of Carbon Monoxide on CuO/CeO2 catalyst	
	Mirko SCANFERLA - <i>University of Padova, Italy</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-277 Hydrogen production by steam reforming of acetone-butanol-ethanol over supported nickel catalysts	
	Mariana SOUZA - <i>Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-278 Steam reforming of ethanol to hydrogen on Co-Ce-O catalysts	
	Tahmina TAGHI - <i>French-Azerbaijani University at Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Azerbaijan</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-279 Boosting Photocatalytic Activity in Gas Phase Water Splitting by External Electric Field using Solid Contact Cell	
	My Nghe TRAN - <i>1 Univ. Lille, CNRS, Centrale Lille, Univ. Artois, UMR 8181 – UCCS – Unité de Catalyse et Chimie du Solide, France - Univ. Lille, CNRS, Centrale Lille, Univ. Polytechnique Hauts-de-France, Junia-ISEN, UMR 8520 - IEMN, France</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-280 Main chain engineering of polymer photocatalysts with sulfide oxidation-tuning segments for photocatalytic hydrogen evolution	
	Huang TSE-FU - <i>Department of Chemical Engineering, National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-281 Dry Reforming of Methane over Ce-, La-modified Ni-Al catalysts	
	Svetlana TUNGATAROVA - <i>D.V. Sokolsky Institute of Fuel, Catalysis and Electrochemistry, Kazakhstan - Chemistry and Chemical Technology Faculty, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Kazakhstan</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-282 Green Hydrogen Production by Sorption Enhanced Gasification Combined with Sorption Enhanced Reforming	
	Umberto PASQUAL LAVERDURA - <i>Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA), Italy</i>	
T23	TUE-POST02-283 Recoverable Highly-dispersed Ni Supported on LaTiO3 perovskite for Dry Reforming of Methane	

 Zhaoyue WENG - *University College London, United Kingdom*

T23 **TUE-POST02-284 | Atomically doped Ni catalysts for alkaline water electrolysis**

 Tingting YAO - *State Key Laboratory of Catalysis, Dalian Institute of Chemical and Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China - University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, China*

T23 **TUE-POST02-285 | Molecular and Heterojunction Engineering of Solution-Processed Conjugated Reticular Oligomer for Photoelectrochemical Devices**

 Boying ZHANG - *University of Johannesburg, South Africa*

T24 **TUE-POST02-288 | Mechanistic insights into acetonitrile synthesis on molybdenum nitride based on experimental and computational analyses**

 Ali Can KIZILKAYA - *Izmir Institute of Technology, Turkey*

T24 **TUE-POST02-289 | Spatial Resolution of the low-temperature Standard NH₃-SCR reaction on a Cu-CHA monolith catalyst**

 Enrico TRONCONI - *Politecnico di Milano, Italy*

T24 **TUE-POST02-290 | Polymer Modified Ru Nanoparticles Boost Electroreduction Nitrate to Ammonia in Water-fed PEM Cell**

 Min LI - *Delft University of Technology, Netherlands*

T24 **TUE-POST02-291 | NO SCR by propene and ethanol over Ag/CeMnO_x catalysts: investigation of powder and structured monolithic samples**

 Leonarda LIOTTA - *CNR-Institute for the Study of Nanostructured Materials, Italy*

T24 **TUE-POST02-292 | Development of ammonia synthesis technologies for sustainable society**

 Yuichi MANAKA - *National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology, Japan - Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan*

T24 **TUE-POST02-293 | Three-way catalysis performance and deactivation of Pd-Cu composite catalysts**

 Zannatul Mumtarin MOUSHUMY - *Kumamoto University, Japan*

T24 **TUE-POST02-294 | Consequence of in situ adsorption for ammonia synthesis at low temperatures**

 William MOVICK - *The University of Tokyo, Japan*

T24 **TUE-POST02-295 | The role of W in V-based catalysts for NH₃-SCR between the "crowding" or electronic effect**

 Chiara NANNUZZI - *University of Turin, Italy*

T24	TUE-POST02-296 Selective catalytic reduction of N2O by NH3 in the presence of NO	
	Masaru OGURA - <i>The University of Tokyo, Japan</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-297 The Influence of Oxygen Concentration on NOx Desorption Temperature from Pd-CHA	
	Takeshi OHTSU - <i>NAGOYA University, Japan</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-298 Lab-Scale Evaluation of Functional Materials for Ammonia Production from Steel Industry Residual Gases	
	Santiago PALENCIA RUIZ - <i>Johnson Matthey, United Kingdom</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-299 Electrocatalytic Conversion of Dilute NO Gas to Ammonium Nitrate	
	Wonyong CHOI - <i>PhD student, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-300 Impact of gas treatment of CuAl-LDH on NO reduction by CO under oxidative conditions	
	Christophe POUPIN - <i>Université du Littoral Côte d'Opale - UCEIV, France</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-301 Experimental and modelling investigation of the high temperature mechanism of NH3-SCR over Cu-CHA catalyst	
	Enrico TRONCONI - <i>Politecnico di Milano, Italy</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-302 Addressing reproducibility challenges in catalytic testing studies on ammonia decomposition	
	Simon RISTIG - <i>Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Germany</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-303 Conceptual design of a process for the use of liquid ammonia as hydrogen vector	
	Ilenia ROSSETTI - <i>Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-304 Development of oxyhydrides by mechanochemical method and its application for ammonia synthesis catalysts	
	Shun SATO - <i>MDX Research Center for Element Strategy, International Research Frontiers Initiative, Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-305 Novel NOx-storage-reduction process with an electric field under lean burn conditions	
	Ayaka SHIGEMOTO - <i>Waseda University, Japan</i>	

T24	TUE-POST02-306 Activity of CuCoCe-LDH catalysts for SCR of NO with C3H6	
	Yaxin SU - <i>Donghua University, CN, China</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-307 Iron active centres in FER and MOR for N2O processing: in situ UV-vis DRS and operando FTIR study	
	Edyta TABOR - <i>J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry of the CAS, v. v. i., Czechia</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-308 SAR and H2O effects on Reduction and Oxidation half cycles of Std SCR over Cu-CHA catalysts: an experimental and modeling analysis	
	Roberta VILLAMAINA - <i>Johnson Matthey Technology Centre, United Kingdom</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-309 Selective catalytic oxidation of ammonia at room temperatures over Ag/MnO2 catalysts	
	Haifeng WANG - <i>Graduate School of Urban Environmental Sciences, Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan</i>	
T24	TUE-POST02-310 Effect of Doping on Ammonia Synthesis Activity of Co3Mo3N	
	Rachel YOUNG - <i>University of Glasgow, United Kingdom</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-313 Highly stable and coke resistant LaNi-Zn perovskite-type oxide for dry reforming of methane	
	Juliana BERTOLDI - <i>University of São Paulo, Brazil</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-314 Critical Importance of High Pressure and High Selectivity for a Successful Oxidative Coupling of Methane (OCM) Process	
	Madan BHASIN - <i>Innovative Catalytic Solutions, United States</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-315 Heterogeneous Transition Metal Catalysts & Effective Reaction Concepts for High-Yield Methane Partial Oxidation to Stable Products	
	Andrea BLANKENSHIP - <i>Institute for Chemical and Bioengineering, ETH Zurich, Switzerland</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-316 In-situ encapsulation of ultrasmall metal (Ni, Pt, Ru) nanoparticles within silicalite-1 for reforming of methane with H2S	
	Xiaomai CHEN - <i>School of Natural Sciences, Technical University of Munich, Germany</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-318 Combined dry reforming intensified over Ni and Ni-Co ceramic open cell foam catalysts	
	Andoni CHOYA - <i>Department of Chemical Engineering, University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, Spain</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-319 Nickel-lanthanum catalysts for methane dry reforming: insights into structure-activity relationship and coke poisoning resistance	

T25	TUE-POST02-320 Intimacy study in the Ox-Zeo process: the limits of the intimacy descriptors	
	Christophe COUDERCY - <i>Univ. Lyon, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, CNRS, IRCELYON, France</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-321 Direct catalytic conversion of methane at low temperature	
	Xiaoju CUI - <i>Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-322 Enhancing higher alcohol formation over prussian blue analogue-derived cobalt-based catalysts	
	Patrick DIEHL - <i>Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry, Ruhr University Bochum, Germany</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-323 Synthesis of Co-Ni@SiO₂ Yolk-Shell Catalyst and Optimization of Irradiation Conditions for Photothermal Dry Reforming of Methane	
	Hamada EL-NAGGAR - <i>Kyoto University, Japan</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-324 The conversion of dimethyl ether to C₃ and C₄ paraffins over Pd/BEA	
	Candace ESLICK - <i>Catalysis Institute, University of Cape Town, South Africa</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-325 Nanosized LEV Zeolite Promotes Ethylene Yield in the Methanol-to-Olefin Reaction	
	Chuanming WANG - <i>SINOPEC Shanghai Research Institute of Petrochemical Technology Co., Ltd., China</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-327 Operando 2D COS UV-Vis-NIR-IR techniques for molecular oxygen splitting and selective methane oxidation on Fe-MOR zeolites	
	Kinga GÓRA-MAREK - <i>Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-328 Ni-based catalyst for partial oxidation of methane (POM)	
	Morvan GUILLON - <i>ICPEES - CNRS, France</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-329 Anode materials for the oxidative coupling of methane (OCM)	
	Morvan GUILLON - <i>ICPEES - CNRS, France</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-330 Optimization of Metal Amount of Ni-Co-Al₂O₃ Catalyst for the Flue-gas Reforming of Methane	
	Saumya TIWARI - <i>Indian Institute of Technology Kanpur (IITK), India</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-331 Application of La-Ni oxide catalysts for microwave-assisted Dry Reforming of Methane	

T25	TUE-POST02-332 Rational Design of MoS₂-Based Catalysts for Highly Efficient CO_x Conversion	
T25	TUE-POST02-333 Optimization of Sequential CO₂/CH₄ Reaction for the Oxygenated Products Synthesis	
T25	TUE-POST02-334 Ba_xNiO₃ and La_xNiO₃ perovskites as catalysts for Dry Reforming of Methane reaction	
T25	TUE-POST02-335 Exploring perovskite as catalysts for sustainable hydrogen production via Dry Reforming of Methane	
T25	TUE-POST02-336 Reforming of methane over Fe-Co based alumina supported catalysts	
T25	TUE-POST02-337 Selective production of kerosene by Fischer-Tropsch synthesis over sol-gel made Co-based catalysts modified by Ce and Zr oxides	
T25	TUE-POST02-338 Low-temperature methane direct conversion into oxygenated hydrocarbons by purely heterogeneous catalysis	
T25	TUE-POST02-339 Hydrogen Production via Chemical Looping Methane Reforming (CL-MR) Using Perovskites as Oxygen Carriers	
T25	TUE-POST02-340 Conversion of Paraffinic Hydrocarbons to Oxygenated Compounds through CO₂-consuming Pathway	

T25	TUE-POST02-341 Highly selective transformation of methanol into ethylene in the presence of syngas by relay catalysis	
	Jincan KANG - <i>Xiamen University, China</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-342 Regeneration of nickel-based catalysts without reduction due to low nickel loading applied for CO₂ reforming of methane	
	Yeon Jeong YU - <i>Chonnam National University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-343 Methane aromatization using molybdenum supported zeolite catalyst	
	Anil Chandra KOTHARI - <i>CSIR-INDIAN INSTITUTE OF PETROLEUM, DEHRADUN, UTTARAKHAND, INDIA, India - Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Ghaziabad, 201002, India., India</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-344 Ru-Ni catalysts over LaMnO₃ for H₂ production via temperature programmed reaction with CH₄	
	Eleonora LA GRECA - <i>Institute for the Study of Nanostructured Materials (ISMN), National Research Council (CNR), Italy</i>	
T25	TUE-POST02-345 Effect of Cu-CHA Composition on Catalytic Activity for Direct Oxidation of Methane to Methanol and Active-Site Structure	
	Junya OHYAMA - <i>Kumamoto University, Japan</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-348 Low-temperature CO₂ methanation over Ni-based catalysts: on the nature of active sites by operando DRIFTS study	
	Gabriel MARINO - <i>National Research Council of Italy (CNR-ITAE), Italy</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-349 Enhancing CO₂ Electroreduction Selectivity by Catalyst Development and Electrode Fabrication Parameters Control	
	Kazuyuki IWASE - <i>Institute of Multidisciplinary Research for Advanced Materials, Tohoku University, Japan</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-350 CO₂ Hydrogenation over Rhodium Cluster Catalysts Nucleated within a Manganese Oxide Framework	
	Juan D. JIMENEZ - <i>Chemistry Division, Brookhaven National Laboratory, United States</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-351 CO₂ conversion to formic acid over Cu-Zn metal-organic framework-derived catalysts	
	Jyotishman KAISHYOP - <i>CSIR-Indian Institute of Petroleum, Dehradun, India, India - Academy of Scientific & Innovative Research, India</i>	

T26	TUE-POST02-352 Low-temperature CO₂ conversion on doped gallium oxides by chemical looping	
	Keke KANG - <i>Waseda University, Japan</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-353 Structure-sensitive Reactivity of CO₂ Hydrogenation Intermediates on Supported Ni Catalysts Probed by In-situ IR Spectroscopy	
	Bram KAPPÉ - <i>Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-354 Sorbent-Catalyst Interactions in a Dual Functional Material for the Direct Air Capture and Conversion of CO₂	
	Freek KARAÇOBAN - <i>Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-355 N-formylation reaction using CO₂ as a carbon source over surface-modified supported Pt NPs with basic metal oxide clusters	
	Soichi KIKKAWA - <i>Tokyo Metropolitan University, Japan</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-356 Robust Ni self-catalytic reactor for CO₂ methanation designed by metal 3D printing with selective electrochemical dissolution	
	Hyo-Jin KIM - <i>Osaka University, Japan</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-357 The Impact of Hydrogen Spillover by Adjusting the Spatial Distribution of Catalytic Components in FeK/CuAl₂O₄ in CO₂ Hydrogenation	
	Yongseok KIM - <i>Department of Chemistry, Chonnam National University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-358 Continuous CO₂ capture and hydrogenation into methanol under unsteady state operations	
	Fumihiko KOSAKA - <i>National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST), Japan</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-359 Role of Ca in Ni-Ca/fumed-SiO₂ Catalyst for CO₂ Catalytic Conversion to Carbon Monoxide and Methane	
	Anand KUMAR - <i>Qatar University, Qatar</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-360 CO₂-mediated oxidative dehydrogenation of n-butane into buta-1,3-diene on Ni-Bi-Mo/Al₂O₃ oxide catalysts	
	Oksana ZIKRATA - <i>L. V. Pisarzhevskii Institute of Physical Chemistry of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Ukraine</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-361 Tuning CO₂ hydrogenation selectivity through the modulation of Ru-based catalyst chemical architecture	
	Karolina LEDWA - <i>1Institute of Low Temperature and Structure Research of Polish Academy of Sciences, 50-422 Wrocław, Poland, Poland</i>	

T26	TUE-POST02-362 Critical effect of the titania phase on the CO₂ hydrogenation performance of Mo/TiO₂ catalysts: an operando study	
	Thomas LEN - <i>IRCELYON, CNRS & Université Lyon 1, Villeurbanne, France, France</i> -	
T26	TUE-POST02-363 From Waste to Fuel: Metal-free Carbon Nanodots for Selective CO₂ Photoreduction into Methanol	
	Thomas LEN - <i>Departamento de Química Orgánica, Instituto de Química Fina y Nanoquímica, Universidad de Córdoba,, Spain</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-365 Operando IR studies on nickel-sepiolite-based catalysts for the CO₂ methanation reaction	
	Raul Bruno MACHADO-SILVA - <i>Instituto de Tecnología Química - CSIC, Spain</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-366 CO₂ reduction to platform chemicals over molybdenum carbide catalysts	
	Wijnand MARQUART - <i>University of Cape Town, South Africa</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-367 Optimizing stability and selectivity of Ni/CeZrO₂ catalyst in CO₂ methanation reaction	
	Jose Antonio DE LOS REYES HEREDIA - <i>Universidad autónoma Metropolitana, Mexico</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-368 Earth abundant catalysts for the photoreduction of CO₂	
	Anna M. MASDEU-BULTO - <i>University Rovira i Virgili, Spain</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-369 Characterization of modified ZSM-5 materials for selective hydrogenation to olefins	
	Amanda MBHELE - <i>University of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-370 Cu-Ce binary oxide catalysts for CO₂ hydrogenation into methanol: operando FT-IR spectroscopy and kinetic study	
	Marco Pietro MEZZAPESA - <i>Politecnico di Torino, Italy</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-371 Catalytic Synthesis of Organic Urea Derivatives from Alkanolamine-Derived Alkylcarbamic Acids over Cerium Oxide	
	Shogen MIHARA - <i>Tohoku University, Japan</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-372 Polymeric networks based on POSS-porphyrin-imidazolium systems as catalytic bifunctional platforms for the conversion of CO₂.	
	Anthony MORENA - <i>Unit of Nanomaterials Chemistry, Department of Chemistry, NISM, University of Namur, 61 rue de Bruxelles, 5000 Namur, Belgium, Belgium</i> -	

of Biological, Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technologies, University of Palermo, Viale delle Scienze, Ed. 17, 90128, Palermo, Italy, Italy

T26

TUE-POST02-373 | CO₂ hydrogenation to hydrocarbons using Na-Fe₃O₄/Fe₅C₂ catalyst

Sara NAJARI - *Interdisciplinary Excellence Centre, Department of Applied and Environmental Chemistry, University of Szeged, Rerrich Béla tér 1, H-6720, Hungary*

T26

TUE-POST02-374 | Reverse water gas shift reaction through the Mars-van Krevelen mechanism promoted by Pd co-catalysis

Shimpei NANIWA - *Department of Molecular Engineering, Graduate School of Engineering, Kyoto University, Japan*

T26

TUE-POST02-375 | Mo₂C catalyst screening for the intensification of the reverse water-gas shift reaction

Lindokuhle NGEMA - *University of Cape Town, South Africa*

T26

TUE-POST02-376 | Selectivity Engineering in CO₂ Valorization over Metal Nanostructures

Jyotsna PALIWAL BAJPAI - *Catalysis and Inorganic Chemistry Division, CSIR-National Chemical Laboratory, India*

T26

TUE-POST02-377 | Study of the synthesis of hydrocarbons from biomass-derived syngas and renewable hydrogen over Fe-based catalysts (PBtX).

Carlotta PANZONE - *Univ Grenoble Alpes, CEA, LITEN, DTCH, Laboratoire Réacteurs et Procédés (LRP), F-38000 Grenoble, France, France*

T26

TUE-POST02-378 | Effect of zeolite acidity in the direct conversion of CO₂/CO into gasoline

Onintze PARRA - *Department of Chemical Engineering, University of the Basque Country, Spain*

T26

TUE-POST02-379 | High C₂-C₄ selectivity in CO₂ hydrogenation by particle size control of Co-Fe alloy NPS wrapped on N-doped graphitic carbon

Vasile PARVULESCU - *University of Bucharest, Romania*

T26

TUE-POST02-381 | CO₂ hydrogenation over P-modified Ni-based catalysts

Matteo PERCIVALE - *University of Genoa, Italy*

T26

TUE-POST02-382 | Thermodynamic and experimental evaluation of CO₂ utilization via light alkane oxidative dehydrogenation

Matteo PERCIVALE - *University of Genoa, Italy*

T26	TUE-POST02-383 CO₂ conversion to cyclic carbonates by potassium hexaniobate and a novel silica-pillared-hexanoate	
	Sibele PERGHER - <i>Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte - UFRN, Brazil</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-384 C₂+ synthesis by direct hydrogenation of CO₂ over modified Co/TiO₂ catalysts	
	Doan PHAM MINH - <i>Université de Toulouse, IMT Mines Albi, UMR CNRS 5302, Centre RAPSODEE, Campus Jarlard, F-81013 Albi, cedex 09, France, France</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-385 Mo₂Ti₂C₃TX MXene performance in catalytic CO₂ hydrogenation and its promotion with single Pt atoms	
	Yilong YAN - <i>IRCELYON, France</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-386 Electrocatalytic CO₂ reduction on gas diffusion electrodes decorated with supported Cu nanoparticles in a zero-gap configuration	
	Jérôme CAPITOLIS - <i>IRCELYON, France</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-387 Bifunctional catalysts for the sorption-enhanced reverse water gas shift	
	Johannis PIETERSE - <i>TNO, Netherlands</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-388 Heteropolyacid-based Catalysts for Single-Step Dimethylether Synthesis from CO₂	
	Maximilian J. POLLER - <i>Universität Hamburg, Germany</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-389 Flue gas composition effects on DFMs for CO₂ capture and hydrogenation investigated by spatially-resolved operando FT-IR	
	Luca LIETTI - <i>Politecnico di Milano, Italy</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-390 Development of Ni/CeO₂ for CO₂ reduction	
	Luiz POSSATO - <i>São Paulo State University, Brazil</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-391 Surface reactions on Cu-based bimetallic catalysts supported on ZrO₂: CO₂ adsorption and its role on methanol production	
	Linda JEWELL - <i>University of South Africa, Department of Chemical Engineering, Florida 1709, Johannesburg, South Africa</i>	
T26	TUE-POST02-392 Influence of the preparation routes of NiMgAl-mixed oxides on their CO₂ methanation catalytic activities	
	Christophe POUPIN - <i>Unité de Chimie Environnementale et interactions sur le vivant, Université du Littoral Cote d'Opale, 59140 Dunkerque, France, France</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-395 Catalytic Production of Renewable LPG	

T28	TUE-POST02-396 Aviation Fuels by co-Oligomerization of Ethylene and 1-Butylene using an Oil tempered Bench Scale Reactor	
	Christoph HAUBER - <i>hte - The High Throughput Experimentation Company, Germany</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-397 Influence of Sulfation on Activity & Stability of Metal oxide Catalysts for Vapor-phase Ketonisation of Volatile Fatty Acid	
	Haresh MANYAR - <i>Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-398 Advanced biodiesel from animal fats using supercritical technologies	
	Joaquin MARTINEZ TRIGUERO - <i>Instituto de Tecnologia Quimica UPV-CSIC, Spain</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-399 Hydrodeoxygenation of biomass-derived oxygenated compounds by metal loaded hierarchical Y zeolite	
	Angela MARTINS - <i>Instituto Superior de Engenharia de Lisboa - IPL., Portugal - Centro de Química Estrutural, Faculdade de Ciências, Institute of Molecular Sciences, Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-400 Synthesis of jet fuel intermediate via aldol condensation of biomass(furfural & acetone) with Mg-Al catalyst in continuous reactor	
	Saleem MUNIR - <i>Universitat Rovira i Virgili, Spain</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-401 Beechwood pyrolysis under H2 at atmospheric pressure with bifunctional catalysts	
	Katy NESPOULOUS - <i>Institut de recherches sur la catalyse et l'environnement, CNRS, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-402 High-throughput design of metal-supported heterogeneous catalysts for the selective conversion of fatty acids to hydrocarbons	
	Sébastien PAUL - <i>Unité de Catalyse et Chimie du Solide (UCCS - UMR CNRS 8181), France</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-403 Hydrotreatment of waste vegetable oil for advanced biofuels production	
	Paula MÁRMOL - <i>CSIC, Spain</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-404 Hydrodeoxygenation of anisole over bimetallic PtxNi/SBA-15 catalysts: Effect of Ni/Pt ratio on the catalytic behavior	
	Daniel E. PÉREZ-ESTRADA - <i>Facultad de Química - Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Mexico</i>	

T28	TUE-POST02-405 Catalytic co-pyrolysis of sugarcane bagasse and single-use polyethylene to produce biofuel using zeolite X from coal fly ash	
T28	TUE-POST02-406 Role of reconstructed hydrotalcite on selective obtention of cyclohexane with Ni-, NiCu-catalysts combined with H-β zeolite.	
	Angie Carolyne RUEDA ALTAMAR - <i>UNIVERSITAT ROVIRI I VIRGILI, Spain</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-407 Co-hydroprocessing of vacuum gas oil and black soldier fly larvae lipids	
	Jon SELIMI - <i>Lund University, Sweden - Hulteberg Chemistry & Engineering AB, Sweden</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-408 Ru Nanoparticles Deposited on Amorphous Aluminosilicates as Effective Low-Temperature Catalysts for Hydrocracking of n-Hexadecane	
	Nataliya SHCHERBAN - <i>L.V. Pysarzhevsky Institute of Physical Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Ukraine - Åbo Akademi University, Finland</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-409 Micro-mesoporous zeolitic materials obtained by recrystallization as catalysts in the isomerization of methyl oleate.	
	Francesco DI RENZO - <i>Institut Charles Gerhardt de Montpellier, France</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-410 Advanced reactor design for continuous pyrolysis oil upgrading into renewable hydrocarbon fuels via hydrodeoxygenation catalysis	
	Alexander SØGAARD - <i>DTU Chemical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, Denmark</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-411 A sustainable pathway towards methane-assisted biorefineries	
	Hua SONG - <i>University of Calgary, Canada</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-412 Spectroscopic Insights of highly dispersed Cu catalyst for CHT and HDO of bio-derived feedstocks	
	Tawan SOOKNOI - <i>Catalytic Chemistry Research Unit, School of Science, King Mongkut's Institute of Technology Ladkrabang, Thailand</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-413 Exploring Morphological Adaptation of Nb₂O₅ in Pellet-Shaped Catalysts and Its Influence on Catalytic Performance	
	Naiara TELIS - <i>Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany</i>	
T28	TUE-POST02-414 Influence of TiO₂ and ZrO₂ on Ru-based catalysts for Hydrodeoxygenation of Phenol and Coprocessing of Phenol and Dibenzothiophene	
	José Antonio DE LOS REYES - <i>Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana, Mexico</i>	

T28	TUE-POST02-415 Aldol Condensation of Cyclopentanone and Furfural on Ce-Based Catalysts for Sustainable Aviation Fuel	
T28	TUE-POST02-416 Transition Metal-Based Heterogeneous Catalyst for Biofuel Application	
	Ka Fu YUNG - The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong	
T29	TUE-POST02-419 Selective C-O hydrogenolysis of erythritol over supported carbide catalysts in aqueous phase	
	Theresa AL BAYEH - Ircelyon, France	
T29	TUE-POST02-420 Cost-effective and stable Zr-based catalysts for the ketonization of valeric acid to dibutyl ketone	
	Damien P. DEBECKER - Institute of Condensed Matter and Nanosciences (IMCN), Université catholique de Louvain (UCLouvain), Belgium	
T29	TUE-POST02-421 Rational optimization of the cascade synthesis of γ-valerolactone	
	Alessandro ALLEGRI - Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna, Italy	
T29	TUE-POST02-422 Unraveling the mechanism of glycerol oxidation to dicarboxylic acids over a copper oxide catalyst	
	Prince AMANIAMPONG - CNRS-University of Poitiers, France	
T29	TUE-POST02-423 Furfural transfer hydrogenation over metal organic framework-derived catalyst	
	Debarun BANERJEE - The University of Queensland, Australia - Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India	
T29	TUE-POST02-424 Dimethyl adipate from bio-based cyclopentanone and dimethyl carbonate: a heterogeneously-catalyzed alternative approach	
	Tommaso TABANELLI - Department of Industrial Chemistry 'Toso Montanari', Alma Mater Studiorum – University of Bologna and Center for Chemical Catalysis – C3, 40136 Bologna, Italy, Italy	
T29	TUE-POST02-425 Synthesis of hydrous zirconia catalysts for lactic acid production from wheat bran.	
	Alicia BOIX - Research Institute of Catalysis and Petrochemistry. Universidad Nacional del Litoral (UNL), Argentina	
T29	TUE-POST02-426 Relationship between Lewis acid sites and activity over carbohydrates conversion	

T29	TUE-POST02-427 The role Al and oxygen vacancy in acetic acid synthesis from ethanol employing Cu/ZnO/Al	
	Bruna BRONSATO - <i>National Institute of Technology, Brazil - Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-428 Hydrogenolysis of isosorbide to triols and diols over a silica-supported Rh catalyst	
	Pengru CHEN - <i>Osaka metropolitan university, Japan</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-429 Effects of Local Reaction Sphere on Acidity of Reactive Hydrogen and their Catalytic Involvement in C-O and C-H Scission Chemistry	
	Cathy Ya-Huei CHIN - <i>University of Toronto, Canada</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-430 Influence of the support acidity on the bioethanol dehydrogenation over Cu-based catalysts for acetaldehyde production	
	Maria S. CHINO - <i>KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Department of Chemical Engineering, Sweden</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-431 Valorization of Biomass through Production of Biodegradable Plastic via CO2 Consumption	
	Yuyeol CHOI - <i>Department of Chemistry, Chonnam National University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-432 Carboxylic acids from hemicellulose-derived mixture of sugars: homogeneous and heterogeneous catalytic process	
	Izabela CZEKAJ - <i>Cracow University of Technology, Poland</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-433 Selective aerobic oxidative cleavage and amidation of C-C bond	
	Xingchao DAI - <i>Leibniz Institute for Catalysis, Germany</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-434 Kraft Oligolignin as crosslinking agent in elastomer chemistry	
	Rémy DEVIENNE - <i>IRCELYON, CNRS, UMR 5256 CNRS-UCBL, France</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-435 Lignocellulose to ethylene glycol: system stability using an organic-rich solvent and semi-batch bi-catalytic hydrogenolysis	
	Romolo DI SABATINO - <i>University of Twente, Netherlands</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-436 Selective Dehydration of Xylose catalyzed by Metallic Mixed Oxides	
	Francisco CERNICHARO-TOLEDO - <i>Instituto de Tecnología Química (ITQ, UPV - CSIC), Spain</i>	

T29	TUE-POST02-437 Non-isothermal study of the catalytic gasification of underutilized biomass using CO₂+H₂O as gasifying agent	
	Sofía ESSOUNANI-MÉRIDA - <i>University of Málaga, Spain</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-438 Aerobic oxidation of ethylene glycol to glycolic acid in water promoted by carbon-supported PtCu bimetallic nanoparticles	
	Claudio EVANGELISTI - <i>CNR-ICCOM, Italy</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-439 Synergetic Catalysis of Dual Metal Sites for Selective Hydrogenation of Furfuryl Platform Compounds into Sustainable Products	
	Wenhao FANG - <i>School of Chemical Science and Technology, Yunnan University, China</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-440 Metal-modified hierarchical MFI catalysts and their olefins selectivity during the catalytic conversion of pyrolysis oil	
	Elise FARAH - <i>KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-441 Manipulating activity and stability of MgO in the presence of water using catalyst fluorination for biomass valorization	
	Jimmy FARIA - <i>Catalytic Processes and Materials group, Faculty of Science and Technology, MESA+ Institute for Nanotechnology, Netherlands</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-442 Selective H₂-free dehydroxylation of glyceric acid to acrylates over Rhenium catalysts	
	Maja GABRIC - <i>National Institute of Chemistry, Slovenia</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-443 Synthesis of 1,4-Butanediol from 1,4-Anhydroerythritol over MoO_x/TiO₂ + Cu/TiO₂ Mixture Catalyst	
	Jianxing GAN - <i>Tohoku University, Sendai, Miyagi, Japan, Japan</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-444 Production of green aromatics via catalytic aromatization of bio-oil compounds over metal-doped zeolites	
	Florian RATHMANN - <i>VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, Finland</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-445 Lignin Upgrading via Coupling Hydrogen Production and Hydrodeoxygenation	
	Yong GUO - <i>East China University of Science & Technology, China</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-446 Aqueous Phase Reductive Amination of Biomass-derived 1,6-Hexanediol Using Reusable Ru-Supported on Carbon Catalyst	
	Navneet Kumar GUPTA - <i>Indian Institute of Science - Bengaluru, India</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-447 Depolymerization of pre-commercial lignins by supported Platinum-based catalyst	

T29	TUE-POST02-448 Towards the oxidation of 5-hydroxymethyl furfural by (bi)metallic colloids in aqueous medium	
	Lénaick HERVÉ - <i>Institut de Recherche sur la Catalyse et l'Environnement de Lyon, France</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-449 Significant Support Effect in Carboxylic Acid Transformation into Hydrocarbons over RuSn Catalysts	
	Marcel Jonathan HIDAJAT - <i>Green Carbon Research Center, Korea Research Institute of Chemical Technology, Korea (Republic of) - Department of Advanced Materials and Chemical Engineering, University of Science and Technology, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-450 Selective Hydrogenolysis of Glucose with supported bifunctional Catalysts	
	Aileen HÜBNER - <i>Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-451 Butadiene from biomass derivatives over Re-Mo based catalysts	
	Georgia IOANNIDOU - <i>Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-452 RS03H/SiO2 nanospheres for fructose dehydration to 5-HMF	
	Aina Syahida JAMAL - <i>University of Manchester, United Kingdom</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-453 Valorization of glycolaldehyde with Sn-zeolites to bio-based building blocks: Effect of zeolite structure on products distribution	
	Jose Manuel JIMENEZ-MARTIN - <i>Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Spain</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-454 Metal-Support Cooperation in Pt/Al(PO3)3 for Remarkably Efficient Hydrogenolysis of Oxygenates	
	Xiongjie JIN - <i>The University of Tokyo, Japan</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-455 Enhancing the catalytic transfer hydrogenation of levulinic acid to γ-valerolactone over bimetallic Ni/CeO2 catalyst	
	Fangli JING - <i>Southwest Petroleum University, China</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-456 Ketonization of Palmitic Acid Over MnO Catalysts with Different Morphologies for Biolubricant Production	
	Siriporn JONGPATIWUT - <i>Chulalongkorn University, Thailand</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-457 Production of biomass-derived polyalphaolefin-grade lubricant	
	Sang Hyeok KO - <i>Hanyang University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-458 One-Pot Epimerization of 1,4-Anhydroerythritol into 1,4-Anhydrothreitol over Supported Ru-Ir Catalyst	

T29	TUE-POST02-459 Catalytic pine wood liquefaction in SC-MeOH: Influence of SC-CO2 and MeONa/ SC-CO2 pretreatment.	
	Awalah Alain KOMENAN - <i>IRCELYON, France</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-460 Continuous pine wood liquefaction in SC MeOH implemented in a plug flow reactor: insights on acid or base catalyzed mechanisms	
	Awalah Alain KOMENAN - <i>IRCELYON, France</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-461 Mechanochemical hydrolysis of chitin over carbon-based catalysts	
	Hirokazu KOBAYASHI - <i>Komaba Institute for Science, The University of Tokyo, 3-8-1 Komaba, Meguro-ku, Tokyo, Japan</i>	
T29	TUE-POST02-462 Synthesis of functionalized xylo-oligosaccharides from hemicellulose side streams by mechanocatalytic depolymerization	
	François JÉRÔME - <i>Institut de Chimie des Milieux et Matériaux de Poitiers, France</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-464 Co3O4/LaCoO3 Heterostructure as an Efficient Catalyst for Methane Catalytic Oxidation under Wet and CO rich conditions	
	Mohamad ABOU DAHER - <i>King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST), Saudi Arabia</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-465 The Effect of Metal Ratio and Precipitating Agent on Highly Active Iron-Manganese Metal Oxide Catalysts for Propane Oxidation	
	Liam BAILEY - <i>Max Planck-Cardiff Centre on the Fundamentals of Heterogeneous Catalysis FUNCAT, United Kingdom</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-466 Utilisation of in situ Generated H2O2 for Greywater Remediation	
	Ben BAYNTUN - <i>Cardiff University, United Kingdom</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-467 Cu-containing Ce-OMS-2-based catalysts for environmental applications	
	Francisco J. CADETE SANTOS AIRES - <i>IRCELYON (UMR 5256 CNRS/UCBLyon1), France</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-468 MOF-derived Rh/Co3O4 as novel catalyst for the decomposition of nitrous oxide	
	Daniel CANO-BLANCO - <i>Paul Scherrer Institut, Switzerland - École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Switzerland</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-469 Structural features leading to high CH4 oxidation activity and stability for Pd/CeO2-based catalysts	

T31	TUE-POST02-470 Cobalt-based catalysts for N2O abatement on NH3-fuelled ships
T31	TUE-POST02-471 Shape-dependent activity of Pd/CeO2 nanorods, nanocubes, and nano-octahedrons on lean methane oxidation
T31	TUE-POST02-472 Influence of nanoparticle structure on activity and stability of bimetallic PtPd/Al2O3 catalysts for lean exhaust emission control
T31	TUE-POST02-473 Effects of Relative Humidity on DAC with K2CO3 Sorbents Supported on Carbons of Different Surface Polarity
T31	TUE-POST02-474 Promotional effect of periodic Rich and Lean switching on the performance of Three-Way Catalysts
T31	TUE-POST02-475 Removal of imidacloprid and its transformation products from wastewater by solar photo-Fenton processes at neutral pH
T31	TUE-POST02-476 Carbamazepine removal by Fenton-like process under solar irradiation
T31	TUE-POST02-477 Activity and stability of catalysts deNOx/deN2O Nitric Acid Proces
T31	TUE-POST02-478 Solar photocatalytic degradation of emerging contaminants in water by clay/TiO2 macrocomposites
T31	TUE-POST02-479 Tin(II) embedded into calcium phosphate for effective Cr(VI) reductive adsorption and its upcycling into a catalyst

T31	TUE-POST02-480 Promotion of Co₃O₄ catalysts by acid-etching and ruthenium incorporation for chlorinated VOC oxidation	
	Andoni CHOYA - <i>University of the Basque Country, Spain</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-481 Thermal ageing of a commercial LNT catalyst: effects on the structure and functionalities	
	Alexandre GOGUET - <i>Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-482 Investigation of the deactivation of a washcoated monolith using a spatially resolved technique	
	Alexandre GOGUET - <i>Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-483 Development of a spatially resolved technique for the measure of effective diffusions.	
	Goguet ALEXANDRE - <i>Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-484 Effect of the o-DCB oxidation in the CH₄-SCR reaction rate	
	Lina-Maria GONZALEZ - <i>Universidad de Antioquia, Colombia</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-485 Impact of the strength of Pd-perovskite in Natural Gas Vehicles three-way catalysts: A kinetic approach	
	Pascal GRANGER - <i>University of Lille, France</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-486 Mesostructured manganese oxides as catalysts for the total oxidation of indoor VOCs at mild temperatures	
	Nadia GRIFASI - <i>Politecnico di Torino, Italy</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-487 A highly active core-shell Ca/Cu/YCeO₂@TiO₂ catalyst for the total oxidation of naphthalene	
	Sichem GUERRERO - <i>Universidad de los Andes, Chile</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-488 Oxidative degradation of highly hazardous chemical and biological contaminants over sulfonic acid ion-exchange resin catalysts	
	Matteo GUIDOTTI - <i>CNR-SCITEC, Institute of Chemical Sciences and Technologies, Italy</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-489 An efficient Ru/STO catalyst for catalytic combustion of CVOCs emissions	
	Yanglong GUO - <i>East China University of Science and Technology, China</i>	
T31	TUE-POST02-490 Construction of High-performance VOC Oxidation Catalysts from Molecular Structure Units	

 Wei HAN - *The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong*

T31 **TUE-POST02-491 | Cu-based Catalysts for Air Purification**

 Masatomo HATTORI - *Institute of Materials and Systems for Sustainability, Nagoya University, Japan*

T31 **TUE-POST02-492 | Reverse Hysteresis during NH₃-SCR of NO_x Catalyzed by Small Pore Cu/Zeolites**

 Gustavo A. FUENTES - *Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana-Unidad Iztapalapa, Mexico*

T31 **TUE-POST02-493 | Performance enhancement of Three-Way-Catalysts by periodic operation**

 Daniel HODONJ - *Institute for Chemical Technology and Polymer Chemistry, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany*

T31 **TUE-POST02-494 | A comparative study of two copper-supported catalysts for CO oxidation in simulated gasoline internal combustion engines**

 María-José ILLÁN-GÓMEZ - *University of Alicante, Spain*

T31 **TUE-POST02-495 | Insights into VOCs and ozone competitive adsorption on catalysts surfaces through in-situ DRIFTS studies at low temperature**

 Amira JABBARI-HICHRI - *IRCELYON UMR5256, CNRS-UCBL, France*

18.07 17:30 - 19:30 | THU-POST03 | Poster Session 3

 Exhibition Hall

T26 **Ni-MgO/Al₂O₃ Dual Functional Material for CO₂ Capture and Conversion**

 Javier IVANEZ - *Ircelyon, France*

T1 **THU-POST03-1 | Functionalization of silanes by carbene Si-H insertion catalyzed by ruthenium phthalocyanine complex**

 Cenna TOULLEC - *IRCELYON, France*

T1 **THU-POST03-2 | Unravelling the mechanism of the alkoxyacylation of butadiene: what is the role of the base?**

 Mohammad AMESKAL

T1 **THU-POST03-3 | A series of heterobimetallic complexes associating tantalum and 3d transition metals as potential candidates for cooperative bond activation**

 Till NEUMANN - *Université de Lyon, Institut de Chimie de Lyon, Université Claude Bernard Lyon I, France*

T1	THU-POST03-4 Synthesis, Reactivity, and Catalytic Behavior of Immobilized Copper Hydrides and Borohydrides	
	Wael BARAKAT - <i>Stuttgart University- Germany, Germany</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-5 Formation of Nanostructured Ti and Cu Si-MFI Zeolites for Bioethanol Upgrading	
	Jessica BEDWARD - <i>Durham University, United Kingdom</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-6 Development of Facile Methods for the Preparation of Alumina Supported Non-Noble Metal Catalysts	
	Abdenmour BENABBAS - <i>CNRS, Université de Poitiers, Institut de Chimie des Milieux et Matériaux de Poitiers (IC2MP), France</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-7 Probing Metal-Ligand Cooperativity Effects in Pincer Mn Catalyzed CO₂ Hydrogenation	
	Wesley BERNSKOETTER - <i>University of Missouri, United States</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-8 Recyclable Heterogenized Molecular Ni Catalysts for the Direct C-H Arylation of Benzothiophenes	
	Jérôme CANIVET - <i>Univ.Lyon CNRS-IRCELYON, France</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-9 Photocatalyzed Alkane Conversion by Polyoxometalates	
	Alix DESJONQUÈRES - <i>Sorbonne Université, France</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-10 Yttrium-Iridium Systems for Methane Deuteration	
	Zachary DUBRAWski - <i>Laboratory of Chemistry, Catalysis, Polymers and Processes, CP2M UMR 5128, Université de Lyon, Institut de Chimie de Lyon, CNRS, Université Lyon 1, France</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-11 SILICA-SUPPORTED GOLD-PALLADIUM NANOPARTICLES FOR PLASMONIC CATALYSIS IN CONTINUOUS FLOW	
	Antonin ENGEL - <i>UCLouvain, Belgium</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-12 Molybdenum Pentahydrides Complexes as Catalysts for Hydrogenation of Alkenes and Ketones	
	Arno ESTIVAL - <i>LCC CNRS, France</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-13 Comprehensive Screening of Pd-Catalyzed Cross-Coupling Reactions using Deep Learning	
	Oliver TRAPP - <i>Department of Chemistry, Ludwig-Maximilians University, Germany</i>	

T1	THU-POST03-14 Selective ethylene oligomerization into C6-C10 olefins	
	Liliana GONÇALVES - <i>Paul Scherrer Institute, Switzerland</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-15 Highly Active and Selective Wacker-Type Markovnikov Oxidation of Olefins into Ketones with First-Row Metal Catalysts	
	Rafael GRAMAGE-DORIA - <i>University Rennes, France</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-16 Unveiling the role of Mo₃S₄ clusters in the (Z)-selective semihydrogenation of alkynes	
	María GUTIÉRREZ BLANCO - <i>Universitat Jaume I, Spain</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-18 CO-induced sintering of isolated palladium surface species at room temperature	
	Lea KOPIETZ - <i>Technical University of Munich, Germany</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-20 Extra-framework cationic vanadium species in zeolites and their reactivity	
	Mariia LEMISHKA - <i>J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry of the CAS, v. v. i., Czechia</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-21 Discussion on the science of size effect in reductive amination of carbonyl compounds	
	Yunong LI - <i>The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, China</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-22 Unconventional sulfoxide hydrogenation catalyzed by Mo₃S₄ cluster units, study of a new sulfur centered mechanism	
	Juan José MATEU-CAMPOS - <i>Universitat Jaume I, Spain</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-23 New N^CN ligands obtained through Pd-catalyzed direct arylation of difluorinated substrates	
	Luca MAURI - <i>Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-24 Highly active and selective direct conversion of CO_x to light olefins over Ga-based bifunctional catalyst	
	Fanhui MENG - <i>Taiyuan University of Technology, China</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-25 Well defined supported nickel oligomerization catalysts	
	Nicolas MERLE - <i>Unité de Catalyse et Chimie du Solide (UCCS) - UMR 8181, France</i>	

T1	THU-POST03-26 Bridging the Gap between Molecular and Solid Catalysts: Nanoporous Phosphine-Based Macroligands for the Activation of CO₂	
T1	THU-POST03-27 Designing Phosphine Ligands: A Study of Steric and Electronic Effects for Palladium(0/II) Catalyzed Reactions	
	Tomas PASKEVICIUS - <i>Center for Physical Sciences and Technology, Department of Organic chemistry, Lithuania</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-28 The use of KIT-6 and SBA-15 for heterogenization of Ni-β dimina complexes for etilene oligomeriation	
	Sibele PERGHER - <i>Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte - UFRN, Brazil</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-29 Silica-Supported Early-Late Heterobimetallic Complexes as the Catalysts for H/D Exchange in Alkanes	
	Andrei PICHUGOV - <i>Laboratory of Catalysis, Polymerization, Processes and Materials (CP2M), Université de Lyon, Institut de Chimie de Lyon, France</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-30 The effect of catalyst nanoparticle size on sugar oxidation	
	Ole REINS DORF - <i>Åbo Akademi University, Finland</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-31 Ru-based supported catalysts for ammonia synthesis at mild conditions	
	Swati SINGH - <i>Khalifa University, United Arab Emirates</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-33 Atomically dispersed 3d metal bimetallic dual atom catalysts and classification of the structural descriptors	
	Ching Kit WUN - <i>Department of Applied Biology and Chemical Technology, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-34 Vapor-phase ethanol carbonylation over Ni/AC catalysts: Influence of the textural properties and oxygen-containing groups	
	Huahua ZHAO - <i>State Key Laboratory for Oxo Synthesis and Selective Oxidation, Lanzhou Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-37 Hydroformylation Catalyzed by Unmodified Cobalt Carbonyl under Mild Conditions	
	Baoxin ZHANG - <i>Leibniz Institute for Catalysis, Germany</i>	
T1	THU-POST03-38 Ru Nanoparticles Immobilized on Guanidinium-Based Supported Ionic Liquids Phases as Adaptive Hydrogenation Catalysts	
	Yuyan ZHANG - <i>Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Germany</i>	

T1	THU-POST03-39 Heterogeneous catalysis of ligand-protected metal clusters	
	Yan ZHU - <i>Nanjing University, China</i>	
T2	THU-POST03-40 μ-Oxo-Hypervalent Iodine Catalysis for Metal-Free Oxidative Aromatic Aminations	
	Shotaro HAMATANI - <i>Graduate School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Ritsumeikan University, Japan</i>	
T2	THU-POST03-41 Metal-free dibenzoxazepinone synthesis through chemoselective aromatic coupling with hypervalent iodine reagent and catalyst	
	Naoki MIYAMOTO - <i>College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Ritsumeikan University, Japan</i>	
T2	THU-POST03-42 Synthesis, Characterization and Functionalization of MOFs and Their Use in Knoevenagel Condensation	
	Caridad NODA - <i>Universidade Federal de Goiás, Brazil</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-45 Tetralin conversion over NiMo and NiW supported on HY prepared by thermal spreading on zeolite previously exchanged by Ni	
	Isabela LEOCADIO - <i>PETROBRAS, Brazil</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-46 Impact of Seed-Assisted Crystallization of CON-type zeolite Catalyst	
	Masato SAWADA - <i>Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-47 Effects of Particle Composition and Interparticle Distance in the Direct Synthesis of H₂O₂ over Model Catalysts Based on Au@Pd NPs	
	Heiko Sebastian SCHIEFER - <i>Institute of Catalysis Research and Technology, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Germany</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-48 X3DTM – additive manufacturing of heterogeneous catalysts for optimized catalyst performance	
	Nils SCHIRMER - <i>BASF SE, Germany</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-49 Novel Approaches for Preparation of 3D Ni-Al₂O₃ Core with Zeolite Shell Catalysts for Dry Reforming of Methane	
	Parisa SHAFIEE - <i>Department of Process and Plant Technology, Brandenburg University of Technology (BTU) Cottbus-Senftenberg, Germany, Germany</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-50 Alginate-based cryostructures as "green" carriers for immobilization of chiral organic catalysts of C-C bond formation	
	Maksim SHANDYBO - <i>HSE University, Russian Federation</i>	

T4	THU-POST03-51 Rationally designed bifunctional catalyst with metal incorporated core-shell ZSM-5 and silicalite-1 architecture	
T4	THU-POST03-52 Hierarchical porous carbon nanomaterials as electrodes for energy applications	
	Zili SIDERATOU - <i>Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, NCSR Demokritos, Greece</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-53 Influence of fluorine on magnesium hydr(oxide) fluorides properties used as catalysts in aldol condensation reaction.	
	Frédéric RICHARD - <i>Institut de Chimie des Milieux et Matériaux de Poitiers, France</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-54 Molecularly Defined Precursors for Atomic-Level Design of Cu/Zn and Cu/Zr Interfaces Targeting CO2 Conversion	
	Leonardo SOUSA - <i>University College London, United Kingdom - Research Complex at Harwell, United Kingdom - University of Campinas, Brazil</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-55 Introducing Defects at the PCN/TiO2 Interface: a Comparative Investigation	
	Giuseppe SPORTELLI - <i>Materials, Environment and Energy Research Group, University of Trieste, Italy - University School for Advanced Studies IUSS Pavia, Italy</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-56 Machine Learning-Enabled Optimization of Supported Gold Catalysts for Base-Free Furfural Oxidation	
	Joelle THURIOT - <i>UCCS - CNRS UMR 8181, France</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-57 New Lamellar Zeolitic Phases and Structural Modifications via Soft Exfoliation Processes in MWW-Type Zeolites	
	Jordi TORRÓ ABRIL - <i>Instituto de Tecnología Química (UPV-CSIC), Spain</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-58 Strategic co-doping of lanthanum-doped CeO2 nanoflowers for improving the oxidative coupling of methane performance	
	Fabiane TRNDADE - <i>Federal University of ABC, Brazil</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-59 Platinum nanoparticle deposition on two-dimensional materials via Electron Beam Lithography: exclusive effect of 2D support	
	Martin VESELY - <i>University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Czechia</i>	
T4	THU-POST03-60 Highly dispersed Ni embedded in SiO2 for methane production from CO2 hydrogenation	

T4	THU-POST03-61 Zeolite stabilized metal nanoparticles for durable catalysis 	
T4	THU-POST03-62 The Influence of Preparation Method on Cooperative Redox Enhancement Effects Exhibited in Au-Pd Systems 	
T4	THU-POST03-63 Thermal-induced intermetallic M1Zn1 nanoparticles with high phase-purity for highly selective hydrogenation of alkyne 	
T4	THU-POST03-64 Perovskite-type oxide catalyst prepared by thermal decomposition of heteronuclear metal cyano complex precursor	
T4	THU-POST03-65 Insight into MoS2 structure on the activity for the methanation of CO2 	
T5	THU-POST03-67 Deriving a Model for Catalytic Methane Pyrolysis: A DFT Study 	
T5	THU-POST03-68 Understanding the formation of surface anion vacancies using DFT for catalysis application 	
T5	THU-POST03-69 Analysis of propane dehydrogenation and metathesis on TiH2(111) surface using an automated reaction path search method 	
T5	THU-POST03-70 Catalytic conversion of methane to methanol over metal oxides supported by CHA-type zeolites: a systematic computational screening 	
T5	THU-POST03-71 Supported Metal Catalysts Circumvent Limitations in Reactivity for Oxygen Electrocatalysis	

T5	THU-POST03-72 On-line optimization for integrated carbon capture and conversion process through a combined DFT-microkinetic-modeling workflow	
	Supareak PRASERTHDAM - <i>Chulalongkorn University, Thailand</i>	
T8	THU-POST03-73 Optimizing the synthesis and probing the acidic properties of an extra-large pore aluminosilicate ZEO-1	
	Mohammad FAHDA - <i>Laboratoire Catalyse et Spectrochimie (LCS), Normandie Université, ENSICAEN, UNICAEN, CNRS, , France</i>	
T5	THU-POST03-74 Unlocking the Catalytic Chemistry Behind Bio-Based Reductive Amination	
	Max QUAYLE - <i>Cardiff University, United Kingdom</i>	
T5	THU-POST03-75 Density functional theory elucidation of potential ammonia synthesis and decomposition mechanisms using Ru/MgO(111) catalysts	
	Yves Ira REYES - <i>Department of Engineering and Systems Science, National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan</i>	
T5	THU-POST03-76 MoO₃ Surface Reactivity in Nuclear Reactor Phenomena	
	Mariam SAAB - <i>Sorbonne & IRSN, France</i>	
T5	THU-POST03-77 Introducing the Automated Multiscale Simulation Environment	
	Albert SABADELL-RENDÓN - <i>ICIQ, Spain</i>	
T5	THU-POST03-78 Exploring surface terminations and reactivity of epitaxially grown maghemite on Pt substrate	
	Amit SAHU - <i>Laboratoire Interdisciplinaire Carnot de Bourgogne, France</i>	
T5	THU-POST03-79 Investigating the role of promoters in the methane to methanol oxidation on the iridium ZSM-5 catalysts	
	B Sathya SAI RENGAM - <i>IIT MADRAS, India</i>	
T5	THU-POST03-80 Prediction of high coverage adsorption on catalyst surfaces by digital annealing techniques	
	Hiroshi SAMPEI - <i>Waseda University, Japan</i>	
T5	THU-POST03-81 Morphology of Ru nanoparticles at titania-water interface - a computational study	
	Joshua M. SIMS - <i>ENS de Lyon, France</i>	
T5	THU-POST03-82 Effect of copper on the hydrothermal stability of Cu-CHA	

T5	THU-POST03-83 Structure - activity relationships for the catalysis of the hydrogen evolution reaction by Ru-based nanomaterials	
	Xavier SOLANS-MONFORT - <i>Universitat autònoma de Barcelona, Spain</i>	
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	Matteo MAESTRI - <i>Politecnico di Milano, Laboratory of Catalysis and Catalytic Processes, Dipartimento di Energia, Italy</i>	
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	Parinya TANGPAKONSAB - <i>Technische Universität Wien, Austria</i>	
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	Frederik TIELENS - <i>ALGC - Materials Modelling Group, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Belgium</i>	
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	Laureline TREPS - <i>ENS Lyon, France - IFPEN, France</i>	
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	Dilan TUNÇER - <i>Izmir Institute of Technology, Turkey</i>	
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	Amira UDDIN - <i>Queen Mary, University of London, United Kingdom</i>	
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	Cheng Hsi YEH - <i>Department of Engineering and Systems Science, National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan</i>	

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	Zisheng ZHANG - <i>University of California Los Angeles, United States</i>	
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	Prerna PAHWA - <i>Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Madras, India</i>	
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	Monika GEŠVANDTNEROVÁ - <i>Comenius University, Slovakia</i>	
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	Haseena K V - <i>Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India</i>	
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	Bin LIU - <i>Kansas State University, United States</i>	
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	Simone PEREGO - <i>Italian Institute of Technology, Italy - University of Milano-Bicocca, Italy</i>	
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	Mohd USSAMA - <i>Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Delhi, India</i>	
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	Tahmina TAGHI - <i>French-Azerbaijani University at Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Azerbaijan</i>	

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	Shuji TANABE - <i>Nagasaki University, Japan</i>	
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	Karolina TARACH - <i>Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland</i>	
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	Karolina TARACH - <i>Jagiellonian University in Krakow, Poland</i>	
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	Cindy Ly TAVERA-MÉNDEZ - <i>Erlangen Center for Interface Research and Catalysis (ECRC), Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU), Germany</i>	
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	Silviya TODOROVA - <i>Institute of Catalysis, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev St., Bulgaria</i>	
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	Antonio TORRES LOPEZ - <i>Cornell University, United States</i>	
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	Yeongjin JO - <i>Hanyang university, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
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	Hilde Johnsen VENVIK - <i>NTNU - Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Department of Chemical Engineering, Norway</i>	

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	Doohoo YOON - <i>hanyang university, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
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	Ximo WANG - <i>2819104341@qq.com, China</i>	
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	Jan WELZENBACH - <i>Technical University of Darmstadt, Germany</i>	
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	Sabine WRABETZ - <i>Fritz-Haber-Institut der Max-Planck-Gesellschaft, Germany</i>	
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	Melis YARAR - <i>Department of Mechanical and Process Engineering, ETH Zürich, 8092 Zürich, Switzerland, Switzerland</i>	
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	Nevzat YIGIT - <i>Institute of Materials Chemistry TU Wien, Austria</i>	
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	Tatchamapan YOSKAMTORM - <i>Wolfson Catalysis Centre, Department of Chemistry, University of Oxford, United Kingdom - Department of Chemistry, Chulalongkorn University, Thailand</i>	
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	Wentao YUAN - <i>Zhejiang University, China</i>	
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	Cheng ZHANG - <i>Long Island University (Post), United States</i>	
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	Mengxuan ZHANG - <i>Institute of Multidisciplinary Research for Advanced Materials (IMRAM), Tohoku University, Japan</i>	
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	Bert M. WECKHUYSEN - <i>Utrecht University, Netherlands</i>	
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	Andy ANTZARAS - <i>Department of Chemical Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece</i>	
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	German ARAUJO BARAHONA - <i>Laboratory of Industrial Chemistry and Reaction Engineering (TKR), Åbo Akademi University, Finland - Grupo de Tecnologías a Presión (PressTech), Instituto de Bioeconomía de la Universidad de Valladolid (BioEcoUVA), Universidad de Valladolid, Spain</i>	
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	Giulia FERRI - <i>Politecnico di Milano, Italy</i>	
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	Leandro GOULART DE ARAUJO - <i>IRCELYON, Institut de Recherches sur la Catalyse et l'Environnement de Lyon, UMR5256 CNRS-Université de Lyon, France</i>	
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	Marc GREUEL - <i>Fraunhofer UMSICHT, Germany</i>	
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	Jord Peter HAVEN - <i>Catalytic Processes and Materials, Faculty of Science and Technology, MESA+ Institute for Nanotechnology, University of Twente, Netherlands</i>	

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	Christoph HUBER - <i>Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany</i>	
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	Atsushi ISHIHARA - <i>Mie University, Japan</i>	
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	Zhenyu KANG - <i>Beijing Key Lab of Green Reaction Engineering and Technology, Tsinghua University, China</i>	
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	Vivien GÜNTHER - <i>LOGE AB, Sweden</i>	
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	Yashan LIN - <i>The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong</i>	
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	Raul LOBO - <i>University of Delaware, United States</i>	
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	Carlotta PANZONE - <i>Univ Grenoble Alpes, CEA, Liten, DTCH, Laboratoire Réacteurs et Procédés (LRP), F-38000 Grenoble, France, France</i>	
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	Abhinandan NABERA - <i>Department of Chemistry and Applied Biosciences, ETH Zurich, 8093 Zurich, Switzerland, Switzerland</i>	

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	Elisabetta ORFEI - <i>University of Bologna, Italy</i>	
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	Puja PAUL - <i>Dr, Australia</i>	
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	Pizzolitto CRISTINA - <i>CASALE SA, Switzerland</i>	
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	Ilenia ROSSETTI - <i>Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy</i>	
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	Tomone SASAYAMA - <i>National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST), Japan</i>	
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	Rebecca FUSHIMI - <i>Idaho National Lab, United States</i>	
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	Jacob VENUTI BJÖRKMAN - <i>Nynas AB, Sweden - KTH Department of Chemical Engineering, Sweden</i>	
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	Jingchong YAN - <i>Anhui University of Technology, China</i>	

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	Reyes MALLADA - <i>Chemical and Environmental Engineering Department. Institute of Nanoscience and Materials of Aragón (INMA). CSIC-Universidad de Zaragoza, Spain</i>	
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	Sebastian WEBER - <i>hte GmbH, Germany</i>	
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	Shabnam TAGHIPOUR - <i>Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong - Department of Civil Engineering, Sharif University of Technology, Iran</i>	
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	Shuji TANABE - <i>Nagasaki University, Japan</i>	
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	Atsuhiko TANAKA - <i>Kindai University, Japan</i>	
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	Xiao TIAN - <i>University of South Africa, South Africa</i>	
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	I-Hsiang TSENG - <i>Feng Chia University, Taiwan</i>	
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	Laura VALENZUELA - <i>Institut de Chimie et Procédés pour l'Energie, l'Environnement et la Santé, CNRS/Strasbourg University, France., France</i>	
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	Priyanka VERMA - <i>Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, India</i>	
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	Chung-Hsin WU - <i>National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology, Taiwan</i>	
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	Jiadong XIAO - <i>Research Initiative for Supra-Materials, Interdisciplinary Cluster for Cutting Edge Research, Shinshu University, Nagano 380-8553, Japan, Japan</i>	

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	Timo PRÖLß - <i>Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany</i>	
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	Mohammad Atiqur RAHMAN - <i>International Research Organization for Advanced Science and Technology (IROAST), Kumamoto University, Japan, Japan - Department of Chemistry, Graduate School of Science and Technology, Kumamoto University, 2-39-1 Kurokami, Chuo-ku, Kumamoto 860-8555, Japan, Japan</i>	
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	Muhammad Sohail RIAZ - <i>University of Galway, Ireland, Ireland</i>	
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	Rohib ROHIB - <i>Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, CNRS, IRCELYON, France</i>	
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	Minori SAITO - <i>Department of Chemical Science and Engineering, Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan</i>	
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	Clément SPADETTO - <i>IRCELYON (CNRS-Université de Lyon), France</i>	
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	Stephan STEINMANN - <i>ENS de Lyon, France</i>	
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	Dorottya SZALAY - <i>University of Oxford, United Kingdom</i>	
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	Valerie THEUNS - <i>Univ. Lille, CNRS, Centrale Lille, Univ. Artois, UCCS, France</i>	
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	Jinjin TIE - <i>Technical University of Munich, Germany</i>	

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	Chiang TZU HSUAN - <i>National United University, Taiwan</i>	
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	Ivo VAN LUIJK - <i>Biobased Chemistry and technology, Wageningen University and Research, Netherlands</i>	
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	Elizabeth VERA - <i>Univ. Grenoble-Alpes, Univ. Savoie Mont-Blanc, CNRS, Grenoble INP LEPMI, France</i>	
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	Miao WANG - <i>Kyungpook National University, Korea (Republic of)</i>	
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	André WARK - <i>Science Institute of the University of Iceland, Iceland</i>	
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	Tan WENYI - <i>Xuzhou University of Technology, China - Nanjing Institute of Technology, China</i>	
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	Yusuke YAMADA - <i>Osaka Metropolitan University, Japan</i>	
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	Liu YAN - <i>Institute of Sustainability for Chemicals, Energy and Environment (ISCE2), A*STAR, Singapore</i>	
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	Wei ZHANG - <i>Shanghai Key Laboratory of Green Chemistry and Chemical Processes, School of Chemistry and Molecular Engineering, East China Normal University, Shanghai, PR China, China</i>	

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	Thales GUIMÃRES ROCHA - <i>Univ. Grenoble-Alpes, Univ. Savoie Mont-Blanc, CNRS, Grenoble INP, LEPMI, France</i>	
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	Yucheng WANG - <i>Cardiff University, United Kingdom</i>	
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	Guillermo DIAZ-SAINZ - <i>University of Cantabria, Spain</i>	
T14	THU-POST03-232 Towards an efficient photoelectrochemical reduction of CO₂ to alcohols with Zr₆- and Hf₆-based photoanodes	
	Guillermo DÍAZ-SAINZ - <i>Departamento de Ingenierías Química y Biomolecular, Universidad de Cantabria (Spain), Spain</i>	
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	Nicolas FONDA - <i>Università degli Studi di Udine, Italy</i>	
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	Tej CHOKSI - <i>Nanyang Technological University, Singapore - Cambridge Centre for Advanced Research and Education in Singapore, Singapore</i>	
T15	THU-POST03-237 Titanium oxynitride/titania plasmonic catalysts for plasma assisted ammonia synthesis under visible light	
	Yuyan GONG - <i>University of Warwick, United Kingdom</i>	
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	Ran LIU - <i>University of South Africa, South Africa</i>	
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	Loren ACHER - <i>CNRS - Univ Lyon, France</i>	

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	Joao TANÉPAU - <i>IBMM, Univ Montpellier, CNRS, ENSCM, Montpellier, France, France - ICGM, Univ Montpellier, CNRS, ENSCM, Montpellier, France, France</i>	
T15	THU-POST03-242 Assisting heterogeneous catalysts with cavitation by bubbles: application in the CuO-catalyzed decomposition of H₂O₂	
	François JEROME - <i>IC2MP / Univ. Poitiers, France</i>	
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	Aleksandr FEDOROV - <i>Leibniz-Institut für Katalyse e. V., Germany</i>	
T16	THU-POST03-246 Designing Selective Hydrogenation Catalysts By Blending Experimental and Theoretical Data with AI	
	Lucas FOPPA - <i>The NOMAD Lab at the FHI of the Max-Planck-Gesellschaft and IRIS-Adlershof of the Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Germany</i>	
T16	THU-POST03-247 Clean kinetic data in ammonia synthesis	
	Oscar GOMEZ-CAPIRO - <i>Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Germany</i>	
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	P. Jakob JÄGERFELD - <i>Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT), Germany</i>	
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	Pedro MENDES - <i>University Lisbon, Portugal</i>	
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	Abdulrhman MOSHANTAF - <i>Fritz Haber Institut, Germany</i>	
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	Kiichi OBUCHI - <i>NEC Corporation & National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology, Japan</i>	

T16	THU-POST03-252 A Machine-Readable Database for FAIR Catalysis Research Data	
	Julia SCHUMANN - <i>Physics Department and IRIS Adlershof, Humboldt Universität zu Berlin, Germany</i> - <i>Department of Inorganic Chemistry, Fritz-Haber-Institut der Max-Planck-Gesellschaft, Germany</i>	
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	Olivier SCHILTER - <i>IBM Research Europe, Switzerland</i>	
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	Takashi TOYAO - <i>Hokkaido university, Japan</i>	
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	Bianca WENTZEL - <i>Fraunhofer FOKUS, Fraunhofer Institute for Open Communication Systems, Germany</i>	
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	Beyza YILMAZ - <i>Bogaziçi University, Turkey</i>	
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	Ramazan YILDIRIM - <i>BOĞAZIÇI UNIVERSITY, Turkey</i>	
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	Pavel AFANASIEV - <i>IRCELYON, France</i>	
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	Sylvette BRUNET - <i>IC2MP CNRS 7285 Université de Poitiers, France</i>	
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	Hong NIE - <i>SINOPEC Research Institute of Petroleum Processing CO., LTD., China</i>	
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	Pascal BLANCHARD - <i>University of Lille - UCCS, France</i>	
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	Pascal RAYBAUD - <i>IFP Energies Nouvelles, France</i>	
T18	THU-POST03-268 A mechanistic study of MoS₂ genesis from model Mo-oxide on gamma-alumina	
	Pascal RAYBAUD - <i>IFP Energies nouvelles, France - Univ Lyon, ENS de Lyon, CNRS UMR 5182, Laboratoire de Chimie, France</i>	
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	Jessica Katherine LAMUS SANGUINO - <i>Centro de investigación en Ciencia Aplicada y Tecnología Avanzada-Legaria, Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Mexico</i>	
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	Etienne GIRARD - <i>IFP Energies Nouvelles, France</i>	
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	Etienne GIRARD - <i>IFP Energie Nouvelles, France</i>	
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	Ma YUZHU - <i>Inner Mongolia University, China</i>	
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	Päivi MÄKI-ARVELA - <i>Åbo Akademi University, Finland</i>	
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	Shinya MASUDA - <i>Department of Chemistry, Graduate School of Science, The University of Tokyo, Japan</i>	
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	Jonathan Moritz MAUß - <i>Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Germany</i>	

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	Judith MEDINA-VARGAS - <i>Institute of Advanced Materials (INAM), Spain</i>	
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	Mario MENEGHETTI - <i>Federal University of Alagoas, Brazil</i>	
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	Takato MITSUDOME - <i>Osaka university, Japan</i>	
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	Tomoo MIZUGAKI - <i>Department of Materials Engineering Science, Graduate School of Engineering Science, Osaka University, Japan - Innovative Catalysis Science Division, Institute for Open and Transdisciplinary Research Initiatives (ICS-OTRI) Osaka University, Japan</i>	
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	Kausik MUKHOPADHYAY - <i>University of Central Florida, United States</i>	
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	Sonja MÜRTZ - <i>Institute for Technical and Macromolecular Chemistry, RWTH Aachen University, Germany</i>	
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	Xuan Trung NGUYEN - <i>ICCOM-CNR, Italy</i>	
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	Emrah OZENSOY - <i>Bilkent University, Turkey - UNAM - National Nanotechnology Research Center and Institute of Materials Science and Nanotechnology, Turkey</i>	
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	Yung-Kang PENG - <i>City University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong</i>	
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	Sibele PERGHER - <i>Laboratório de Peneiras Moleculares, Instituto de Química, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil</i>	

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	Piyasan PRASERTHDAM - <i>Chulalongkorn University, Thailand</i>	
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	Gerhard MESTL - <i>Clariant Produkte (Deutschland) GmbH, Germany</i>	
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	David RUIZ-ALMOGUERA - <i>Institute of Advanced Materials (INAM), Spain</i>	
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	Heloisa RUSCHEL BORTOLINI - <i>Universidade de São Paulo, Brazil</i>	
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	Kosuke SAKAMOTO - <i>Department of Chemistry, Graduate School of Science, The University of Tokyo, , Japan</i>	
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	Evaristo SALAYA-GERONIMO - <i>Leibniz-Institute for Catalysis, Germany</i>	
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	Anna SAOTTA - <i>Alma Mater Studiorum-University of Bologna, Center for Chemical Catalysis "C3", Italy</i>	
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	Juan SEGUEL - <i>Pontificia Universidad Catolica, Chile</i>	
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	Kazuki SHUN - <i>Division of Materials and Manufacturing Science, Graduate School of Engineering, Osaka University, Japan</i>	

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	Tomohiro TSUDA - <i>Department of Materials Engineering Science, Graduate School of Engineering Science, Osaka University, Japan</i>	
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	Simon VERSTRAETEN - <i>KU Leuven, Belgium</i>	
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	Adrian WALKOWIAK - <i>Adam Mickiewicz University, Poland - Laboratoire Catalyse et Spectrochimie, Normandie Université, ENSICAEN, UNICAEN, France</i>	
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	Ying WAN - <i>Shanghai Normal University, China</i>	
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	Chuanming WANG - <i>SINOPEC Research Institute of Petroleum Processing Co., Ltd., China</i>	
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	Peipei XIAO - <i>Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan</i>	
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	Li XIAOYU - <i>Sinopec Research Institute of Petroleum Processing Co., LTD, China - CAS Key Laboratory of Science and Technology on Applied Catalysis Dalian Institute of Chemical Physics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China</i>	
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	Ya XU - <i>National Institute for Materials Science, Japan</i>	

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	Sho YAMAGUCHI - <i>Osaka University, Japan</i>	
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	Emmanuel IKWA - <i>IFP Energies Nouvelles, France - ENSL, CNRS, LCH UMR 5182, France</i>	
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	Andrea LAZZARINI - <i>Department of Physical and Chemical Sciences, University of L'Aquila, Italy</i>	
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	Jiasi LI - <i>Wolfson catalysis centre, University of Oxford, United Kingdom</i>	
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	Nataliia MARCHENKO - <i>Institut de recherches sur la catalyse et l'environnement, CNRS, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France</i>	
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	Kazuki MIYASHITA - <i>Tokyo Institute of Technology, Japan</i>	
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	Phillimon MODISHA - <i>North West University, South Africa</i>	
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	Maurice MOURAD - <i>R&D Solutions, Avantium, Netherlands</i>	
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	Benjamin MUTZ - <i>hte GmbH, Germany</i>	
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	Katsutoshi NAGAOKA - <i>Nagoya University, Japan</i>	

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	Diaz EVA - UNIVERSITY OF OVIEDO, Spain	
T22	THU-POST03-319 Improving the stability of hydrothermally derived carbon supported catalysts for ammonia reforming	
	Michael POSCHMANN - Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Germany	
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	Yi QIU - Laboratory of Catalysis and Catalytic Processes, Dipartimento di Energia, Politecnico di Milano, Italy	
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	Irene REY AGUILERA - UPV/EHU, Spain	
T22	THU-POST03-322 Dimethyl ether as vector for long-distance hydrogen transport: Indium oxide is a superior catalyst for DME steam reforming	
	Patrick SCHÜHLE - Institute of Chemical Reaction Engineering, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany	
T22	THU-POST03-323 Achieving Equilibrium Conversions for Low-Temperature Ammonia Decomposition via Electric Field-Enhancement	
	Jeong Gil SEO - Hanyang University, Korea (Republic of)	
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	M. Nasiruzzaman SHAIKH - King Fahd University of Petroleum and Minerals (KFUPM), Saudi Arabia	
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	Chyan Kyung SONG - Seoul National University, Korea (Republic of)	
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T22	THU-POST03-327 Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (LOHC) for hydrogen storage produced through power-to-gas (P2G) technology	
	Mikel TELLECHEA - <i>Leitat, Spain</i>	
T22	THU-POST03-328 Cracking of green ammonia to hydrogen using innovative catalyst and plasma technology	
	Frea VAN STEENWEGHEN - <i>Center for Surface Chemistry & Catalysis: Characterization and Application Team (COK-KAT), Belgium</i>	
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	Shilong CHEN - <i>Institute of Inorganic Chemistry, Kiel University, Germany</i>	
T22	THU-POST03-330 Promoting Co/AC for preventing methanation during NH3 decomposition	
	Franziska Luise WINTER - <i>Fraunhofer UMSICHT, Germany - Ruhr-University Bochum, Germany</i>	
T22	THU-POST03-331 Thermal encapsulation of nanocatalysts guided by the Tammann temperature enables excellent stability	
	Molly Meng-Jung LI - <i>Department of Applied Physics, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, China</i>	
T22	THU-POST03-332 Effect of Support Morphology on Activity of Ru/CeO2-based Catalysts for Ammonia Synthesis	
	Kiyoshi YAMAZAKI - <i>Toyota Central R&D Labs., Inc., Japan</i>	
T22	THU-POST03-333 Active pyrrolic nitrogen sites with low activation energy for catalytic NH3 decomposition	
	Dongpei YE - <i>wolfson catalysis centre, department of chemistry, University of Oxford, United Kingdom</i>	
T22	THU-POST03-334 Synthesis of Pt and Pt3Sn Supported Catalysts for Transfer Hydrogenation from perhydro-dibenzyltoluene to acetone	
	Smitkriti . - <i>University of Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France</i>	
T22	THU-POST03-335 Dehydrogenation of Alkanes on Highly Dispersed Pt Clusters	
	Mingxia SONG - <i>Key Laboratory for Green Chemical Technology of Ministry of Education, Tianjin University, China</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-338 Steering the location of active sites to boost methanol aromatization	

 Teng LI - *King Abdullah University of Science and Technology, Saudi Arabia*

T25 **THU-POST03-339 | Structural dynamics of Pt/CeO₂ catalysts and its use for accelerating the water gas shift reaction**

 Stephane LORIDANT - *Univ. Lyon, Université Claude Bernard-Lyon 1, CNRS, IRCELYON-UMR 5256, France*

T25 **THU-POST03-340 | Unravelling Morphology Effects in Methanol Decomposition with Pd/CeO₂ Catalysts**

 Ligia A. LUQUE-ÁLVAREZ - *Department of Inorganic Chemistry and Institute of Materials Science of Seville (CSIC – University of Seville), Spain*

T25 **THU-POST03-341 | Carbon-assisted method for the preparation of Fe/mesoporous SiO₂ FTS catalyst**

 Zhuang MA - *China University of Petroleum, China*

T25 **THU-POST03-342 | Fischer-Tropsch pathway for power-to-liquid kerosene production: An investigation into sustainable production**

 Hadis MARAMI - *Department of Chemical Engineering, Biotechnology and Environmental Technology, University of Southern Denmark, Denmark*

T25 **THU-POST03-343 | Chemical looping dry reforming of methane over Ni-modified WO₃/ZrO₂**

 Shinta MIYAZAKI - *Institute for Catalysis, Hokkaido University, Japan*

T25 **THU-POST03-344 | Low temperature and high pressure RWGS over Pd/TiO₂ catalysts: Effect of Pd incorporation method on activity enhancement**

 Carlos QUILIS - *Instituto de Catalisis y Petroleoquímica. Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Spain*

T25 **THU-POST03-345 | The conversion of methane to methanol with in situ generated H₂O₂**

 Fenglou NI - *Cardiff Catalysis Institute, Cardiff University, United Kingdom*

T25 **THU-POST03-346 | Photothermal Activation of Methane Dry Reforming on Perovskite-Supported Ni Catalysts**

 Andrea OSTI - *Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Padova, Italy*

T25 **THU-POST03-347 | Oxidative coupling of methane La₂O₃-based catalyst: Operando thermal inspection and spatial reactor analyses**

 Jose PALOMO - *Delft University of Technology, Netherlands*

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	Lucie RIVIERE - <i>IRCELYON-UMR 5256, France</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-349 Synergistic alloy effects in low-temperature methane dry reforming in an electric field	
	Clarence SAMPSON - <i>Waseda University, Japan</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-350 EFFECT OF Ce AND Mg PROMOTOR ON ACTIVITY OF Ni/g-Al₂O₃ CATALYSTS IN carbon dioxide REFORMING OF METHANE	
	Djamila SELLAM - <i>University, Algeria</i>	
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	Junjie SHI - <i>Institute of Coal Chemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China - Institute of Materials Chemistry, TU Wien, Austria</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-352 Kinetic assessment of CO hydrogenation over Fe/H-ZSM5 catalyst.	
	Lucas SILVA - <i>Polytechnic School of the University of São Paulo, Brazil</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-353 An investigation of the impact of niobia loading on platinum catalysts for sour water-gas shift reaction	
	Fabio PASSOS - <i>Universidade Federal Fluminense (UFF), Brazil</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-354 Cobalt supported on mesoporous niobia in the Fischer-Tropsch Synthesis	
	Hidila SILVA - <i>Federal University of Uberlandia - Faculty of Chemical Engineering -, Brazil</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-355 Tioresistance of Cu-Zn/HAP catalysts applied in water-gas shift reaction	
	Fabio PASSOS - <i>Universidade Federal Fluminense, Brazil</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-356 Enhanced oxygen carriers for chemical looping steam methane reforming prepared by physical mixing	
	Andrea STRAZZOLINI - <i>University of Udine, Italy</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-357 LaAlO₃ series perovskite catalysts for low-temperature OCM reaction in an electric field: effects of doping metal and H₂O supply	
	Harunobu TEDZUKA - <i>Waseda University, Japan</i>	

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	Fabiane TRINDADE - <i>Federal University of ABC, Brazil</i>	
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	Ida UOTILA - <i>VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, Finland</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-360 Selective oxidation of methane to formaldehyde over Pt-Ni and Pt-Cu nanoalloys	
	Singobile MAHLABA - <i>University of Cape Town, South Africa</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-361 Perovskite supported Pt-based catalysts for dry reforming of methane obtained from real leaching solutions of spent autocatalysts	
	Alessio VAROTTO - <i>Dept. Fundamental and Applied Sciences for Engineering (SBAI), Sapienza University of Rome, Italy - Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development-ENEA, Energy Technologies and Renewable Sources Department, Italy</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-362 ZnFexAl2-xO4 spinel supported PdZnβ catalyst for methanol steam reforming	
	Shaolong WAN - <i>Xiamen university, China</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-363 Mechanistic Insights into the Methanol-to-olefin Conversion in Zeolites	
	Chuanming WANG - <i>Sinopec Shanghai Research Institute of Petrochemical Technology Co., Ltd., China</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-364 Light alkane conversion through ammonia assisted reforming and dehydrogenation	
	Yizhi XIANG - <i>Mississippi State University, United States</i>	
T25	THU-POST03-365 Study on Methanol Oxidative Carbonylation to Dimethyl Carbonate Catalyzed by Nitrogen-doping Order Mesoporous Carbon	
	Zhong LI - <i>State Key Laboratory of Clean and Efficient Coal Utilization, Taiyuan University of Technology, China</i>	
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